

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D2.5 – Report on vision co-design methodology and its application for pilot shared visions

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

Document Information

Grant Number	Agreement	101096405	Acronym	UP2030
Full Title	Urban Planning and design ready for 2030			
Start Date	01/01/2023	Duration	36 months	
Project Website	https://up2030-he.eu/			
Deliverable	D2.5 - Report on vision co-design methodology and its application for pilot shared visions			
Work Package	WP2 – UPDating			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/12/2023	Actual	28/06/2024
Nature	R- Report	Dissemination Level	PU-Public	
Lead Beneficiary	TSPA (Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture)			
Author(s)	Aurelija Matulevičiūtė (TSPA), Frances Grout-Brown (TSPA), Cole Peters (TSPA), Majd Murad (TSPA), Liam Prentice (TSPA), Felicitas Leithner (Buro Happold), Jill Theobald (Buro Happold), Peter Scheibstock (Buro Happold).			
Reviewer(s)	Trinidad Fernandez (Fraunhofer), Catalina Diaz (Fraunhofer), Constanza Vera (USTUTT), Grigoris Kalogiannis (DRAXIS)			
Abstract	The report outlines a methodology for defining neighbourhood visions and adaptive pathways within a co-design framework. The methodology, supported by theoretical and practical insights, is adapted to be tested within various contexts, through UP2030 pilot cities. It emphasises the co-design approach and alignment of urban strategies with broader project goals. The report concludes with reflections on the methodology's initial applications and outlines future steps for its enhancement and replication and includes practical resources for process application.			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	17/11/2023	Draft of Table of Content	Design of table of contents	TSPA/Buro Happold
0.2	22/11/2023	Review of ToC	Review of table of content, executive summary, and alignment	Fraunhofer IAO
0.3	29/11/2023	1st Draft	1 st draft of the report	TSPA/Buro Happold
0.4	05/12/2023	1st Draft Review	Review of first draft	Fraunhofer IAO
0.5	11/12/2023	2nd Draft	2 nd draft of the report, incorporating suggestions	TSPA/Buro Happold

			from 1 st review and city updates	
0.6	15/12/2023	Coordination Review	Review of second draft by coordination team	DRAXIS
1.0	20/12/2023	Final Version	Final version ready for submission	TSPA/Buro Happold
2.0	28/06/2024	Final Updated Version	This version includes application process of developed methodology	TSPA

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EUROPEAN UNION or the EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The content, format, citations, and sources presented in this report are the sole responsibility of the author. While efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the content presented, there may be gaps in the information provided, or the information may become outdated over time. Readers are encouraged to independently verify any information presented in this report to ensure its accuracy and relevance to their specific needs or circumstances.

Copyright message

© UP2030 Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Contents

Executive summary.....	9
Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	9
Acronyms.....	11
1. Introduction.....	12
1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Document.....	12
1.2. Document Structure.....	12
1.3. Glossary for Co-visioning Process.....	14
2. Background.....	17
2.1. Context.....	17
2.2. Co-visioning Scope within UP2030.....	17
2.3. UP2030 Thematic Pillars Guiding the Co-visioning Process.....	19
2.4. Theoretical Framework.....	20
2.4.1. Co-Designing Approach.....	20
2.4.2. Visioning Process.....	21
2.4.3. Adaptive Pathways.....	21
2.5. Purpose of the Methodology for the Co-Design of Visioning and Adaptive Pathways.....	23
3. Methodology for Co-designing Vision and Adaptive Pathways.....	24
3.1. Overview of Methodology.....	24
3.1.1. Brief Introduction.....	24
3.1.2. Innovation Component – Co-Designing Visions and Adaptive Pathways.....	25
3.1.3. Rationale – Bridging Theory to Practice.....	26
3.1.4. Key Roles and Responsibilities.....	28
3.1.5. Engagement Toolkit.....	28
3.2. Process Milestones.....	29
3.2.1. Objectives Validation.....	30
3.2.2. Spatial Assessment.....	32
3.2.3. Pillar Visions.....	34
3.2.4. Pilot Vision.....	36
3.2.5. Action Prompt Development.....	39
3.2.6. Unpacking Objectives.....	41

3.2.7.	Comprehensive Assessment	44
3.2.8.	Adaptive Pathways Validation.....	45
3.3.	Guiding Principles for Practical Implementation.....	46
3.4.	Dissemination and Communication Aspects.....	48
4.	Integration with UP2030 Processes	50
4.1.	Links to Engagement Activities	50
4.2.	Links to Benchmarking Framework and KPIs	52
4.3.	Link to Prototyping Activities	53
5.	Application Process.....	54
5.1.	Reflections on Co-Visioning Methodology Application.....	54
5.2.	Application Process in Pilot Cities	56
5.2.1.	Belfast	56
5.2.2.	Budapest.....	64
5.2.3.	Granollers	69
5.2.4.	Istanbul	74
5.2.5.	Lisbon.....	79
5.2.6.	Milan.....	83
5.2.7.	Münster	89
5.2.8.	Rotterdam.....	95
5.2.9.	Thessaloniki	99
5.2.10.	Zagreb.....	105
6.	Conclusions and Next Steps.....	110
6.1.	Key observations.....	110
6.2.	Next Steps.....	111
7.	References	112
8.	Annex.....	115
8.1.	Guide for Visioning	115
8.2.	Guiding Questions for Workshop Implementation	124
8.2.1.	Co-Visioning.....	124
8.2.2.	Adaptive Pathways.....	126
8.3.	Action Prompts	127

8.3.1.	Belfast	127
8.3.2.	Budapest	131
8.3.3.	Granollers	133
8.3.4.	Milan	135
8.3.5.	Münster	137
8.3.6.	Thessaloniki	139
8.4.	Pilot Adaptive Pathways Pages	141
8.4.1.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Belfast.....	142
8.4.2.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Budapest	150
8.4.3.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Granollers	153
8.4.4.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Lisbon	156
8.4.5.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Milan	159
8.4.6.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Münster.....	161
8.4.7.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Thessaloniki	163
8.4.8.	Adaptive Pathways Page for Zagreb.....	165

Figures

Figure 1: UP2030 Pilot Cities (Source: UP2030, 2023)	17
Figure 2: The 5UP-Approach Conceptual Framework (UP2030, 2022)	18
Figure 3: Process Milestones: Vision and Adaptive Pathways Process (Source: TSPA, 2024)	25
Figure 4: Screenshot from the Engagement Toolkit Platform	29
Figure 5: Process Milestones: Vision and Adaptive Pathways Process (Source: TSPA, 2023)	30
Figure 6: Objectives Validation workshop at the UP2030 1st General Assembly on 15th November 2023, Lisbon (Source: TSPA, 2023)	32
Figure 7: Screenshot of the Community Maps Interface adjusted for UP2030	33
Figure 8: Integrated Spatial Analysis Workshop (Source: TSPA, 2023)	34
Figure 9: Photo and Example Template from the Exploratory Charrette (Source: TSPA, 2023).....	34
Figure 10: Thematic brainstorming method from the stakeholder engagement toolkit (Source: TSPA, 2023)	36
Figure 11: Vision Page Template (Source: TSPA, 2023).....	38
Figure 12 Template example for Unpacking Objectives Method.....	41
Figure 13: Template for unpacking objectives into actions (Source: TSPA, 2023).....	43

Figure 14: Diagram of the Four Project Phases (Source: UP2030 Project, 2022) 50

Figure 15 Co-visioning Process and Links to Other Activities (Source: TSPA, 2023) 51

Figure 16 Belfast Recommended Co-Visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023) 57

Figure 17 Screenshot of the Community Maps platform, showcasing projects related to the UP2030 activities, which could maximise or support project efforts..... 57

Figure 18 Results of Carbon Neutrality pillar vision brainstorming. Mentimeter tool 58

Figure 19 Example of one of the Future Newspaper headlines 58

Figure 20 Moment from the co-visioning workshop..... 59

Figure 21 Illustrations capturing ideas from the workshop discussions. 59

Figure 22 Vision for Belfast Pilot. Side A 61

Figure 23 Vision for Belfast Pilot. Side B 62

Figure 24 Results of survey conducted at the end of the vision workshop. 63

Figure 25 Belfast Recommended Co-Visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023) 65

Figure 26 Vision Workshop in Budapest 66

Figure 27 Vision for Budapest’s Pilot..... 67

Figure 28 Unpacking Objectives during the adaptive pathways workshop 68

Figure 29 Granollers Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023) 70

Figure 30 Vision workshop in Granollers..... 70

Figure 31 Figure 1 Results of problem tree method, conducted in vision workshop. 71

Figure 32 Preparation for the vision workshop..... 71

Figure 33 Digitised results from Common Vision mapping methods..... 72

Figure 34 Vision Page for Granollers Pilot..... 73

Figure 35 Istanbul’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023). 75

Figure 36 Moments from the vision workshop 76

Figure 37 Vision for Istanbul’s Pilot..... 77

Figure 38 Moments from the workshop. 78

Figure 39 Lisbon's Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)..... 80

Figure 40 Lisbon's workshop on co-visioning methods (Source: CML, 2024). 80

Figure 41 Vision workshop in Lisbon. 81

Figure 42 Vision for Lisbon's Pilot. 82

Figure 43 Milan’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)..... 84

Figure 44 Vision workshop in Milan. 85

Figure 45 Vision for Milan's Pilot..... 86

Figure 46 Results from Thematic Brainstorming method. 87

Figure 47 Münster’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023). 89

Figure 48 Vision for Münster's Pilot. 91

Figure 49 Brainstorming session during visioning workshop in Münster. 92

Figure 50 Digitised results from vision workshop on the co-creation of guidelines for a joint approach to climate friendly and energy efficient neighbourhood development. 93

Figure 51 Rotterdam’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)..... 96

Figure 52 Vision for Rotterdam's Pilot. 97

Figure 53 Co-visioning Roadmap with Suggested Engagement Methods for Thessaloniki (Source: TSPA, 2023)..... 99

Figure 54 Results from the spatial analysis milestone. 100

Figure 55 Highlights from the Spatial Assessment Workshops & Interviews. 100

Figure 56 Vision for Thessaloniki’s Pilot. 102

Figure 57 Highlights from the Adaptive Pathways workshop in Thessaloniki. 104

Figure 58 Template filled during the Adaptive Pathway Workshop: Waste Management | Recycling and waste management actions by local shops/restaurants/hotels. 105

Figure 59 Co-visioning Roadmap with Suggested Engagement Methods for Zagreb (Source: TSPA, 2023). 106

Figure 60 Vision for Zagreb’s pilot..... 107

Figure 61 Vision workshop in Zagreb. 109

Executive summary

The Report on Vision Co-design Methodology and Application for Pilot Shared Visions outlines a methodology to help cities define pilot visions and adaptive pathways for achieving carbon neutrality goals. At the heart of the UP2030 project lies an innovative methodology called the 5UP-approach (Update, Upskill, Upgrade, Upscale and Uptake), positioning cities at the forefront of the transition to carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition. Urban areas and neighbourhoods are seen as a crucial scale and intersection point for transformation. Therefore, the vision co-design methodology serves as a useful tool for cities in setting a clear direction for an impactful implementation at a pilot scale. In turn, valuable lessons can be derived for city-wide upscaling, both within and outside of UP2030.

The methodology leverages theoretical principles from co-design approach, visioning, and adaptive pathways to develop flexible and responsive urban strategies, engage multiple stakeholders, and promote a shared responsibility in the vision development. This report then provides an overview of the methodology, emphasizing innovation through co-design, the theoretical basis for the dual components of visioning and adaptive pathways, and the division into distinct milestones. Furthermore, the adaptability of the methodology across diverse urban contexts is highlighted, along with its potential for customisation in places with unique characteristics.

The report integrates theoretical principles with practical insights from participating cities and technical partners, to inform the development of a methodology that is practical for cities to use. Reflections on the co-visioning methodology's dissemination and communication strategies are then detailed, offering insights into what materials are to be provided, to whom, when, and for what purpose.

The section 'Application Process', describes how the methodology for co-visioning was applied in each pilot, detailing the process and reflections on it. This section also includes process outcome – pilot visions.

The report concludes with key observations and prospects, outlining steps. Materials such as a visioning glossary, guides, and other templates that have been used in the process are compiled in the Annex to provide a valuable resource for replicating this process across different urban landscapes.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with Fraunhofer, Mapping for Change (MfC), RCities, iCatalist, Buro Happold (BH), Universitat Internacional de Catalunya (UIC), Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), TU Delft and other partners from WP2, WP3 and WP4. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D 4.1 UP2030 Implementation Plan for the Pilot Cities 1</p> <p>D 4.3 Sustained Engagement Strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to Promote the Neutrality Vision in the UP2030 Pilots</p> <p>D 2.4 An Interactive Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement in Co-Design of Visions and Pathways towards Climate Neutrality</p>	<p>D 4.4 Report on Monitoring, Evaluation and KPI Validation in the SUP-approach Implementation Pilot 1</p> <p>D 3.6 Digital Planning and Design Tools for Climate Neutral Cities 1</p>
<p>M5 - Cities run first workshop on needs</p>	<p>M6 - Cities run second workshop on vision</p> <p>M7 - Cities establish user stories</p> <p>M10 - Cities run third workshop on action</p>

This document describes the methodology for co-designing visions and adaptive pathways to achieve carbon neutrality goals. It is tailored to serve a diverse group of stakeholders within the realm of sustainable urban development. It primarily targets cities administrations and practitioners, as well as the project consortium. Furthermore, it holds value for the broader public, including other European cities not directly involved in the project but interested in adopting the suggested methodologies. The initial version of this document was developed and delivered at the end of the first year of the project and updated with insights to the pilot process during the vision phase and its outcomes at M18 of the project. It encapsulates a year and a half worth of collaborative efforts and lays the groundwork for subsequent stages of the project.

The content of this report already was and will be shared through extensive stakeholder engagement and dissemination activities with WP6, ensuring that the methodology is not only disseminated but also practically tested with pilot cities (Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Münster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb). Beyond the formal publication, interactive workshops, masterclasses, and presentations at relevant conferences will be instrumental in promoting the methodology's adoption both within and beyond the project's scope. The aim is to foster a replicable model of co-designing city visions and adaptive pathways towards resilient, carbon neutral and just urban development.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AP	Adaptive Pathways
BH	Buro Happold
D	Deliverable
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LAA	Learning and Action Alliance(s)
M	Milestone
M#	Project month number
MfC	Mapping for Change
NBS	Nature-based Solutions
TF	Task Force
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
UCCRN	The Urban Climate Change Research Network
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València
WP(s)	Work package(s)

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Scope of the Document

The purpose of this document is to outline the methodology developed for co-designing shared pilot visions and adaptive pathways. It provides an overview of the theoretical background, explaining the key concepts upon which the methodology was shaped, as well as a detailed explanation of the methodology itself, including its key components and guiding principles, in a user-friendly manner. This approach enables the report to serve purposes beyond the UP2030 project scope, facilitating the upscaling of the process to cities outside the project consortium.

The scope of this document covers main sections: background, methodology for visions co-design, and reflections on its application process that includes process outcomes. The background provides an overview of UP2030 project and co-visioning activities within it, as well as the purpose of the task for developing the methodology for co-designing visions. The methodology section provides an in-depth overview of the chosen approach and how it can be contextualised for each pilot case. Meanwhile, the section on Application Process, (one finalised by cities) will provide reflections on how the methodology was implemented, and key outcomes.

1.2. Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction
 - Purpose and Scope of the Document
 - Document Structure
 - Glossary for Co-visioning Process
- ❖ Section 2 – Background
 - Context
 - Co-visioning Scope within UP2030
 - UP2030 Thematic Pillars Guiding the Co-visioning Process
 - Theoretical Framework
 - Purpose of the Methodology for the Co-design of Visioning and Adaptive Pathways
- ❖ Section 3 – Methodology for Co-designing Vision and Adaptive Pathways
 - Overview of the Methodology
 - Brief Introduction
 - Innovation Component – Co-designing Visions
 - Rationale - Bridging Theory to Practice

- Key Roles and Responsibilities
- Engagement Toolkit
- Process milestones
 - Objectives Validation
 - Spatial Assessment
 - Pillar Visions
 - Pilot Vision
 - Action Prompts Development
 - Unpacking Objectives
 - Comprehensive Assessment
 - Adaptive Pathways Validation
- Guiding Principles for Practical Implementation
- Dissemination and Communication Aspects
- ❖ Section 4 – Integration with UP2030 Processes
 - Links to Engagement Activities
 - Links to Benchmarking Framework and KPIs
 - Links to Prototyping Activities
- ❖ Section 5 - Application Process
 - Reflections on Co-Visioning Methodology Application
 - Application Process in Pilot Cities
 - Belfast
 - Budapest
 - Granollers
 - Istanbul
 - Lisbon
 - Milan
 - Münster
 - Rotterdam
 - Thessaloniki
 - Zagreb

- ❖ Section 6 – Conclusions and Next Steps
 - Key Observations
 - Next Steps
- ❖ Section 7 - References
- ❖ Section 8 - Annex
 - Guide for Visioning
 - Guiding Workshop Questions
 - Action Prompts
 - Pilot Adaptive Pathways Pages

1.3. Glossary for Co-visioning Process

Action - a specific activity, task, or intervention that helps to achieve was identified as needed for mitigating or adapting to climate change impacts in the pilot area and to overcome any identified barriers.

Adaptive Pathways - a sequence of actions required to achieve defined objectives and vision. Barriers, turning points, and vulnerabilities are considered in the sequencing of actions, which leads to alternative routes that can be taken in the future. This is a flexible and dynamic approach to implementing strategies, as it allows for adjustments and responses while addressing challenges and needs.

Adaptive Pathways Page - a concise document outlining the final result of a pilot's adaptive pathways process. It encapsulates actions, barriers, and a preferred strategy for achieving transformation, serving as a reference for the envisioned future state.

Co-Designing Process – a collaborative design process that aims to actively engage stakeholders and include diverse needs, and opinions into the outcome. A collaborative approach where designers, stakeholders, and users work together to create solutions ensuring that the outcome meets the needs of the users or community.

Engagement Method – a structured approach designed to involve various stakeholders in the planning process and capture diverse insights presented in the process and to ensure that all concerns and responses are reflected. E.g. *Integrated Spatial Analysis Method*

Engagement Toolkit - a comprehensive collection of methodologies or tools from UP2030 technical partners that were and will be used within the project. Each method within a Toolkit presents a method and details what and how to implement it. The toolkit was designed based on the methodology used for the UP2030 project, aiming to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their carbon neutrality targets by leveraging participatory urban planning and design. Toolkit is publicly accessible via the [UP2030 Toolkit for stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality](#).

(Governance) Barriers – refers to the obstacles and challenges that hinder the effective implementation of policies, programs or initiatives and which were identified during the needs and barriers assessment steps.

Implementation Roadmaps – a translation of visions to specific actions to obtain the delivery of prototyping actions in the tested neighbourhood environments (Fernandez et al., 2023).

Liaison(s) - Each Pilot City is assigned a City Liaison partner. The Liaisons are research/technical partners of the project from the same country as the pilot city for logistical and language reasons, who help the cities engage more efficiently and deeper with the project through direct support. Previous project experience has shown this is a strong asset for the integration of the city in projects and better demonstrators (UP2030, 2022).

Vision Milestone: The visioning process is made up of milestones, which are significant stages to be completed within the process. The milestones build upon each other to produce the final outcomes of the visioning and adaptive pathways. Each milestone includes recommendations to help achieve that specific stage of the process.

Monitoring KPIs - quantifiable measures to evaluate the success and achievements of a system. Within UP2030, KPIs will be determined to measure these achievements and study the impact of actions within the project's lifetime (Ammouriova & Tsertsvadze, 2023).

Need(s) - (in the context of integrated spatial analysis) what is considered necessary for mitigating or adapting to climate change impacts in the pilot area, at a spatial scale.

Barrier(s) - (in the context of the integrated spatial analysis) an obstacle to achieving what was identified as needed for mitigating or adapting to climate change impacts in the pilot area.

Opportunity(-ies) - (in the context of the integrated spatial analysis) what you see as an opportunity or strength (e.g., natural capital, participation, digitization) in the pilot area to achieving what was identified as needed for mitigating or adapting to climate change impacts. E.g. Need: green infrastructure Opportunity: opportunity to connect three existing parks in the pilot area; Barrier: lack of sustainable financing to develop and maintain green infrastructure; Action: (a specific action that supports in arriving at sustainable financing mechanisms).

Pilot Objectives - are clearly defined targets that encapsulate the city's aspirations towards achieving carbon neutrality in a specific pilot area. These objectives serve as guiding principles, articulating the envisioned outcomes that align with the broader ambitions of the project. Rather than detailing the specific actions or strategies, these objectives focus on the end goals, exemplifying what the city aims to accomplish in terms of environmental sustainability and carbon neutrality. E.g. Achieving a 30% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in the pilot area by 2030).

Pilot Vision - a clear, aspirational statement that outlines desired future scenarios which serves to guide short-term actions and long-term strategies towards sustainable, inclusive, and resilient urban development. The comprehensive future-oriented framework engages various stakeholders, leverages innovative and technological solutions, and provides a holistic approach to urban development. A vision provides a crucial guiding framework for its realisation. E.g. Melbourne's Climate 2050 Strategy statement: "In 2050, Melbourne is a thriving, resilient, zero-emissions city that enhances and protects its natural environment, embraces social inclusion and activation, demonstrates leadership, and facilitates the transition to a new climate economy."

Pillar Vision - it represents a thematic element within the overarching Pilot Vision, focusing on a specific realm crucial to achieving inclusive, carbon neutral and resilient urban development. Each Pillar Vision

addresses distinct, yet interconnected, aspects of urban development and provides detailed, aspirational, objectives which will guide actions and decision-making within its sphere.

- **Pillar for Carbon Neutrality** aims to establish a strategic framework for achieving net zero carbon footprint vision within pilot area
- **Pillar for Resilience** aims to develop a foundation to enhance the capacity to anticipate, withstand, prepare and adapt to various challenges (environmental, social, economic)
- **Pillar for Just Transition** aims to ensure inclusive and equitable progress within the pilot area as it navigates towards a resilient and carbon-neutral vision. E.g. Resilience Vision Pillar: "Envisioning a Future-Ready, Adaptive Community"

Project Pillar - thematic fields within which targets and implementation strategies are developed to guide cities through socio-technical transitions to meet their ambitions. The three project pillars are carbon neutrality, climate resilience and just transition.

Risks - potential for adverse outcomes or uncertainties that could impact the success and sustainability of an action or project. This includes environmental, social, economic, and infrastructural vulnerabilities that cities face.

Spatial Analysis - a method used to analyse and interpret spatial components, where stakeholders collaboratively engage in identifying, mapping, and assessing spatial issues and opportunities within a specific area or community. Without relying on advanced GIS tools, this approach emphasizes direct stakeholder involvement, utilizing simpler, more accessible methods such as physical maps, drawings, or other visual aids.

UP2030 Project Terminology - identification of different development trajectories, based on adaptation and transformation of the current system, for addressing a carbon-neutral future.

Vision Page - represents a concise document outlining the desired outcome of a pilot visioning process. It captures the vision statement, pillar visions and objectives, for the future that the visioning process seeks to achieve.

2. Background

2.1. Context

UP2030 aims to support cities in facilitating the socio-technical transitions necessary to achieve their carbon neutrality goals through the integration of urban planning and design. This involves understanding and utilising urban planning and design as tools to enhance the quality of life in urban communities. The focus on liveability connects these approaches to providing various socio-environmental benefits, especially at the neighbourhood level. The strategic emphasis on piloting and prototyping in neighbourhoods is driven by their significance in problem-solving, investment, and climate innovation within cities. This localised testing serves as a valuable learning ground for potential city-wide implementation and long-term upscaling of the project results.

As part of the consortium, ten European cities and one observer outside the EU are participating and bringing the project results directly into practice, providing synergies between different cities and testing developed concepts which then can be subsequently used as a model for replication and implementation through cities outside of the current project consortium. Further dissemination activities through WP6 as well as the observing role of Rio this will be supported.

The following cities are part of the consortium: Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Münster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb, with Rio de Janeiro as an observer city. Each city is to implement the UP2030 project in a pilot area, which are generally at a neighbourhood or site-level scale.

Figure 1: UP2030 Pilot Cities (Source: UP2030, 2023)

2.2. Co-visioning Scope within UP2030

UP2030 is following an innovative methodology called the 5UP approach which positions the city at the centre of leading the transition towards carbon neutrality. With urban areas and neighbourhoods being a crucial scale and intersection point for transformation, the overall scope of this approach is to support cities in:

- **UP-dating** those policies, codes, regulations that need to be left behind to make room for the new vision,
- **UP-skilling**, through building the capacities of the entire city stakeholder ecosystem that shall deliver actions,
- **UP-grading**, through the development of solution prototypes (digital and physical) at selected neighbourhoods,
- **UP-scaling** to achieve city-wide impact by shaping the enabling governance arrangements and matching project portfolios to financial resources, and
- **UP-taking**, by engaging with the Mission and sharing best practices across European cities. (CINEA, 2023, p. 76).

Figure 2: The 5UP-Approach Conceptual Framework (UP2030, 2022)

Co-creating pilot visions is a dynamic process within the 5UP approach that involves a comprehensive analysis to identify areas in need of updates. Going beyond analysis, this approach actively shapes and co-creates a vision for the future of the pilots and delineates the complex strategies to achieve it. This forward-looking aspect of visioning aligns with the core tenets of the 5UP approach described above.

Shaping pilot visions plays a key role in the 'UP-dating' phase by ensuring that the pilot projects are not hindered by outdated frameworks but instead are in line with the overarching goals of UP2030. Beyond that, visioning is also instrumental in the 'UP-skilling' phase, focusing on building capacities of the entire city stakeholder ecosystem. The visions serve as a guiding force that informs and inspires the various stakeholders involved in the pilot projects. It provides a clear direction for the development of skills and knowledge necessary for effective implementation. Additionally, the visioning process sets the stage for the subsequent phases of the 5UP approach, including 'UP-grading', 'UP-scaling', and 'UP-taking'. Well-defined visions and strategies for pilot projects become the foundations for the development of

implementation measures, the scaling-up of successful initiatives to achieve city-wide impact, and the dissemination of best practices across European cities.

In essence, visioning for pilot projects under the 5UP approach is crucial for establishing a forward-thinking framework, aligning stakeholders, and ensuring that the subsequent phases of the methodology unfold in an integrated and aligned manner, leading to comprehensive and impactful urban development following the overall UP2030 objectives.

2.3. UP2030 Thematic Pillars Guiding the Co-visioning Process

Within the UP2030 project, *project pillars* serve as thematic fields within which targets, and implementation strategies are developed to guide cities through socio-technical transitions to meet their ambitions. The three project pillars are carbon neutrality, climate resilience, and just transition and are defined as follows:

- **Carbon Neutrality:** With cities accounting for 75% of global CO₂ emissions (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022), climate mitigation is heavily dependent on urban action. The project pillar of carbon neutrality targets the reduction of greenhouse gases associated with a city, accounted for in the form of CO₂ emissions, to achieve carbon neutrality.
- **Climate Resilience:** Generally, city resilience is defined as a city's 'capacity to survive, adapt and thrive no matter what kinds of chronic stresses or acute shocks they experience' (Rockefeller Foundation & Arup, 2014). With a focus on climate resilience, this project pillar targets to increase the cities' capacity to react, respond, adapt, or transform in the face of climate change related events such as droughts, floods or heat stress.
- **Just Transition:** This project pillar aims for the reduction of socio-economic vulnerability within the anticipated urban transformation. This includes impacts of decarbonisation and resilience actions and the consideration of how communities are facing these transformations.

The above listed definitions are in line with the detailed conceptual review of the three project pillars and their dimensions of implementation that can be found in deliverable D2.2 UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities.

These project pillars were defined at an early stage of the project and aim to ensure a holistic development of the city pilots. The visioning approach therefore aims to integrate the three thematic pillars of UP2030. This integration serves to ensure a holistic approach also to the pilot visioning. While the individual steps of the visioning process are outlined in Section 3 of this report, the following section serves to detail how the project pillars are integrated into the visioning process at different steps. Within the visioning process, certain measures (such as aligning objectives with three pillars and identifying pillar visions) are taken to ensure the development of the pilot vision as a holistic vision, considering all three project pillars.

Cities are guided to align their pilot objectives with the three pillars as they work through visioning and adaptive pathways process milestones. By using curated templates and methods, they develop pillar-specific visions, targets, and actions for implementation. The benchmarking framework, developed as part of WP2 (Task 2.2 Benchmarking against the state of the art in urban planning and design) supports cities in the identification of strategies to implementing climate actions on the ground. This framework

emphasises carbon-neutral, resilient, and just transitions, enhancing the holistic development of the visioning process across the project's three pillars. A more in-depth explanation of the co-visioning process alignment with other inputs and activities is further elaborated in Section 4.

2.4. Theoretical Framework

The following section presents a concise overview and theoretical foundation of the key components that make up the methodology for co-designing pilot visions and adaptive pathways: co-design approach, visioning, and adaptive pathways. This section aims to provide readers with an understanding of the core concepts and frameworks that inform the development of a methodology that fosters inclusive and innovative solutions.

2.4.1. Co-Designing Approach

Co-design is a creative and inclusive approach that actively involves a broad spectrum of stakeholders in the design process to address specific community challenges and needs. This approach blends expert knowledge to design spaces that respond to community needs to enable the inclusion of life experiences, views, and skills from diverse perspectives. The consistent involvement of stakeholders in the design process ensures that the result meets their needs. Co-design is grounded in the philosophy that all stakeholders are experts in their own right and thus should collaborate as equals with professional designers. The stakeholders' possession of first-hand experience and knowledge of their own context and needs can contribute unique insights that significantly enhance the design process (Simonsen & Robertson, 2013). Co-design is an engagement-driven process, where activities such as workshops, brainstorming sessions, prototyping, and testing aim to create more satisfactory, efficient and effective, products, systems, or plans (Steen et al., 2011). In terms of urban planning, it aims to promote active participation and shared decision-making and has its roots in participatory planning methods pioneered by architects like John F. C. Turner in the 1960s (Turner, 1976).

Originally known as cooperative design, the concept originated in Scandinavian countries during the 1960s and 1970s, a period when trade unions sought to have a say in the design process of technologies that affected their work in response to being previously excluded from such discussions. After introducing it in the United States, co-design started being referred to as 'participatory design' (Sundblad, 2011).

Co-designing methods may involve various degrees of participation, ranging from collaboration between different stakeholders to the active involvement of the community in the design process. According to recent literature, there is a growing interest in co-designing methods to achieve urban innovation and planning, with a focus on shared responses to the social, environmental, and economic challenges in contemporary urbanism (Tewdwr-Jones & Wilson, 2022). Billger (Billger et al., 2020) emphasizes that co-designing methods should not only consult stakeholders but actively involve them in all phases of the design process. Their study on the development of a serious game for collaborative urban sanitation planning highlighted the importance of iterative testing and collaboration with relevant stakeholders to create an engaging and effective tool for knowledge sharing and attitude change. Furthermore, research on the development of a virtual care guidance document emphasized the rapid co-design process that involved consultation sessions, surveys, and literature review to support health and community service providers, older adults and caregivers during the COVID-19 pandemic (Glover et al., 2023).

The co-design approach offers multifaceted benefits for planning, especially in the context of carbon neutrality strategies. The engagement of diverse groups of stakeholders can lead to the development of comprehensive and context-sensitive solutions (Simonsen & Robertson 2013). The pooling of varied expertise inherent to this approach can foster innovative solutions that are both sustainable and socially inclusive (Steen et al., 2011). Furthermore, involving community members ensures that local knowledge and values are integrated into climate action plans, leading to increased community buy-in and enhanced feasibility of implementation (Simonsen & Robertson, 2012). Additionally, co-design processes can facilitate a shared understanding and alignment of goals among stakeholders, which is crucial for the complex, interdisciplinary challenge of achieving carbon neutrality (Manzini, 2015).

2.4.2. Visioning Process

Visioning in the planning context refers to the process of developing a vision for a community, organisation, or project. The vision serves as a guiding image or statement that describes the desired future or outcome. Visioning is a concept that emerged mainly in the USA in the 1980s and 1990s, representing a strategic approach to long-term city development, aiming to outline a clear and formalised future direction for urban areas over a span of 25 years or more. This approach is used globally in both planning practice and theory, although its concepts have often been applied without critical examination (Shiple, 2000). The methods of visioning have evolved to integrate various planning methods such as inclusive scenario building, storytelling, and the integration of sophisticated spatial models into public planning processes, making a shift towards more participative planning practices (Pelling et al., 2023).

In the realm of planning, visioning can be segmented into two interrelated streams: substantive and procedural. Substantive visioning delves into the essence of the vision - laying out precise objectives and the envisioned accomplishments that a community or entity strives for. It zeroes in on the "what"—the concrete and aspirational results that the planning endeavours to bring into existence. Conversely, procedural visioning is oriented towards the "how"—the assortment of strategies and steps taken to conceive and convey a vision. It advocates for a collaborative approach, establishing not just the desired outcomes but also the strategic pathway to attain those objectives, thereby framing both the end goal and the journey toward it (Minowitz, 2012).

A study published in 2023 explores a successful implementation of visioning in planning (Jittrapirom et al., 2023), the paper proposed an integrated robust, and generative framework for visioning future transport systems, aiming to address the challenges of urban transport and develop a shared vision for the future. The framework involved a comprehensive approach to envisioning future transport systems, taking into account factors such as sustainability, efficiency, and accessibility. By engaging stakeholders in combination with using advanced modelling and scenario planning techniques, the study demonstrates how visioning can be effectively applied to address complex planning challenges and create a shared vision for the future of a city's transport system.

2.4.3. Adaptive Pathways

Adaptive pathways — also known as adaptation pathways — began being conceptualized in 2010 as a strategic approach to managing and planning for uncertain futures, particularly in the context of climate change and environmental management. Adaptation pathways involve analytical processes to explore and sequence potential actions in response to external developments over time. This approach addresses uncertainty by incorporating the flexibility of considering a wide range of future scenarios in the context of the established vision. While being similar to other decision-making tools under uncertainty such as

decision trees, adaptation pathways put a bigger emphasis on planning and adjusting over time and prioritise learning and flexibility, and adaptation pathways may include decision trees as one of the many tools to inform the sequencing of actions (Barnett et al., 2015).

Adaptive pathways are conceptualized within three overlapping categories (Werners et al., 2021). The first, performance threshold-oriented, prioritizes the ordering of adaptation actions based on different projected scenarios within a specific system, where actions are aligned with measurable targets reflecting established values. Originating in environments rich in data, these approaches benefit from clear objectives and decisive leadership. The second category, multi-stakeholder-oriented, underscores the social and institutional dynamics of adaptation, incorporating diverse influences and perspectives, including non-scientific insights, to foster collaborative learning and enhance adaptive planning capacities. Lastly, transformation-oriented pathways consider more radical shifts, suggesting strategic directions that diverge from current value systems and question the adequacy of present system performance, thus not merely supporting but potentially altering the status quo.

Adaptive pathways enhance strategic planning by addressing the intricate and unpredictable nature of future scenarios, especially relevant for climate change which is a dynamic process with evolving impacts. While traditional scenario planning evaluates different future outcomes based on key uncertainties, forming a scenario matrix with various potential developments, it usually prepares for a limited set of possible futures. In contrast, adaptive pathways emphasise ongoing adaptability, allowing plans to evolve with new information. This method stands out from more rigid planning strategies by incorporating decision points that facilitate the adjustment of actions over time, providing sustained flexibility. The flexibility and forward-looking aspect of adaptive pathways that anticipate and respond to changes over time has a significant contribution to resilience and sustainability. This allows systems whether social, ecological, or spatial to absorb disturbances while undergoing change to retain essentially the same function and structure, or even to transform and improve the structure into a new stable state that resembles the essence of the original system, despite the previously unforeseen changes (Haasnoot et al., 2013). Sustainability is enhanced through adaptive pathways by ensuring that decisions made today do not preclude future options but instead support enduring ecological balance and resource availability (Wise et al., 2014).

The inherent long-term planning function of adaptive pathways under uncertainties places the temporal dimension at the centre of this approach. The time needed to develop and implement adaptive pathways varies significantly depending on the context, guiding vision, and level of uncertainty involved. The development and implementation of adaptive pathways comprise several overarching phases such as an analytical phase, strategic phase, and operational phase, each of which requires significant time to develop, implement, and adjust. For example, a study on coastal adaptation strategies in New Zealand found that developing a 100-year coastal adaptation strategy using dynamic adaptive pathways and real options analysis required ongoing political leadership and governance with monitoring systems that can manage the adaptive process over long timeframes (Lawrence et al., 2019).

Incorporating adaptive pathways in planning and decision-making is complex due to the unpredictability of forecasting future conditions. This uncertainty inherent to long-term planning in the context of challenges such as climate change often requires substantial adjustments to, or complete revision of, initial plans in response to new information (Walker et al., 2013). The flexibility needed to accommodate such changes, while necessary, can also be resource-demanding and lead to fatigue from constant revision (Haasnoot et al., 2013). Path dependency is another concern, with early decisions potentially constraining

future options and leading to less effective strategies as circumstances evolve (Lawrence & Haasnoot, 2017). Actions intended to address specific risks may inadvertently lead to maladaptation, increasing vulnerabilities in other areas or future scenarios (Barnett & O'Neill, 2010). Adaptive pathways methodologies are theoretically intended to grapple with these challenges.

2.5. Purpose of the Methodology for the Co-Design of Visioning and Adaptive Pathways

Cities have historically followed a project-by-project decarbonisation approach, however there is a need to shift towards a strategy-based approach. Furthermore, one of the major problems is the disconnect between strategy-making and implementation, whereby there is a need to connect strategy to the fast deployment of high-impact transformational change (UP2030, 2022). The use of visions and adaptive pathways supports in making this connection.

Visioning coupled with the development of adaptive pathways is an important strategic pairing, whereby pathways are constructed towards an aspirational vision of what could be based on participatory measures. This pairing is especially appropriate in multi-driver contexts where a need for transformational change has been identified, as is the case of the multi-pilot and co-design context of UP2030 (Werners et al., 2021).

The overall aim of visioning within UP2030 is to co-design holistic carbon neutrality blueprints specific to each pilot context that align with the aspirations of the stakeholders. Based on the city's pilot objectives and vision, adaptive pathways are then essential for creating a flexible strategy that can evolve with changing circumstances, ensuring an effective and resilient implementation towards a sustainable urban future.

This also feeds back into the overall success of the UP2030 project: as visions serve as instruments that assist cities in pursuing their goals with precision and alignment among different stakeholders, they enable the early implementation of overarching UP2030 objectives in pilot projects. This facilitates the evaluation of the success of individual measures, allowing for their transfer to other contexts or cities. In essence, the use of visions acts as a strategic guide, not only helping cities achieve their specific immediate goals but also contributing to the broader, long-term objectives outlined in UP2030.

Furthermore, UP2030's overall objective is to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their carbon neutrality targets. Therefore, the outcome of Task 2.4 Co-designing pilot shared visions and adaptive pathways for transformation does not lie solely in co-designing pilot-shared visions and adaptive pathways for transformation, but also in the development of a methodology that will meaningfully support cities outside UP2030 in doing so. The methodology serves as a useful tool for cities in setting a clear direction for an impactful implementation at a pilot scale. In turn, valuable lessons can be derived for city-wide upscaling, both within and outside of UP2030.

3. Methodology for Co-designing Vision and Adaptive Pathways

3.1. Overview of Methodology

The following sections of the report describe the methodology for co-designing pilot-shared visions and adaptive pathways. The methodology, unique for UP2030, is not only grounded in a theoretical framework of co-design, visioning, and adaptive pathways described in Section 2.4 but is also tailored based on the authors' expertise and feedback from the pilot cities. By summarizing the developed methodology, this document illustrates its practical and dynamic nature, reflecting the collaborative inputs and adjustments made during the process. Furthermore, it elaborates on the roles played by cities, liaisons, and technical partners in implementing this adaptive and co-creative approach. Detailed explanations are provided for each vision milestone, including their recommended engagement methods and the connection to other critical inputs such as needs assessment, benchmarking, key performance indicators (KPIs), and tool selection. This helps to contextualize the visioning process as part of a broader mission toward carbon neutrality and transformational change. Lastly, the report underscores the guiding principles that make the methodology practical for implementation in the pilot settings.

3.1.1. Brief Introduction

The co-visioning methodology outlined in the report is divided into two primary components: visioning and adaptive pathways (Figure 3). The division into the two components is strategic: Visioning serves as the foundational stage where collective aspirations are articulated and to understand *what the future scenario for the cities should be*, while adaptive pathways are about translating these aspirations into actionable and flexible steps on *what needs to be done to get there*. This divide is essential to reflect the dynamic nature of urban development, which requires not only direction but also the ability to adapt to changing circumstances. Combining the 'what' and 'how' components in visioning also reflects the theoretical framework of substantive and procedural visioning (Minowitz, 2012).

Within each of these key components, the approach is further granulated into milestones, where each is accompanied by specific engagement methods. Breaking the process down into smaller steps ensures that at each stage of the process, stakeholders are engaged meaningfully, and their contributions are mapped against clear targets. By breaking down the process into manageable units, the methodology allows for adjustments that are sensitive to the local context and responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities. Furthermore, just as the theoretical frameworks emphasised how adaptive pathways stand out from more rigid planning strategies by providing sustained flexibility, the use of milestones looks to mirror this idea of responding to context and accounting for flexibility.

Figure 3: Process Milestones: Vision and Adaptive Pathways Process (Source: TSPA, 2024)

The visioning component is made up of the following suggested milestones:

- **Validation of pilot objectives:** to form a base on which to start the visioning process.
- **Spatial assessment:** to spatially identify ongoing projects, strengths, and opportunities, within pilot area and reveal synergies among them.
- **Definition of pillar visions:** to contextualise carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition to themes specific to the pilot context to facilitate the process for shaping the holistic vision.
- **Definition of pilot vision:** to form a holistic vision statement about the desired future scenario for the pilot area.

The adaptive pathways component is made up of the following suggested milestones:

- **Action Prompts Development:** To prepare for the objective unpacking session, generate targeted prompts to guide discussions and identify actions in urban planning, governance, finance, and engagement. This step integrates the benchmarking filter to align with best practices for carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition.
- **Unpacking Objectives:** to identify operative actions, risks and alternative activities while unpacking objectives.
- **Comprehensive assessment:** to leverage technical expert knowledge to transform the content into draft adaptive pathways.
- **Validation of adaptive pathways:** to provide a final round of validation and iteration for this phase.

3.1.2. Innovation Component – Co-Designing Visions and Adaptive Pathways

The methodology for visioning is anchored in co-design principles that are integrated at every stage, ensuring that the process involves relevant key stakeholders directly, rather than outsourced to consultants as common in planning practice. As described, the proposal 'UP2030 sees citizens as an

integral part of the transition as they shall become agents of change' (UP2030, 2022). This inclusive approach allows for collectively defining visions and pathways for transformation and becomes an instrument for decision-making. As further explained in Section 2.4.1, the co-design component not only fosters a sense of ownership among participants but also ensures that the solutions are relevant and effectively address the unique challenges of the environment in which they are applied (Simonsen & Robertson, 2013).

The strong focus on co-design principles throughout the entire visioning process is what makes the approach innovative. Innovation at this stage is not only in the sense of the outcomes but also in the approach to the process. The goal of UP2030 is to innovate the typical planning practice by establishing a sustained engagement strategy from the very beginning of the project and using it as a tool for co-creation and distributing decision power among key stakeholders. The methodology was thoroughly crafted to be accessible to a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, enhancing engagement and collaboration at every step. There is a deliberate effort to design a process that is inclusive and accessible, built upon a deep local understanding of the context, yet supported by urban professionals with international expertise.

3.1.3. Rationale – Bridging Theory to Practice

The development of the methodology for co-designing pilot visions and adaptive pathways to reach carbon neutrality targets was grounded in theoretical foundations (Section 2.4), in practical implications relative to UP2030 (Section 3.3), and with significant consideration for applicability beyond UP2030. This section briefly describes the theoretical influences in the development of the main components of the methodology.

The creation of the specific and divided milestones was influenced by the theoretical backing that pathways benefit from clear objectives, especially from incorporating diverse influences and perspectives (Haasnoot et al., 2013). Each milestone has a certain output from which the visioning and adaptive pathways are built, along with engagement methods that reflect the diversity of perspectives needed to shape these outputs. In the context of UP2030, since the first year of the project was dedicated to the analysis of barriers and needs, the understanding of objectives has evolved. Therefore, using the validation of existing pilot objectives as the first milestone within the visioning component looks to establish a clear and up-to-date base to shape both, the visions and adaptive pathways.

For the adaptive pathways' component, the action prompts development (preparation for the unpacking objectives session) is a necessary step for ensuring the targeted and comprehensive identification of actions. Each objective is assessed and set of prompts are created to address topics of governance, policy, financing, engagement and spatial interventions. The intention of prompts is to address the need stated in the literature to avoid maladaptive consequences within the suggested actions and interventions (Walker et al., 2013). Due to the variety of involved stakeholders' expertise and often different professional views towards the same notions, prompts help to guide the discussion towards operative actions, ensuring that key topics are covered. The benchmarking filter, developed in the task T2.2, supports efforts on prompts identification.

The unpacking objectives exercise which centres around the identification and sequencing of actions and risk at the pilot scale, is a core exercise for gathering the input from the stakeholders. As theory suggests, the integration of diverse expertise and knowledge in the development of adaptive pathways has the potential to enhance the quality of decisions (Werners et al., 2021). It allows for a more comprehensive

output of actions and risks at the outset of the adaptive pathways' development, which will increase the quality and flexibility of decisions to be made in the future.

It is also important to mention that in the context of UP2030, the approach and outcomes of adaptive pathways was altered to the specific project scope, but more importantly, to pilot neighbourhoods' needs. A core element of adaptive pathways is flexibility and the ability to anticipate and respond to changes over time has a significant contribution to resilience and sustainability (reference to the section 2.4.3) which requires multiple adjustments and revisions over the time. Therefore, given the project timeline and contexts (focus on socio-technological transitions), the adaptive pathways conducted within the project focus rather on creating the solid foundation – initial version of adaptive pathways, which can be adjusted and further detailed, over the period. (Walker et al., 2013). Due to this fact, the focus is on identifying operative actions and risks in connection to the objectives to address needed transformation and start building the capacity of city administrations for planning future transitions. While a significant component of the literature points towards adaptive pathways use-cases which focus primarily on very long time scales and higher-level strategy in the context of uncertainty, the approach being used here in UP2030 is significantly condensed. The rationale behind such is that the context within UP2030, grapples with the co-visioning and planning of carbon-neutral, resilient, and just pilot projects. While the uncertainty and complexity does not stem from time scales of decades and centuries – as climate change necessitates short-term urgency – it instead derives from the complex interdisciplinarity and uncertainty regarding implementation in pilot scale settings. Hence, the methodology of adaptive pathways is contextualised and grounded to a tangible scale that aims to help cities navigate their unique processes of working towards carbon neutral pilots.

In a general sense, the methodology for co-designing pilot visions and adaptive pathways, is based on urban planning and design principles. The discipline allows to take into consideration the complexity of urban systems while also promoting tangible and intangible interventions. With specific reference to applying the urban planning and design approach of UP2030 to the co-visioning and adaptive pathways process, it will mean embedding spatial planning and design in the recommended engagement methods, recognising the interdisciplinary nature of urban planning and design by bringing together a range of stakeholders needed within the recommended methods, aligning the methodology with the three pillars of carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition to form a holistic vision, and representing both structural (physical) and non-structural (intangible) interventions within the adaptive pathways.

Unique to the UP2030 framework is the definition of thematic pillars, further described in Section 2.3. This process aids in contextualising resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition, and helps to facilitate the process of shaping a holistic vision.

A defined vision lays the groundwork for the definition of adaptive pathways, while the objectives act as a guide for action identification. These actions are then evaluated in conjunction with previously identified barriers (e.g., lack of data, lack of financing), contributing to the formulation of a preliminary adaptive pathway. The first draft co-designed by cities' stakeholders will then be analysed and, if needed, further elaborated by the technical partners, to ensure that the strategy is comprehensive and technically sound. To assess the preliminary draft of adaptive pathways, partners also plan to employ filter for actions, developed under D2.2. The filter acts as a comprehensive guide to ensure that identified actions are aligning with three project pillars (resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition) but also, does not lead to maladaptive space.

The full methodology for co-designing visions and adaptive pathways is defined in step-by-step manner in the Section 3.2. It includes detail explanation of each process milestone, it's outcomes as well as suggested engagement methods.

3.1.4. Key Roles and Responsibilities

The UP2030 project operates with a clear delineation of responsibilities among its participants throughout different project steps. As co-design approach is central to UP2030 processes, cities are at the centre of focus, having the best overview of the pilot area and relevant stakeholders needs. In this case, they are not mere observers, but active participants in the process, with their challenges and observations being pivotal to the project's direction. Therefore, it was essential to provide a link between cities and technical partners, to enable more effective communication and ease the load cities will face. For that reason, liaisons, selected research or technical partner from the same country as the pilot city, have been assigned to this role at the beginning of project. They serve as vital connectors between the cities and the project team and play a significant support role in facilitating the workshops with city representatives, help the cities engage more efficiently and deeper within the project. For this specific reason, authors for co-visioning methodology have developed set of materials, such as 'Guide for Co-visioning' as a main reference for the process, and a program for introduction and capacity training with liaisons to effectively introduce the concept and other existing materials to support the implementation of this methodology.

Finally, technical partners bring their expertise by offering guidance and defining a suggested framework for the methodology. Their role is crucial in ensuring that the project's approach is professionally and technically sound, as well as innovative.

When extending the co-visioning scope beyond the UP2030 framework, cities and their engaged stakeholders are identified as pivotal in adopting the methodology. Their role expands to contextualising co-visioning process and delineating transformative pathways toward achieving the ambitious targets of carbon neutrality and resilience.

3.1.5. Engagement Toolkit

Each one of the co-visioning process milestones includes a set of recommendations for its implementation. Most of which consist of certain engagement methods which has been collected from UP2030 partners. The collection of engagement methods, unique to UP2030, known as [Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality](#), was developed by MfC with support of TSPA and is further referenced in document *D2.4 Interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality*. (Covernton et al., 2023)

Figure 4: Screenshot from the Engagement Toolkit Platform

The choice of combining engagement methods and creating a publicly assessable database aims to make collaboration of multiple stakeholders more seamless. It is also crucial to point out that the engagement methods listed within the Toolkit and employed at the co-visioning process are not experimental; they have already been proven in practice by consortium members and have been validated in different contexts. Engagement methods, that are associated with the co-visioning process were packaged into the vision roadmap, ensuring that future applications can benefit from a tested framework that is both robust and adaptable, embodying the very principles of the co-visioning process it seeks to promote. Each method presents user with a clear, step by step guide, explaining its implementation, including templates, required materials and expertise and outlining key results.

Within the visioning process, engagement methods were grouped with process milestones, creating the Visioning Roadmap. A more detailed description of each milestone and method will be further outlined in Section 3.2, which provides an in depth-overview of co-designing visions and adaptive pathways methodology and its steps.

3.2. Process Milestones

The following section presents an in-depth description of the key milestones in the co-visioning and adaptive pathways development methodology, which is unique to the UP2030 project. It's important to note that this section outlines the general methodology and does not delve into the specific application process. The detailing of the application process for each of the project's pilot cities is defined in Section 5.

For each process milestone in this section, an overview is given, including detailed information on the Inputs, Purpose, Key Outcomes, Stakeholders, and Methods:

- *Inputs* describe what information, expertise or content is needed to feed into the development of the milestone.

- *Purpose* describes the intention of the suggested approaches in that step and highlights the aim of the individual exercises.
- *Key Outcomes* describes the expected outputs and progress to be made in achieving the milestone.
- *Stakeholders* explains which partners, organisations, and groups are to be involved, as well as their role. This includes assigning of responsibilities, which partners may support, and which stakeholders should potentially be involved.
- Finally, the *Methods* overview describes the *how* component of the milestone – in essence – which engagement methods should be utilised to successfully execute this process milestone.

Figure 5: Process Milestones: Vision and Adaptive Pathways Process (Source: TSPA, 2023)

3.2.1. Objectives Validation

Many cities already have broad visions and agendas for reaching carbon neutrality. The implementation of such may take place in both wide-scale policy reforms and smaller, localised projects in which sustainable development principles are tested and applied. It is in these localised projects where specific development objectives can be aligned with principles such as social justice, carbon neutrality, and resilience.

While cities may have sets of objectives at both the municipal level and project level, the *Objectives Validation* step is an exercise for synthesising these together and gaining a better overview of the timeline they align with. For example, in the *UP2030* project, each city has already identified its own set of objectives, for their specific pilot that might include both, targets from ongoing programmes, as well as newly conceived objectives, for aligning with the pillars of *resilience, just transition, and carbon neutrality*. The *Objectives Validation* milestone is thus achieved when the city's previously identified objectives are validated as to their clarity, relevance, feasibility, and contribution to the thematic pillars. In the case of *UP2030* it was resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition.

Inputs

Prior to the validation of objectives, it is imperative that the city identifies a set of objectives for the project. This can come from various methods such as SWOT analyses, needs and barriers assessments, or any other form of identification. In the case of *UP2030*, objectives were gathered from various sources

and stakeholders through the use of multiple living documents and process updates from each city such as the *City Storylines* and *First Engagement Reviews*.

Purpose

To develop a coherent project vision objectives must be tested and considered for feasibility, contribution to the cities' strategic goals such as resilience, carbon neutrality, or equity, and to ensure the utility of the identified objective. In effect, the *objectives validation* phase is intended to develop useful and actionable goals. The challenge, which is being responded to, is that objectives can be formulated in a wide range of scopes, scales, and timelines. For example, an objective could be formulated as broadly as '*make urban transportation sustainable*', or as specific as '*plant 150 trees in Westerpark by 2025*'. The validation phase is thus intended to expand or refine these objectives into a practical scope and timeframe.

Key Outcomes

The key outcome of this milestone is a set of objectives which synthesise previous assessments and analysis activities. The objectives are validated by key stakeholders regarding their relevance, feasibility, and approximate timeline (short-, medium-, long-term goals). Validated objectives should be framed or categorised regarding their contribution to guiding principles of the respective project, such as UP2030's pillars of *resilience, just transition or carbon neutrality*.

Stakeholders

Internal stakeholders such as municipal officials, planning experts, and key external stakeholders related to the project are central to this process. The original sets of objectives, however, can be collected from a wide array of both internal and external stakeholders. In the case of UP2030, the *Objectives Validation* is administered by technical partners, who are responsible for compiling the original set of objectives from previous work and research within the consortium, and the subsequent communication with each city, their respective liaisons, and documentation of the milestone.

Methods

Considering parallel efforts within complex municipal projects, the first step of the process is the scanning of previous research done in *assessments of needs, strategic goals, SWOT analysis* or any such evaluation of key outcomes that has been done previously. This is done to avoid duplicating efforts and to capitalise on pre-existing knowledge. At this stage, the *objectives* are preliminary, as they may have been collected in various formats and from numerous sources.

The objectives are collected and compiled, with an effort to be as comprehensive as possible. They are then communicated with whichever stakeholders have been granted the agency to take part in the validation process – a choice that is ultimately the decision of the project's implementing body. The representatives are then asked to assess the relevance of each listed objective, and to reword, refine, or eliminate them as they see fit. For example, an objective may be eliminated if the project scope has changed since it was originally conceived and it is therefore no longer relevant. It is also the key moment to add in objectives that have been missed in earlier project activities. The stakeholders are finally asked to indicate which of the guiding principles each objective contributes to most, and to assess the timeframe in which they would expect that objective to be achieved.

The validation process can be executed digitally using shared co-editable documents, in person through workshops held with relevant stakeholders to foster discussion, or some hybrid of the two methods.

Figure 6: Objectives Validation workshop at the UP2030 1st General Assembly on 15th November 2023, Lisbon (Source: TSPA, 2023)

3.2.2. Spatial Assessment

Regardless of the project focus, be it social, economic, environmental, etc., the co-visioning process can benefit from localising the challenges and

opportunities through spatial assessment. The Spatial Assessment milestone is critical for grounding the project in the local context, to enrich the understanding of complex challenges which affect the project, and to coax out where adjacent processes, projects, and issues which may interact or align with the proposed project. There are several methods for undertaking this milestone depending on the city's unique needs. The aim is to create rich visual and spatial representations of both barriers and drivers for the project, which can be included in the further visioning and adaptive pathways development.

Inputs

Leading into workshops developed for spatial assessment, facilitators and/or researchers should have a baseline understanding of core project components and aims. For example, the validated objectives can feed into the spatial assessment milestone. They can be localised within the context of the project neighbourhood, and in turn they can define the topics which may be mapped and analysed. Prior to such workshops, the topics of discussion should be agreed upon, the geographic scope delineated, and any relevant background data should be collected and transformed into practical formats for the participants to grapple with.

Purpose

The primary objective of spatial assessment is to represent specific challenges and opportunities to be further addressed in the future vision. This is to identify potential vulnerabilities, localise barriers and risks, and create a spatial representation of various stakeholders' understanding of the context which the project is to exist within. While ongoing projects and challenges may have potential for interplay with any proposed project, the understanding of these may be radically different from various perspectives – i.e. that of a local resident versus that of a sectoral expert. Spatial assessment can bring various forms of knowledge together to be considered and visualised in the context of their local interactions, rather than just from a policy or conceptual understanding.

Key Outcomes

While it depends on the method(s) used, the key outcomes of spatial assessment are sketches, visuals, and schematic maps. Thematically differentiated maps of challenges, existing and ongoing projects, risks

and opportunities can be created. Complex subjective, qualitative, and quantitative information can be brought together, such as ideas, opinions, local knowledge, and technical assessment. New datasets and visualisations are primary potential outputs. These, in turn, are utilised for creating more specific, contextually sensitive strategies, visions, and actions to be undertaken. For everyone involved, a key outcome is an enriched understanding of the interplay between various local factors, and the perspectives of other stakeholders with different views, expertise, and understanding.

Methods

Community Maps is a mobile and computer-based web-application which can be leveraged for public engagement of various forms. It can be used to allow stakeholders to collect and engage with spatial data co-created by those stakeholders themselves. The detailed process for using the platform and method is in the link below:

<https://up2030.notion.site/Community-Maps-a68a2a311bc446eeac564934b650be72>

Figure 7: Screenshot of the Community Maps Interface adjusted for UP2030

Source: <https://up.communitymaps.org.uk/project/up2030-visioning>

Integrated Spatial Analysis is a workshop-based method. It is primarily executed by hand-sketching thematic maps of local issues and opportunities in groups and allowing for collaboration of a range of stakeholders. Opportunities, drivers, challenges, and risks are prioritised, considered for potential synergies or interactions with the pilot project, assessed for agency and responsibility, and localised on the map. In UP2030 for example, these maps can be thematically differentiated between resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition issues and opportunities. Sketches and maps can then be presented, moderators can identify overlaps in a pin-up style review, and can eventually be documented, digitised, and distributed. The detailed process for this method can be found in the link below: [Engagement Toolkit](#).

Figure 8: Integrated Spatial Analysis Workshop (Source: TSPA, 2023)

Exploratory Charrette is a workshop-based method that aims at collaboratively determining spatial priorities for productive decision-making and plan development. Stakeholders are engaged in a cooperative and hands-on process, discussing spatial challenges, marking up plans, and localising high level targets. The method provides an overview of the spatial priorities and opportunities the project will address, as well as enables a common understanding of goals, targets, and objectives.

Step by step process for conducting this method can be found here: [Engagement Toolkit](#).

Figure 9: Photo and Example Template from the Exploratory Charrette (Source: TSPA, 2023)

Stakeholders

Depending on the method used, target stakeholders vary. With the *Integrated Spatial Analysis* method, participants can include *Decision Makers, Urban Planners, Sustainable Development Experts, local stakeholder representatives, and/or people with deep knowledge of some aspect of the context of the project*. The *Community Maps* method should be set up by urban planners or experts who are trained on the process, whereas practically any other stakeholder group can make use of the tool. The stakeholders involved in contributing to the maps will depend on the topics and locales that are chosen to be mapped. Liaisons are responsible for organising, facilitating, and recording the exercises.

3.2.3. Pillar Visions

Pillar visions represent a thematic element within the overarching pilot vision, focusing on a specific realm crucial to achieving inclusive, climate-neutral, and resilient urban development. Each Vision Pillar addresses distinct, yet interconnected, aspects of urban development and provides detailed, aspirational,

objectives which will guide actions and decision-making within its particular sphere. In the case of UP2030, these are visions which are developed specifically in reference to the future of Carbon Neutrality, Resilience, and Just Transition in the pilots. Shared values from multiple stakeholder groups are brought together, and a common understanding of the strategic direction are developed along the lines of the project pillars. This common understanding categorises and prioritises the key objectives for each pillar and identifies gaps or overlaps. Pillar vision can be seen as a first step in defining and informing the holistic pilot vision definition, or in other cases, take place after the holistic vision was already created. In that way, the pillar vision can support the identification and formulation of specific and shared thematic values and priorities.

Inputs

Objectives validation is a pre-requisite to the development of this milestone. In order to develop pillar or principle-oriented visions, there should be a baseline understanding of the project scope, and key objectives within it. While not strictly necessary, having executed some degree of spatial analysis can enrich and stimulate the process of visioning, by providing greater understanding and context for the brainstorming and development of new ideas.

Purpose

The first aim in achieving this milestone is to connect the city's overarching visions for each principle or *pillar* to the strategic objectives of the specific project or *pilot*. The other key aim is to develop a common understanding of shared values and priorities from different stakeholder groups, and to synthesise those into a coherent co-defined vision for the future of the project areas.

Key Outcomes

Objectives that have been previously defined are considered in depth and sets of ideas for the achievement of them are developed from various perspectives. This can aid in the development of actions in the later stages of the adaptive pathways. The key output from this process, however, is the generation of visions that are highly specific to the project (*pilot*), concise, actionable, and aligned amongst the various stakeholders.

Methods

The approach proposed for developing the *Pillar Visions* milestone is a method called *Thematic Brainstorming*. Thematic Brainstorming is a flexible method which can be executed in person or remotely. It functions by asking groups to enrich the previous *Validated Objectives*, by generating ideas according to how each of those objectives could contribute to the project principles or *pillars*. The groups are subsequently asked to take these ideas and synthesise them into coherent and ambitious visions for each principle or *pillar* within the scope of the project. Finally, these ideas and visions from separate groups are presented, compared, and clustered together, to discuss and integrate the visions from all the involved stakeholders.

The detailed steps for this method can be found in the link below: [Engagement Toolkit](#)

Stakeholders

Any stakeholder with a deep understanding of the physical, institutional, or thematic context of the project area can participate in the *Pillar Visioning* process. This can include technical professionals, urban planners, policy makers, local residents, asset managers, NGO representatives, etc. The process should be facilitated and moderated by professional familiar with the contexts. In the UP2030 context, city liaisons have been assigned to this role.

Thematic Brainstorming

🕒 Duration	1-3 hours
📄 Format	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> On-site <input type="checkbox"/> Online
👤 Target stakeholders	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Urban Planners <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Residents <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Decision Makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economy industry and commerce <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NGOs/activists <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainable development experts <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Service/utility providers
👤 Author	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TSPA
🕒 Last edited	November 1, 2023 4:26 PM

Figure 10: Thematic brainstorming method from the stakeholder engagement toolkit (Source: TSPA, 2023)

3.2.4. Pilot Vision

The *Pilot Vision* is the synthesis of all the other visioning activities. It is also the development of a comprehensive and holistic vision for the desired future transformations to take place within the scope of the project or *pilot*. The vision is co-defined primarily as a vision statement (text-based component) and as a vision diagram or map (visual component). It incorporates the validated, refined, and categorised objectives. It also includes the *pillar visions*, which should effectively align with the overall vision. All these components are collected into a concise document referred to as the *Vision Page* – Figure 11. Vision Page was developed specifically for UP2030 project as a template to document the city’s vision and can be adjusted to each city’s outcome. In that sense, each pilot city within UP2030 will contribute to developing its own vision page at the end of this process.

As a pivotal milestone concluding one of the two main components of the co-visioning process, the *Pilot Vision* is crucial for developing a clear direction to head towards and is necessary for the development of Adaptive Pathways. In essence, the *Pilot Vision* will define the adaptive space within which the pilot ought to operate.

Inputs

Validated and refined objectives, spatial analysis, and an overview of opportunities and challenges can all provide the basis upon which a comprehensive pilot vision can be defined. This is an effort primarily to

synthesise information previously developed in earlier processes within the project to create a cohesive concept, rather than starting from a blank slate. It would also be advantageous to have developed *pillar visions* prior to developing the overarching vision concept, however, this is not strictly necessary. Of the two methods proposed, the *Future Newspaper* requires little in the way of formal inputs, whereas the Common Vision – being a spatial exercise – requires layer overlays such as those developed in the integrated spatial analysis method.

Purpose

The ultimate purpose of this step is to fully develop the comprehensive vision which has been co-created throughout the prior milestones. It should provide decision makers with clear spatial areas for intervention, connect higher level carbon-neutrality, resilience, or equity-based ambitions with the local scale, and outline an ambitious but realistic future which stakeholders aim to achieve through the implementation of the project or *pilot*. To prepare cities for developing an adaptive pathways approach to planning, it is assumed that the path to getting from where they are now – the status quo – to where they would like to head, will be non-linear. Thus, this approach to co-visioning asks the stakeholders to define what that future would look like, thereby defining the space within which iteration and adaptation in the development / transformation process can operate.

Key Outcomes

The key outcomes of the Pilot Vision milestone are collected and represented in the *Vision Page*. This is in effect, the synthesis of all the co-visioning milestones. This will include a clear *Title* for the project. An indicative *vision statement*, which can be defined and elaborated in the *Future Newspaper* method, encapsulates the holistic concept for the *pilot* or project's future and impact. There are *Pillar Visions*, which are comprised of the outcomes from the previous milestone, and effectively break down the holistic vision into envisioned contributions to the guiding principles. In the case of *UP2030*, these are the three pillars of *carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition*. The graphic – referred to as the *Vision Page* (Figure 11) – can be derived from the *thematic brainstorming* and *common vision* methods and gives a spatial and localised understanding of the vision. Finally, the page will include the *refined objectives* which are associated with the relevant principles or *pillars* which they are most associated with.

Figure 11: Vision Page Template (Source: TSPA, 2023)

Methods

In this milestone, there are two proposed methods which can help cities round out their visions. The first is the *Future Newspaper* method. This is an exercise which is intended to be done in a workshop environment. The method is valuable in helping participants think through and conceptualise how they envision the future by coming up with headlines that they would read in their local newspaper about the site. This can help them come up with ambitious but realistic end-goals which they aim to achieve through the project. The grouped participants consider the headlines in reference to the project's key climate, resilience, or equity-based priorities, and develop the 'stories' that such an article might describe. This method can be adapted to whichever theme(s) cities are working on and can help define the qualitative and/or quantitative characteristics of the vision. The details of this method are in the link here: [Engagement toolkit](#)

The other suggested method is the *Common Vision* method, which focuses on defining a singular and cohesive spatial vision. The method brings stakeholders together and focuses on aligning priorities and objectives into a spatially actionable concept. This vision is a spatial map of the project's future and a powerful tool that can be shared, discussed or further contested. Working with layered inputs from previous mapping exercises such as the integrated spatial analysis, participants are asked to trace and plot objectives at the *pilot* or project scale. Overlapping these, they are asked to find synergies, conflicts, and other intersections. Finally, participants are asked to develop a graphical sketch of their cohesive vision, or a few options for this. In the case of multiple options, they are then merged and harmonised by the workshop organisers. The details of this method are in the link here: [Engagement Toolkit](#)

Finally, the results from the methods completed in this step, and in those prior, are recorded and shared with technical partners or internal experts who can compile them into the Vision page format.

Stakeholders

As a synthetic step, all involved parties and stakeholders are, in essence, engaged in this milestone. However, the methods described above are to be championed by the city and its liaison organisation and should include stakeholders both internal and external in this pivotal step of holistically defining the vision for the project or *pilot*. In UP2030, this means engaging with the LAAs. Ultimately, the cities, liaisons, and technical partners are responsible for compiling results from each workshop into formats which can be clearly understood and communicated with technical partners for assessing and compiling the outcomes. For this reason, the Vision Page will serve the purpose of communicating the outcome, the pilot vision along vision pillars and associated objectives to all participating stakeholders.

3.2.5. Action Prompt Development

As a preparatory step to bridge from the visioning milestones, Action Prompt Development aims to shape the direction and form, ensuring that the development of the adaptive pathways is comprehensive. Prior to objectives being unpacked into actions, this step leans on technical experts to integrate the benchmarking criteria of the project into prompts for workshops and interviews. Essentially, the step aims to amalgamate the benchmarking framework with the specific objectives from the visioning phase to effectively guide the dialogue into relevant and effective action development. The prompts should be geared towards stimulating the identification of both the actions required to achieve the project's vision and the risks or barriers therein. These prompts should encourage participants to identify actions and risks that expand across the critical topics of Policy and Governance; Urban Planning; Energy, Mobility, and Sustainability; Financing; and Engagement and Citizen science.

Inputs

The key inputs to this process are the objectives and pilot vision derived within the vision milestones. Additionally, other content that has been generated in parallel or as a result from these phases can be integrated. In the case of UP2030, for example, this could include considering the Community Maps exercise where cities identified key ongoing projects for alignment as well as needs identified in the previous project phase. The other key input to this milestone is the benchmarking framework. The formulation of the prompts is contingent upon a pre-defined set of criteria that the vision and objectives can be evaluated against.

Purpose

The purpose of this is threefold: First, to provide facilitators the content to guide the unpacking of objectives discussion into functional, tangible, and realistic actions. Second, to embed the benchmarking framework regarding the Carbon Neutrality, Resilience, and Just Transition pillars with the vision goals to ensure that actions and risks identified are aligned with objectives and do not contribute to path-dependency or maladaptive outcomes. Third, and finally, to shape and stimulate workshops to span between disciplines to develop a more comprehensive set of actions and risks. In example, to avoid leaving large gaps such as failing to consider governance or financing aspects of the pilot actions.

Key Outcomes

The key outcome from this process is a set of validated prompts which span between spatial planning, energy, sustainability, policy, finance, citizen science, and engagement considerations. These prompts, depending on the format of the adaptive pathways' engagement – such as in workshops or in interviews – are integrated into templates for the unpacking of objectives and identification of risks in the following milestone (Figure 12) These templates can be adapted to the specific context of the pilot or project. For example, in UP2030, the prompts were integrated into text documents designed for small interviews or focus groups for some cities, while for others they were integrated into visual templates designed to be printed out in large formats that would allow for group roundtable discussions. The prompts should provide facilitators in the next milestone with the content required to stimulate interdisciplinary discussion and the identification of actions and risks that stay within the project's respective pillars or benchmarking framework.

Methods

The development of the prompts was guided by the UP2030 benchmarking framework, bolstered by the technical expertise of our partners. This process involved transforming filter questions (filter questions can be found in D2.3) into actionable prompts. The filter defines the standards that each action should meet or contribute to. In the case of UP2030, these are dimensions such as governance, policy, financing, spatial planning, energy, mobility, and citizen engagement, in the context of the three pillars of carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition. For example, for the city of Budapest (more information in section 5.2.2), which has an objective to “Create guides and standards for our own companies, districts and the planners involved,” the following prompts were developed:

- *What is needed for the Municipality of Budapest to prepare and enforce standards for its own companies or for third parties (districts, private property developers etc.)*
- *Describe sub-actions/steps to ensure that the standards incorporate the UP2030 dimensions of carbon-neutrality and resilience and social justice.*
- *Define action how guides and standards can include community involvement approaches in the planning and development process.*
- *Explore what strategies can be used embedded these guides and standards into planning and development processes within private and public sector. What mechanisms can be put in place to adapt the guides in response to changes in regulations and policies?*

The idea here is to encourage the stakeholders to consider the various interlinking and co-dependant actions that would be necessary to achieve the objective in question. The prompts, as done above, should also encourage deliberation on the risks inherent to following certain paths to achieving the objective, such as questions of policy, funding, stakeholder opposition etc. These prompts are formulated by experts in these respective fields, and subsequently shared with the city for validation. This provides an opportunity to hone the prompts further and ensure that they are appropriate for the stakeholder groups that will be engaged. Following the validation the prompts are shared in the format relevant to the engagement method that will follow in the proceeding milestone. If relevant, the templates and prompts should be translated into the local language(s) of the stakeholders who will be engaged in the process.

Stakeholders

This stage is to be spearheaded by technical partners who have expertise in the dimensions of the benchmarking framework of the project. In the case of UP2030 this included partners with expertise in spatial planning, mobility, policy and governance, and stakeholder engagement. In other cases, partners should be familiar with the overall picture of the city’s vision for the pilot or project. Representatives of the city and/or their liaisons are also fundamental to connecting and refining the prompts such that they align with the essence of their vision and objectives.

3.2.6. Unpacking Objectives

Having completed the co-development of the shared vision, the *Unpacking Objectives* milestone is the second step of the adaptive pathways’ development. This section aims to pave the way for practical, adaptive strategies aligned with the project or *pilot* objectives and vision. The focus here is to break down objectives into potential actions (interventions, strategies and activities) required to accomplish what is stipulated in the vision. This step is also linked with identifying potential risks and barriers that stand in the way of such actions, and risks which may lead towards a maladaptive space outside of the vision or towards path dependency and ‘lock-in’. The risks are identified in combination with the development of mitigation strategies, or ‘alternate actions’ that are designed to help pre-empt the future barriers to successful implementation of the objective. The actions, risks, and mitigation strategies are also given time frames to assist with sequencing into adaptive pathways.

Figure 12 Template example for Unpacking Objectives Method

Inputs

The primary inputs for the Unpacking Objectives step are the objectives, comprehensive *vision and vision pillars* and the action prompts developed in the previous milestone. As a cue for the format of this milestone's output, templates developed in the previous step, fitted to the relevant engagement approach are valuable for the facilitation of workshops or interviews. Depending on the project's previous analysis and engagement efforts, previously executed needs and barriers assessments can be a valuable contribution to this phase. In the case of UP2030, governance barriers identified in the first engagement review could feed into this step. Additionally, a clear glossary of defined terminology for the adaptive pathways process is valuable for stakeholders and participants for whom this methodology is unfamiliar.

Purpose

This key step in developing adaptive pathways aims to make connections between the current status quo, and the future state that has been collectively envisioned. By breaking down the vision into its constituent objectives, and transforming those into tangible actions, pathways can start to be developed. However, it is expected in complex transformations such as aiming for carbon neutrality, resilience, and achieving justice, that this will be a non-linear process. As such, identifying key risk and barriers to these actions can start to build a more robust and dynamic approach for delivering on the project's objectives. It is also important to project the actions into the future and to begin adding temporal data to them to understand how the actions relate to each other and where interdependencies lie.

Key Outcomes

The *Unpacking Objectives* milestone and the associated methods are designed to make projects actionable. The key outcomes are tangible actions, risks, and mitigation strategies that are directly focused on achieving the objectives of the project itself whilst remaining in line with the benchmarking framework that it operates within. These can subsequently set the stage for the following milestones which see the actions sequenced into clusters of actions and adaptive pathways. This milestone contributes significantly to transforming the vision into a concrete, implementable, and dynamic action plan.

Stakeholders

Due to the complexity and novelty of developing adaptive pathways for achieving carbon neutral urban *pilots* or projects, this milestone is to be led by a combination of the cities and their liaison organisations who are advised and assisted by technical partners. In the case of UP2030, the LAAs and internal municipal stakeholders are generally the key participants being engaged in the development of this milestone. However, the engagement of external stakeholders can certainly be a welcome addition, adding other forms of knowledge and nuance to the discussion around the formulation of the actions and the identification of risks. Ultimately the stakeholders engaged in this milestone need to have a baseline understanding of the processes required to achieve some components of the vision, to meaningfully contribute to the development of material actions. Co-creation approach to adaptive pathways illustrates how stakeholders can collectively contribute to a shared vision while amplifying the impact of each individual action. As a result, priority topics emerge, establishing defined focus areas and initiating actions.

Methods

This step utilises the *Unpacking Objectives* method from the Engagement Toolkit to come up with a set of actions that form a decision-making framework for the future. The approach is based on a back

casting/forecasting approach which can be selected based on the pilot needs and participating stakeholders. Actions, risks and alternative actions are defined through the group discussion or interview sessions. Working within the overarching project vision, and the specific *pillar* vision, actions, and risks that could lead towards or away from the objectives begin to define the *adaptive space* that the project aims to operate within.

This process is aided by the prompts developed in the previous milestone and can take place in multiple formats. The unpacking of objectives and the identification of risks and mitigation strategies can be done in conjunction or as distinct activities. Within UP2030, it was typically the latter. In the case of interviews or small focus groups, a table with the objectives, prompts, and empty columns for short-, medium-, or long-term actions can be used for recording of participants suggestions. Similarly, tables with the objectives, risk-related prompts, and columns for recording suggestions can be used for identifying risks and mitigation strategies. In the case of workshops, these templates can be formulated into larger format such as A0 visual templates which participants around a table can append sticky notes to while reacting to the prompts. These templates can also allow the participants to do preliminary sequencing and clustering of related actions. Examples of these templates can be found in Figure 12 and Figure 13

The full description of this method can be found in the link here: [Engagement Toolkit. Unpacking Objectives](#)

UP2030

STRATEGIC ADAPTIVE PATHWAYS

CITY NAME: _____
 PROJECT TITLE: _____

Exercise: Unpacking Pilot Objectives and Visions

<p style="color: #800080; font-weight: bold;">List Identified Key Pilot Objectives</p> <p style="font-size: 10px; color: #800080;">(inherited from previous definitions)</p>	<p style="color: #800080; font-weight: bold;">Unpack Objectives Into Key Actions & Strategies</p> <p style="font-size: 10px; color: #800080;">(primary approaches for achieving objectives)</p>	<p style="color: #800080; font-weight: bold;">Identify Where the Issues are Localised</p> <p style="font-size: 10px; color: #800080;">(mark on the map the most impacted areas and assign a letter to each)</p>
<div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 10px; text-align: center; color: #800080;"> Framework for Expanding Green Infrastructure </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 10px; height: 30px; margin-bottom: 10px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 10px; height: 30px; margin-bottom: 10px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 10px; height: 30px;"></div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e.g. increase permeable surfaces in area x • e.g. connect inner city green spaces with periphery • _____ 	<div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; align-items: center; gap: 20px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px; display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center; font-size: 20px; color: #800080;">A</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid #800080; border-radius: 50%; width: 40px; height: 40px;"></div> </div>

Figure 13: Template for unpacking objectives into actions (Source: TSPA, 2023)

3.2.7. Comprehensive Assessment

Following the development of the prompts in line with the benchmarking framework and after the unpacking of objectives into their respective actions, risks, and alternate actions or mitigation strategies, the content generated by stakeholders needs to be sequenced into adaptive pathways and assessed for gaps. The *Comprehensive Assessment* milestone leverages technical expert knowledge to transform the content into draft adaptive pathways. These technical partners make first pass of grouping and linking the actions and associating them with other actions into clusters of related and interdependent actions to form strategies. The expert partners then assess the draft adaptive pathways, adding comments, identifying gaps and making suggestions based on their field of expertise. Finally, the draft pathways are compiled into a database of the adaptive pathways, in preparation for the final milestone where they will be validated by the city.

Input

The key inputs into this step are the complete vision page and actions, with risks, and mitigation strategies that have been identified in the previous milestone's engagement sessions. These results should be translated if necessary. Expertise of technical partners regarding the development of adaptive pathways is also a necessary input for this stage.

Purpose

The aim is to develop initial version of implementable adaptive pathways, grounded in the co-defined objectives and vision. The pathways are intended to provide clear, practical, and dynamic implementation strategies. They should serve to help cities avoid executing their projects and failing to achieve their various visions which were defined at the outset. Thus, this step involves capitalising on the technical, theoretical, and practical expertise of the technical partners to cluster, sequence, and assess the actions and preliminary adaptive pathways. This external technical assessment is intended to highlight unseen gaps, barriers, and risks associated with the proposed sets of actions and assist in developing more robust approaches to achieving the city's vision.

Key Outcomes

There are two key outcomes of this milestone. First is the technical refinement and assistance in developing comprehensive adaptive pathways. This includes the identification of additional risks and gaps that have been identified in what had been proposed. Second, is the initial version of Adaptive Pathways. This is a comprehensive, unified product which charts the sequences and interlinkages of actions and clusters of actions which should help provide navigability towards the realisation stated objectives and visions. In turn, this allows for communication and dissemination with the cities, and their respective liaisons and stakeholders for further refinement.

Methods

Technical partners receive from the cities or their liaisons the results of the unpacking objectives milestone. In the case of UP2030, the technical partner TSPA used *Miro* to visualise, sequence, and cluster the actions. As this preliminary draft of the adaptive pathways is formed, additional technical experts are brought in to assess the relationships between the actions and begin identifying gaps or aspects of the pathways that are unclear. Input is then arranged into the draft Adaptive Pathways databases. The gaps,

suggestions, and questions are compiled into a table where they are associated with the action or cluster of actions that they refer to.

Stakeholders

The primary partners involved in this stage are the technical partners, who receive the information from the previous milestone from the liaisons and cities, and then take this stage upon themselves. However, this stage may also require coordination and communication between the technical partners and cities for clarification. Translation assistance may be necessary to ensure that key characteristics of the actions and risks are not lost between languages.

3.2.8. Adaptive Pathways Validation

The last milestone of the adaptive pathways' development methodology, the *Adaptive Pathways Validation* stage serves to provide a final round of validation and iteration before the city takes agency and ownership over the adaptive pathways. The drafts of the adaptive pathways are to be shared with the cities and liaisons for review, to respond to questions, gaps, and comments received from the technical partners in the previous milestone. This sets the stage for the delivery of the adaptive pathways in the format of an editable database and 'Adaptive Pathways Pages' which encapsulate the pathways of clusters of actions in a simplified format. This step is a final milestone in the described methodology, however, it's not a mere exchange between city and technical partners but stands for a continues improvement of adaptive pathways to maximise its benefits.

Input

The key inputs to this phase are the drafts of the adaptive pathways databases, and the complete co-developed visioning pages. The drafts include the comments, gaps identified, and questions from technical partners.

Purpose

While the previous milestone, the *Comprehensive Assessment*, provided drafts of the adaptive pathways, it is imperative that the final versions of these are collectively assessed by vested stakeholders with the local, contextual knowledge base. This iterative process allows for assumptions and judgements made by external technical partners to be checked by those with the intimate understanding of their city's processes and capacities. In essence, it is of utmost importance that local stakeholders have the final say in shaping the pathways. The adaptive pathways should be useful and understandable to those who will utilise them, so it is important to have a final revision for clarifications and to fill in gaps.

Key Outcomes

The key outcome from this final process milestone is the completed *Adaptive Pathways* in the form of editable databases and the *Adaptive Pathways Pages*. The *databases* are intended to be dynamic, living products that differ from a more static spreadsheet or visualisation. They should be interactive and editable to continue to adapt as progress is made and new knowledge is developed. The *pages* are intended for communication with stakeholders, provide summarised version of pathways - clusters of actions (strategies and projects) to make the adaptive pathways and the objectives that they stem from understandable, becoming a communication tool with the broader audience when needed. Together, they should be, by design, non-linear guides which help navigate the complex implementation of carbon neutral

projects in cities, and to pre-empt and mitigate the impact if various actions are not successfully realised. By allowing space for alternative paths to achieving their vision, the adaptive pathways should facilitate robust implementation of their projects. In UP2030, this should provide a basis for the action phase of the project. It is important to note that adaptive pathways.

Methods

The primary method for this milestone is the distribution of draft adaptive pathways to cities and liaisons. This is done through the sharing consolidated pathways' draft of database or in a form of spreadsheet with the actions, risk, respective clusters, and gaps appended for the city's review. The city's representatives can assess, modify, distribute, and make editorial suggestions where they see fit. Depending on the pilot context, the comments can be communicated back to the technical partners to incorporate all the revisions into the initial *adaptive pathways databases* and *pages*. Otherwise, further revisions and modifications can be done solely by the implementing bodies. However, the validation milestone should be a continues process, to truly reflect the concept of adaptive pathways as a flexible planning tool and maximise its benefits. Therefore, the validation milestone encompasses important aspect of building city, or pilot neighbourhood administration's ownership of the developed pathways.

Stakeholders

The parties involved are, most crucially, the cities and their respective internal and external stakeholders whom they choose to involve in the final revision of this document. In the context of UP2030, each city's respective liaisons and LAAs are likely to be consulted in this final iteration as well. The technical partners are critical in supporting the incorporation of revisions and putting the final documents together.

3.3. Guiding Principles for Practical Implementation

UP2030 is made up of 10 European city pilots, and one observer city in the Global South, each with societal and environmental challenges that shape a unique context in which carbon neutrality is to be achieved (UP2030, 2022). To support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their carbon neutrality targets, the goal was to develop a general methodology that supports a practical implementation for each pilot's context.

The practical application of theory is central to UP2030's aim of developing and applying an innovative methodology that cities can adopt to meaningfully engage with the Mission. In particular, the co-development and implementation of science-based, yet practical tools. (in this case, the author refers to the tools in the wider perspective without linking the digital solutions proposed by UP2030 partners) (UP2030, 2022). Therefore, bridging theory and practice is essential in the development of a methodology that can be used to translate visions into practical actions.

The Analysis Phase is crucial in gaining critical insights into the context and realities of each pilot. For example, as part of the Engagement and Vision Task Force within UP2030, meetings were held with each participating city and liaisons to discuss and reflect on the engagement activities undertaken within the Analysis Phase. Critical feedback on the practicalities related to the implementation of UP2030 thus far was received. In turn, this feedback helped to establish guiding principles for the development of a methodology for co-designing visions and adaptive pathways that are practical for cities to use.

The following are key points regarding practicalities for implementation, relevant to the development of the methodology, based on the feedback from pilot cities:

- **Challenging to hold long engagement sessions:** it is challenging for cities to hold long engagement sessions, for example longer than three hours, due to the multitude of stakeholders needed and their respective commitment capacities.
- **Pre-existing projects, initiatives and processes within the pilot areas:** Cities often have pre-existing projects in the pilot areas, relevant to the three pillars of UP2030 of carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition. For example, in the case of Rotterdam, the "Resilient BoTu 2028" program was launched in 2019. In Münster's case, the pilot area of Frauenstraße has already undertaken visioning workshops with residents prior to UP2030. Therefore, a challenge of scoping UP2030 within the pilot areas was a frequent topic brought up by cities.
- **Duplication:** UP2030 is made up a large consortium with multiple tasks being performed in parallel. Cities are often at the centre of these tasks. Therefore, cities and liaisons expressed the need for avoiding the duplication of work and the need to build on information already being provided in the project thus far.
- **Terminology:** There is a wide range of stakeholders involved in the engagement sessions, whom have different understandings of technical vocabulary related to urban planning, design, and climate, and project-specific terminology related to UP2030.
- **Forward planning:** Cities have limited resources and engagement includes multiple stakeholders with varying capacities, therefore communication around the entirety of processes and timelines are highly valuable for planning resources for a successful implementation.

Building upon what was heard from cities and liaisons during the first year of the project, five principles were established to guide the development of the methodology to ensure it is valuable and practical for the cities and liaisons to implement within and outside UP2030 project.

- **Modular and Adaptive Processes:** The process is broadly applicable yet adaptable to each pilot's needs and context. This also supports the potential to up-scale the methodology to contexts beyond UP2030. The methodology is designed specifically in milestones, in which their execution and timeline is flexible. Each milestone contains recommended engagement methods that can be combined into one long-workshop or separated into sequential workshops depending on city and liaison capacity and timeline. For example, with the case of Rotterdam the preferred timeline was to combine several milestones into one longer workshop, tackling the development of pillar vision and holistic pilot visions and adaptive pathways at once, while in the case of Budapest the milestones might be distributed over a period of time.
- **Alignment:** Both within and outside of the UP2030 project, cities have ongoing projects and work related to the pilot areas. Specific engagement methods are recommended within the co-visioning process to support integrating and aligning parallel efforts at the outset of the visioning process. In case of Thessaloniki, which has clearly defined objectives, but pilot area comprises many ongoing projects, the suggestion was to dedicate time for mapping ongoing projects (by exploring *Community Maps* and *Integrated Spatial Assessment*) that align with UP2030 goals, enabling to revealing link and synergies among them. Additionally, scoping within the three project pillars (Carbon Neutrality, Just Transition, and Resilience) is built into the engagement methods of the

co-visioning process to support aligning the pilot's objectives to the UP2030 scope and ensure a cross-cutting and non-siloed approach to achieving carbon neutrality.

- **Iterative:** To build more resilient strategies, feedback loops are embedded in the process to allow for revision and refinement; to adjust to the progression of the implementation of the visioning and adaptive pathways methodology to changing circumstances and to ensure they continuously reflect the context in the pilot area. The feedback loops and close communication with cities and liaisons are key for each step of the process. The goal is not only a key open communication channels, but also update and refine outcomes in each step.
- **Accessible language:** Consistent use of pre-defined terms is done from the onset of the visioning process, so it is clear to multiple stakeholders what is being asked of them and how they can contribute. The glossary with key terms for co-visioning process can be found in Section 1.3. Furthermore, significant focus is placed on how to ensure the dissemination and communication of information on co-visioning and adaptive pathways is clear across a multitude of stakeholders involved in the process. Refer to Section 5.2 for further details of the dissemination strategy.
- **Co-Design approach:** With cities' expertise of being closest to the on-the-ground implementation, they can tailor this process to their unique circumstances, by structuring their process to the milestones and engagement methods that best suit their needs.

3.4. Dissemination and Communication Aspects

The dissemination and communication of the co-visioning and adaptive pathways process is an important consideration for supporting a practical and successful implementation and for adapting the general methodology to the local context. From a conceptual standpoint, the principles previously described of co-design, adaptability, iteration, language accessibility, and alignment were used to strategize on what materials are to be provided, to whom, when, and for what purpose.

The following are communication forms, based on the UP2030 context yet still applicable beyond UP2030, which were shared with cities and liaisons in reference to the co-visioning and adaptive pathways methodology.

- **Visioning Guide (Annex 8.1):** A guide detailing, step-by-step, each milestone and engagement method recommended as part of the entire co-visioning process was created. This guide, tailored for each specific city context, was shared with cities and liaisons at the beginning of the process to communicate in a clear and visual manner what can be expected from the entire task. This allows cities to be able to plan the resources needed and strategize on what milestones and engagement methods are applicable to them. As part of the guide, a glossary was provided for key terms used in the methodology, so that there is a clear and consistent use of terms and to make sure it is clear to various stakeholders what kind of information is being asked for and why.
- **Capacity Training Sessions:** In line with the co-design approach, liaisons play a key support role for cities as they will be facilitating the visioning engagement activities with cities. Therefore, a capacity training session was held to breakdown the different engagement methods available and to offer an opportunity for direct discussions and questions on the methodology. Each session was

tailored to city or city cluster needs, also enabling the peer-to-peer exchange. In the case of UP2030, the sessions were recorded and shared with the participants, in case clarifications would be needed. (It is important to note that during the project, the authors of methodology had several individual sessions with cities and liaisons to further clarify any questions or support the preparation efforts).

- **Workshop(s) Guiding Questions (Annex 8.2):** the questions are intended to support the facilitation of the workshops and to stimulate the dialogue. However, they are neither a comprehensive list nor a limitation to what you can ask. It is important to tailor the questions to the specific context.
- **Vision Page Template:** The Vision Page represents the template for consolidating the outcome of the co-visioning process into one easy to read document. The Page was shared with cities and liaisons at the onset of the co-visioning process in order to understand what the outcome will be. This allows the city to anticipate how they can expect to use all the information obtained from the visioning activities in a way that is useful for communicating their results.
- **Adaptive Pathways Template:** The Adaptive Pathways Page represents the template for consolidating the outcome of the adaptive pathways – objectives and clusters of actions (a.k.a strategies) represented in the timeline.

4. Integration with UP2030 Processes

According to the project proposal (UP2030, 2022), the UP2030 process is structured into four steps: Analysis, Vision, Action, Upscale. Co-designing pilot visions and adaptive pathways is part of *Step 2 - Vision* and builds on results and steps previously carried out, such as the needs and barriers analysis. The integration of the previous inputs (such as needs analysis) and key findings within the task (for example vision and actions) is crucial for the project's success. It is equally important to build upon and pass on the information and knowledge gathered within first steps of the process and to align the implementation of each of key project step.

Figure 14: Diagram of the Four Project Phases (Source: UP2030 Project, 2022)

The following section aims to articulate important links to other tasks and activities carried out within the first year and a half of the project and to reveal the connections with other parallel processes.

4.1. Links to Engagement Activities

The co-visioning methodology is connected to several interrelated and parallel processes within the UP2030 process. From the outset, the visioning phase was built upon the needs assessment conducted under Task T2.3 and enriched by data from City Storylines. The City Storylines are living documents, comprising key information on each of the pilot cities and their progress throughout the UP2030 project. Meanwhile, the Needs Assessment identified challenges cities were facing in the context of their pilots – primarily along the lines of governance gaps. Both fed directly into the objective validation process.

Milestone 1 from the co-visioning process as illustrated in Figure 15, set a base for the entire co-visioning process. Identified objectives determined which of the engagement methods are most appropriate for each milestone. The first milestone also connected to a peer-to-peer learning opportunity at the UP2030 General Assembly in Lisbon, where technical partners worked with the cities to validate the objectives which had been derived from the previous engagement activities.

For the pursuit of carbon neutrality goals in an inclusive manner, establishing a sustainable engagement strategy and setting up stakeholder groups that can follow the entire process is essential. In UP2030, this came in the form of Learning & Action Alliances (LAAs). LAAs are living labs set up within each participating

city, which are made of a wide range of stakeholders and designed to facilitate knowledge sharing and action planning. Formed with a focus on either particular challenges or specific geographic areas, they aim to achieve positive, robust impact via collaborative action. The LAAs play a key role, ensuring a seamless integration and information flow throughout each project phase. These alliances, formed early in the project’s process, create a stable stakeholder ecosystem. Their involvement in needs analysis and co-visioning is vital, incorporating a wide range of perspectives and needs. Thus, the co-visioning process was designed to integrate LAAs throughout its duration. The LAAs provided for many cities a reliable stakeholder ecosystem that could be engaged while developing and validating numerous aspects of the visioning and adaptive pathways milestones. The LAA's role within the rest of the project is further elaborated in D.4.3, the Sustained Engagement Strategy of Learning & Action Alliances, to advance the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots.

Figure 15 Co-visioning Process and Links to Other Activities (Source: TSPA, 2023)

The LAAs and the visioning process have also intertwined in relation to the development of Partnership Commitments. The Partnership Commitments – developed in Task 4.2 – are not binding contracts, but rather agreements developed between stakeholders as memorandums of understanding. They outline their mutual and collective willingness to work together while characterising the interests and inputs of each stakeholder. They are crucial in formalising commitments to the vision and to carrying forward into other activities within UP2030 and beyond.

4.2. Links to Benchmarking Framework and KPIs

A cohesive benchmarking framework was drafted together with technical partners (from UIC (in lead), UPV, TU Delft, BH, TSPA, UCCRN) to establish a coherent theoretical framework throughout the project, from analysis to co-visioning, to the monitoring of actions and impact through KPIs. This framework is anchored in the project's core principles of neutrality, resilience, and justice. A deeper elaboration on the framework can be found in D.2.3. To establish consistency throughout UP2030, the synchronisation of benchmarks, co-visioning, and KPIs tasks was critical. To this end, UP2030's benchmarking framework was devised comprising three primary components:

- Inspiring
- Driving
- Measuring

This structure not only reflects the project's pillars but also embodies fundamental principles of urban planning and design, anchoring future visions in best practice models, including resilience but also compactness or connectedness principles.

The first component of the conceptual framework is designed to motivate and 'inspire' stakeholders and shape the definition of pillar visions and comprehensive pilot visions. Incorporating analysis and benchmarking of exemplary urban models (notable models include the 15-minute, water-sensitive, inclusive city and positive energy district concepts) - those that exemplify resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition goals — enables the accumulation of collective, global knowledge. Instead of starting from scratch, it helps identify effective measures and concepts that have been applied in similar context.

The 'Driving' component of the benchmarking framework is intended to act as a filter. The filter embeds ambitious targets aligned with the three pillars and derived from the broad expertise of the consortium members, to maintain consistency across the project's phases. The filter was developed as a 'methodological checklist' to guide how cities' plans or strategies could ensure that they are building towards carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transitions. The filter was formulated as questions which aim to identify trade-offs, and subsequent compensation mechanisms, such as 'Is your action increasing urban densification for energy optimization increasing soil sealing?' or 'Is the community (or part of it) actively included in the transformation process led by your action'. This filter system was integrated deeply into the visioning and adaptive pathways process. However, the retroactive approach of testing pre-defined actions was adapted by technical partners TSPA and UIC to instead shape the development of actions. This was done via the development of prompts as described in sections 3.2.5 and 3.2.6. The prompts thus embedded the pillar-oriented benchmarking filters into the unpacking of objectives and identification of risks. Additionally, the benchmarking filters laid out the system upon which the comprehensive assessment of the adaptive pathways was conducted as described in section 3.2.7.

The third component of the framework – 'Measuring' – is where the co-visioning methodology intersects with both the benchmarking and KPI development components of the project. The definition of the visions contributes to developing pilot-specific KPIs by establishing consensus on the direction the cities want to go in within their prototypes and beyond. Essentially aiding the definition of which high-level achievements the cities want to fulfil. Furthermore, the adaptive pathways process, as described above with its integration of the benchmarking filter, helped cities to develop tangible actions. With these

actions, more specific KPIs can be developed for each city along the lines of the thematic clusters described in section 3.2.7.

In essence, this integration resulted in the proposal of a KPI monitoring system that directly integrates the thematic priorities that co-visioning and adaptive pathways process helped elucidate. The monitoring system was proposed to integrate the pillars and thematic clusters to support the monitoring of not just the development of physical infrastructures, but also the progress on topics such as governance, policy, financing, participatory inclusion, etc. Additionally, this system was co-defined between the leader of T.2.4. (TSPA) and T4.4 (UPV) to include the 5UP approach into the KPI monitoring process in order to enable the monitoring of progress across the phases within the UP2030 project and beyond. More information on the development of the KPI system can be found in D.4.5.

The coherence between analysis, visioning, and monitoring (KPI) activities relies on integrating thematic fields, UP2030 pillars—resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition—into each task, fostering linkage and alignment among different tasks.

4.3. [Link to Prototyping Activities](#)

The co-visioning process involved a synergistic approach where visions and information were continuously exchanged across different project components. As a cornerstone of building the direction the cities want to go in, the activities enabled them and their LAAs to refine broader objectives into visions, actions, and adaptive pathways. Throughout the process, cities and their stakeholder ecosystems could use this to continuously clarify the focus of the prototype they aimed to develop through UP2030. In theory, as the pilot needs, objectives and visions became clearer, and specific actions were defined through the adaptive pathways, the cities could gain a better understanding of which technological tools they might require to support engagement activities and co-design processes but also, implement their respective prototypes and how to most effectively utilise them for their aims.

5. Application Process

The goal of this section is to provide insights, on how the methodology described above was applied in each pilot city and reflect on key takeaways of the application process. The section detail key learnings from the process and present the outcome - co-designed visions and adaptive pathways developed in each pilot unique to its needs and context.

5.1. Reflections on Co-Visioning Methodology Application

The application process for co-designing the vision for pilot cities began with the Objectives Validation milestone. Cities were tasked with revising their previously defined objectives, ensuring their alignment with the three key pillars: resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition. Concurrently, capacity training sessions were organized for city liaisons to introduce the proposed methodology and the available materials to support the planning and implementation of the workshops. During these sessions, clusters of cities, comprising 2-3 pilots per session, were formed to foster more interactive and individual engagements, allowing for a deeper dive into each case. The pilot cities were grouped based on their thematic focus areas and similarities in the proposed visioning and engagement processes.

The sessions, held online, began with an explanation of the aim of the co-visioning and adaptive pathways activities. Following this, the key principles underlying the methodology were discussed, progressing into a detailed explanation of each co-visioning milestone and how they interconnect. One of the key messages was that the visioning process was developed as flexible methodology comprised of multiple adaptable steps that can be used for conducting one, two or more engagement sessions, allowing to contextualise the process to each pilot's needs and stakeholder profiles.

After introducing the methodology, one method was presented in-depth to provide a comprehensive understanding. The session also included an introduction to all available materials developed for the visioning process, such as templates and an engagement toolkit (for more details, refer to section 3.1.5 Engagement Toolkit) which contained detailed descriptions of each engagement method.

Ultimately, the Guide for Visioning was presented as a key instructional document, serving as a customised reference for any questions the cities might have or related documents they might need throughout the co-visioning and adaptive pathways processes. The customised Guides incorporated all the elements and topics mentioned above.

At the end of each session, time was dedicated to questions and further clarifications. The decision to conduct these training sessions with liaisons stemmed from cities expressing challenges in coping with the project scale. This approach aimed to facilitate better information flow and to empower the effective role of liaisons as the main supporters of cities in navigating the complexity of the project.

After the capacity training sessions, each pilot case was then followed-up with and advised individually via monthly online sessions to support the unique nature of each pilot project. These meetings were held throughout the whole visioning phase.

Budapest and Granollers cities were the first to organize their workshops. Their insights after conducting the first co-visioning workshops were shared during an online meeting attended by all pilot cities and liaisons. This meeting aimed to inspire and motivate other pilots, as well as to share valuable learnings and

pitfalls to avoid. Key lessons were distilled into concise points, such as the realization that workshops shorter than half a day were insufficient, and longer sessions are necessary to cover all relevant topics comprehensively.

Documented co-visioning workshop outcomes were shared with TSPA for revision and later consolidated into the vision pages. The vision pages underwent several iterations to ensure accuracy and completeness.

Once the vision workshops were completed, the focus shifted towards preparing for adaptive pathways. Most cities chose to conduct two or more sessions for co-designing visions and adaptive pathways, while Belfast and Rotterdam opted to organize one session addressing both parts. Preparation for adaptive pathway activities, similarly to the co-visioning process, was conducted through online sessions between each city and technical partners. During these sessions the purpose and concept of adaptive pathways, how they could support city processes, and presented the methodology for unpacking objectives along with key suggestions for successful implementation were discussed. All these points were shared in text form with the pilots as workshop organization guidelines and recommendations.

An essential component of pathways workshop preparation was the development of prompts for each objective. These prompts ensured that identifying actions through the unpacking objectives exercise would target topics such as economy, governance, engagement, and spatial interventions. This also supported facilitation efforts, as session facilitators often had limited experience in workshop moderation. These prompts were derived by the authors of the methodology (TSPA) in collaboration with UIC, who led the development of the benchmarking framework.

During the preparation sessions, several cities decided to conduct interviews with key experts instead of holding a single workshop. Some cities, like Milan and Granollers, opted for a targeted approach, organizing interview sessions with technical stakeholders. This allowed for a deeper dive into the technical aspects for unpacking pilot objectives (that includes assessment of ecosystem services, or certain governance changes in terms of upgrading tendering processes linked to urban transformation projects), identifying related risks and alternative paths more comprehensively. Meanwhile, pilot of Rotterdam chose to alter the workshop method by asking each participant to note down their minimum and maximum contributions towards the objectives. This approach allowed to form a direct connection to key stakeholders, turning the workshop session outcomes into more operative and individual contributions, and clarifying the commitment and responsibilities of each involved party. Also, each case decided individually whether to identify risks per objective, allowing a deeper dive into each objective, or to do it as a revision, identifying risks and alternative actions after the first round of action identifications.

In some other cases, such as Münster, Lisbon, and Zagreb, the actions and risks that fed into the pathway's development were identified by the city team, distilled from the first workshop on the vision outcomes or based on their knowledge of the pilot project. On the other hand, Istanbul decided to not produce adaptive pathways.

Consolidated and translated results from the workshops were then analysed by the technical partners. The analysis was led by TSPA, who also involved other experts with expertise in governance, finance, engagement and urban planning and design, helping to create more comprehensive pathways. The results were then shared with cities for revision and validation. In some cases, the additional iteration was needed to further elaborate actions or risk.

5.2. [Application Process in Pilot Cities](#)

This section provides an in-depth introduction and overview of the application process in each pilot city, detailing the proposed and adopted methodology and reflections on the process. It presents the final outputs, including co-designed pilot visions represented by vision pages and the initial outcomes of the adaptive pathways process.

This section was developed together with pilot cities and their liaisons, who contributed to the narrative, especially focusing on providing their insight to the *Reflections* sections.

5.2.1. [Belfast](#)

Through UP2030, Belfast seeks to create a framework that will be applied in all its regeneration projects which integrates tree planting, green infrastructure, play and co-design with young people. The framework will be tested in the Linen Quarter district, which has been identified to become the first sustainable and net zero business district in Northern Ireland. Lessons learned from this pilot will be useful to identify opportunities in other neighbourhoods and upscale the concept of net-zero districts across the city.

5.2.1. [Proposed process and its applications](#)

During the visioning phase, several meetings were held between the task lead and the city team, including the liaisons, to discuss workshop organization details and customise and contextualise the UP2030 methodology.

It was decided that Belfast would organize an extended session to address both the vision and adaptive pathways. Belfast instead took the approach of splitting up sessions based on three key thematic groups: Active Mobility, Greening, and Retrofitting.

As one of the initial steps in preparation for the co-visioning process, the city conducted an extensive revision of the objectives, applying the *Theory of Change* method to distil the desirable impacts and outputs of the project. This was particularly focused on greening strategies, active mobility, and retrofitting topics and tailored to the stakeholders involved in each working group. This process helped identify short-, medium-, and long-term outputs and the necessary activities to achieve them.

Belfast's focus on community engagement, particularly involving youth, significantly influenced the recommended methods. For example, additional activities such as *Participatory Mapping with Children* were included.

Figure 16 Belfast Recommended Co-Visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)

Additionally, the *Community Maps* platform was offered to support efforts in gathering information on all ongoing projects. This interactive platform allows users to mark projects on a map and provide detailed information, facilitating knowledge sharing and identifying ongoing or planned projects that could impact or contribute to project goals. The information provided by the city was later incorporated into the platform with the support of city liaisons, revealing synergies among the ongoing projects.

The platform was further enriched with spatial climate data and presented in the vision workshop to facilitate discussions on spatial challenges and solutions.

Figure 17 Screenshot of the Community Maps platform, showcasing projects related to the UP2030 activities, which could maximise or support project efforts.

5.2.1. Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

A series of workshops were held over the course of the co-visioning process, culminating in an online session to present and validate the results. The first meeting took place on April 16th for the City of Belfast, engaging a range of cross-departmental stakeholders within the Council. The purpose of this workshop was to contextualize the UP2030 programme, gather input on priorities and interventions across thematic areas that could shape the vision for a net-zero framework, and explore actions, risks, mitigation strategies, and other opportunities for transforming a neighbourhood in Belfast towards net-zero.

Figure 20 Moment from the co-visioning workshop.

Figure 21 Illustrations capturing ideas from the workshop discussions.

This session was followed by a workshop with youth, represented by the Alternatives Youth group. The purpose of the session was to engage young people living in the pilot area and introduce UP2030 and climate change challenges, and to gather their perspectives and ideas for a climate-neutral neighbourhood and how the transition can be fair. The session included two exercises: "Map My Future" and collaborative mapping.

On April 17th, the city held two additional sessions with the greening and active mobility groups. To define the pillar visions, the *Mentimeter* platform was used. Participants shared three words that represent Carbon Neutrality, Resilience, and Just and Fair Transition. Additionally, the "Future Newspaper" exercise was conducted to brainstorm headlines for a net-zero future Belfast in 2050. The Adaptive Pathways method was also employed to distil actions needed to achieve these visions. Meanwhile, an illustrator captured the participants' ideas, visually depicting the vision of a net-zero, resilient, and just Belfast.

The active travel group focused on engaging various organizations and departments connected with sustainable travel. The goal was to contextualize the UP2030 programme, gather input on priorities and interventions, and explore actions, risks, mitigations, and opportunities for achieving a net-zero neighbourhood in Belfast. A similar workshop was held with experts from the greening group that consisted of stakeholders from key organizations and departments working on city greening, health, research, and housing sectors.

The last session with the retrofitting group was held on May 22nd. This workshop engaged the Retrofit Steering Group to contextualize the UP2030 programme, gather input on priorities and interventions, and to explore actions, risks, mitigations, and opportunities for achieving a net-zero neighbourhood in Belfast. Because the cluster already has advanced with their program and activities, this session was organised

differently. The main outcome of this session was the vision statement for the retrofitting group: "Retrofitting is the act of adapting a building to increase energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption through a range of interventions such as modifications to the building fabric (insulation, airtightness improvement, ventilation, new and improved windows and doors), new or improved low carbon heating systems, and renewable energy generation."

The final joint session was held on May 31st with all stakeholders to validate the results from the previous sessions and present the initial outputs of the vision and adaptive pathways.

The results of Belfast's vision, including illustrations presenting the vision, key objectives, and the unified vision statement, were added to the vision page below.

Creating net-zero neighbourhoods in Belfast

To create a climate neutral neighbourhood that adapts and mitigates climate risks through increased greening, better sustainable transport and more energy efficient buildings to act as a beacon of success for other neighbourhoods

Climate neutrality will be achieved in a fair and just way by involving the community, along with other stakeholders, to develop more sustainable, accessible and affordable transport, better quality of homes through retrofitting buildings, and access to good quality green space. The communities will become the champions and drivers of its success, with opportunities of training for green jobs, community management of public spaces and ambassadors for public and active travel. This requires a collaborative approach across all levels and departments of governance, the third sector and private organisations.

Just Transition

Co-create an inclusive, more equitable and fair society where all communities are aware and included in a democratic, accessible and transparent way to take ownership and benefit from the actions to support carbon neutrality, including new jobs, better homes and affordable sustainable transport.

Net-Zero

Take an ambitious approach to the challenge of carbon neutrality through greening, sustainable travel, green energy and better buildings to provide clean air, green space and healthy environment for all to live.

Resilience

Take a democratic and sustainable approach to be prepared, adapt and mitigate climate risk and shocks including flooding to create a safe and thriving neighbourhood.

Figure 22 Vision for Belfast Pilot. Side A

Figure 23 Vision for Belfast Pilot. Side B

5.2.1. Reflections

The Vision workshops were well received, as noted in the survey results completed by a sample of workshop attendees. Many appreciated the opportunity to work alongside peers from different disciplines to approach this topic, looking at both challenges and opportunities, and noted the benefit of focusing on just one area within the city through the project.

Did the workshop improve or fill gaps in your level of understanding of the topic of net zero delivery?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

Would you be interested in future collaboration based on the discussions during the workshop?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

Do you feel like you now have a good understanding of what UP2030 is and what it is trying to achieve?

Answered: 10 Skipped: 0

The workshops successfully engaged participants through various tools and methods, such as Mentimeter and the Future Newspaper exercise, which generated productive group discussions. However, more time was needed to thoroughly work through the adaptive pathways, potentially incorporating the interactive map.

Figure 24 Results of survey conducted at the end of the vision workshop.

It was observed that engagement techniques that stimulate discussions using maps and data can be very beneficial. A clearer timeframe should also be set, outlining milestones for achieving net zero by 2050, ensuring progress by 2030, setting actions for 2026-2030, and focusing on 2024-2025 for framework development.

General feedback from participants was positive, but there was a consensus that the information needs to be more widely disseminated to community groups for further input. Key topics consistently raised included the need for green spaces, growing opportunities, car-free zones, better active travel infrastructure, and accessible public transport. Unfortunately, not all community representatives attended, including those from Sandy Row and Barrack Street.

Participants valued the creative approaches and the interactive nature of the workshop. Mapping climate change impacts on neighbourhoods was particularly useful for increasing understanding. Although some tasks, like the future newspaper article, were seen as less effective, the workshop overall fostered valuable learning and cross-disciplinary collaboration. However, it also highlighted the importance of including the wider community in these critical discussions to ensure comprehensive and inclusive strategies.

5.2.2. Budapest

Budapest's aim through UP2030 is to and disseminate the Healthy Streets process and methodology through the city, across districts, and between departments. *Healthy Streets* is a human-centred approach developed in London by Lucy Saunders. This framework uses social, economic, and environmental sustainability indicators that describe an aspect of the human experience of being on streets, to embed public health in transit, the public realm, and planning (Healthy Streets, 2023). To upscale the Healthy Streets approach, Budapest adapts two methods. The city is facilitating street upgrades through a tendering process supported by the EU, enabling districts to apply for and receive funding. Budapest developed a Call for Proposals on applying the Healthy Streets methodology, and as of mid-June 2024, is evaluating the proposals. In addition to the funding proposals, the objectives of the pilot were expanded with the aim to upscale the Healthy streets methodology, i.e., to achieve the widespread application and adaptation of the Healthy Streets method in practice. This is to be done by urban development professionals, via the development of active dissemination methods, involvement of locals, establishment of a knowledge centre and knowledge sharing platform, and involvement and mobilization urban development professionals. The goal is to share the learnings and knowledge such that professionals can apply the Healthy Streets approach in upgrading and developing public spaces in both private and public practice, create guides and standards, and in general expand the impacts to a significantly wider reach. Ultimately, this is to contribute to a more liveable, people-oriented city whose public spaces are vibrant, facilitate communal, social, and ecological resilience, and promote social interaction.

5.2.2. Proposed process and its application

The proposed visioning process for Budapest was not heavily influenced by spatial engagement methods, since the Healthy Streets programme pilot lacked a specific spatial focus; instead of focusing on one neighbourhood or street, upgraded streets will be scattered all over the city depending on successful application of districts for the funding. Instead, the visioning process was proposed to focus on activities to develop an engagement strategy that could facilitate the co-development of a vision that would align with the aims for program development and an awareness-building effort would target both the city-level the district-level, in support of the tendering process and upscaling of the Healthy Streets methodology. The *Thematic Brainstorming* and *Future Newspaper* methods were suggested for the city. The Thematic Brainstorming method was proposed to help Budapest in reducing the complexity of the process and to develop and thematically categorise pillar visions, for each of the resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition aspects of the project. The Future Newspaper method, on the other hand, was proposed to assist Budapest's stakeholders in defining a holistic pilot vision by collectively defining an ambitious, but realistic future for the programme and the areas it would affect through the lens of carbon neutrality.

In practice, the first visioning workshop took place on January 17th, 2024, with the core LAA of the Budapest Healthy Streets program aimed to achieve a few objectives. The Visioning workshop brought together key stakeholders, including representatives from Budapest City Hall, the Budapest Transport Company (BKK), and the NGO Járókelő. Additionally, experts from the Budapest City Planning Co. (BFVT) participated (i.e. the core LAA). The first visioning workshop first sought to validate and refine the project's objectives that include the broader goals of Budapest Healthy Streets. The broader objectives of the Budapest pilot – looking beyond the scope of implementation of the winning Healthy Streets proposals through tendering – have been defined in a dedicated workshop held in November 2023 with Budapest's liaison, GGGI. A further objective of first visioning workshop was to create a clear and unified vision, through the definition

of pillar statements and vision statements to guide the project through UP2030 and beyond. And additionally, to define high-level action plans that outlined concrete steps to achieve these objectives within the pilot project, to begin building towards the adaptive pathways.

The second workshop, for adaptive pathways was held on April 24th, 2024, with the LAA. Group work had been proposed to fill in provided templates for unpacking objectives into actions and for the identification of risks and alternative strategies. Templates and instructions were provided to the city in to use for these purposes, utilising prompts pre-defined by TSPA and UIC to encourage stakeholders to consider a wide range of actions, barriers, and risks required to achieve their objectives. (prompts can be found in the Annex section 8.3.2)

Figure 25 Belfast Recommended Co-Visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)

5.2.2. Vision and Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

Budapest have conducted two sessions for co-designing visions and adaptive pathways. The first session – the visioning workshop – was held on the 17th of January 2024. The Visioning workshop brought together key stakeholders, including representatives from Budapest City Hall, the Budapest Transport Company (BKK), and the NGO Járókelő. Additionally, experts from the Budapest City Planning Co. (BFVT) participated.

At the workshop, Budapest’s LAA worked in groups utilising the Thematic Brainstorming method to validate the objectives and to come up with high-level action plans and goals for the city’s streets and public spaces along the lines of carbon neutrality, resilience, and the just transition.

Figure 26 Vision Workshop in Budapest

The development of the holistic vision process for the workshop proved to be more challenging than anticipated. Instead of working in separate groups as initially planned, participants began brainstorming together (which worked well as number of participants present did not exceed 15 people), jotting down key words and ideas collectively. The approach to developing vision ideas included defining the desired characteristics of Budapest's public spaces and outlining the steps needed to achieve these characteristics. Rather than strictly following the Future Newspaper steps, the exercise resembled a thematic brainstorming

session. As mentioned above, Budapest's pilot is not location-specific, hence no spatial analysis or common vision was conducted. Instead, the process involved generating "catchphrases" and discussing whether the vision should describe an outcome or a process. There was also a debate on whether the vision should be a short 2- or 3-word catchphrase with a longer explanatory part, which could also serve as the "mission," or a longer vision that includes more goals with less explanation in the mission and more focus on the steps to achieve it.

At the end of the workshop, with some time remaining, participants began jotting down ideas related to each objective, including short-, mid-, and long-term actions, any identified risks or barriers, and recommendations for new objectives or modifications, which contributed to the next visioning workshop on adaptive pathways.

The input from the session was further iterated by the city team with the involvement of both the Urban planning and Climate departments, with the help of a communication expert from the latter department. The vision was defined for the longer-term outlook of the Healthy Streets approach; the programme aims to achieve in terms of impact beyond the scope of the pilot and prototype within UP2030. In short, Budapest envisions a liveable, people-centred city with high-quality public spaces that promote social interaction, climate resilience, and environmentally conscious transport. The city aims to harmonize communities with green and blue infrastructure, fostering sustainability and reducing carbon footprints through active transport, while enhancing urban resilience against climate impacts. The vision page can be found below in figure 27.

Healthy Streets for Budapest

Liveable, people-centred Budapest

Our vision is to create a liveable, people-centred city, where every element of design builds on a harmonious synergy of communities, green and blue infrastructure and sustainability, creating high quality public spaces that promote social interaction, climate resilience and environmentally conscious and active transport and public space use.

Just Transition

The reimagined urban life is built on a close harmony between human relationships and the natural environment. We are committed to taking into account the perspectives of local communities, the interests of city dwellers, and both existing and future conditions in all aspects of urban planning. The creation of areas free from consumption pressure and public spaces where certain groups do not appropriate places.

Carbon Neutrality

Public spaces offer opportunities for human interaction, relaxation and recreation. Areas designed in this way promote walking and cycling, thereby supporting the physical and mental health of the population, as well as reducing the carbon footprint of urban areas.

Resilience

We are creating public spaces that improve the quality of urban life, have a stimulating economic impact and result in more resilient infrastructure and cohesive communities in the face of changing climate impacts. In doing so, we not only protect biodiversity but also improve the resilience of urban spaces to climate impacts.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

Figure 27 Vision for Budapest's Pilot

The second workshop was held on 24th of April 2024. It was successful in generating ideas and suggestions for implementing the objectives. Although attendance was moderate (again participants were around 15 people), the participants who attended were very active. Initially, the workshop revisited the vision

statement and pillar visions: 30 minutes had been allocated to finalize the vision, as the content had been pre-prepared based upon the first workshop. However, the group up spent significant additional time brainstorming to refine it and discuss how and where Budapest would use the vision statement.

Figure 28 Unpacking Objectives during the adaptive pathways workshop

Group work had been proposed to fill in provided templates for unpacking objectives into actions and for the identification of risks. Participants preferred to work individually, moving around the templates and jotting down their ideas, occasionally discussing them ad hoc with nearby colleagues. This approach allowed participants to focus on the objectives they were most interested in and knowledgeable about. Finally, interdependencies between actions were identified by Zoltán (City Hall) and Diana Kupper (GGGI) following the workshop.

Translated actions were shared for assessment with technical partners, who further clustered and sequenced the actions into draft adaptive pathways. Together with other project partners including GGGI, BH, Adelphi and UIC the adaptive pathways were analysed for gaps and shared with the city for a final revision of clarifications and questions.

Some of the key cross-cutting themes identified for Budapest's adaptive pathways are community engagement and participation, education and awareness, and standards and framework development. Some clusters regarding engagement include actions pertaining to actively involving local citizens in the planning and implementation process as well as ensuring they have a stake in the outcomes. For education and awareness, clusters of actions build towards a focus on raising public knowledge and their involvement through mapping tools and effectively disseminating the benefits of Healthy Streets initiatives through various communication channels and workshops. Standards and framework development clusters emphasize the need to assess and if possible, develop a higher regulatory system at the municipal level and the creation of robust guidelines to ensure consistency and effectiveness in urban development.

The adaptive pathways page, summarizing the clusters of actions and their sequencing relative to each other can be found below, while the database containing the adaptive pathways in their entirety can be found in Annex section 8.4.2.

5.2.2. Reflections

Regarding the defining of the vision, in both workshops more time was needed than initially allocated. In the first workshop the group took a lot of time to come to an agreement and circle down on the most important topics to be involved in the vision statement. In the second workshop we spent quite some time reviewing and refining each word. This part also involved some negotiation and compromise. This highlights that each word in a vision statement must be considered carefully and “negotiated” between participants, to arrive at a statement that fully supports the objectives of the program and finds a careful balance of being high level enough to include several goals, but not too much to lose meaning and focus.

In terms of approaches used, participants at times preferred group work (especially in defining the visions), and other times preferred to work individually in their own space, which allowed them to focus on items they were more knowledgeable about or involved in.

5.2.3. Granollers

With UP2030, Granollers aims to build towards developing an inclusive and equitable carbon neutral district in the La Bòbila sector. Through the process of developing the plans, policies, and capacities necessary to achieve their ambition on the site, Granollers will prototype a set of development guidelines for upscaling the process to other neighbourhoods and developments in the city going forwards. Granollers has the ambition to integrate and expand ongoing initiatives. In doing so Granollers intends to bring together departments, plans, and a wide set of programmes to take a holistic approach to integrating carbon neutrality, resilience, and a just transition. Ultimately, the city is pushing to expand and link green spaces throughout the city and the La Bòbila site, to integrate Nature Based Solutions, to prevent gentrification and maintain equity and inclusion through social and affordable housing, and to define the policy measures necessary to achieve such ambitions. In turn, the city hopes to eventually upscale the approach to develop multiple other carbon-neutral areas by 2030.

5.2.3. Proposed process and its application

The engagement methods recommended included more spatially oriented exercises in the context of new urban developments, such as *Design Charrette* and *Common Vision*, given the context of the pilot as a new urban development on an uninhabited site. Granollers completed the first stage of the Co-visioning, Milestone 1, through validation of the objectives taken from the various processes in the first year of the UP2030 process. A capacity training, to support the liaison in facilitating visioning activities with the city, was held in November 2023 with Granollers' liaison, Aquatec.

The co-visioning process in Granollers was performed in two steps. The first one took place in a plenary workshop in January 2024 with 35 attendees where the collaborative methods problem tree and common vision were used. The *Problem Tree* method allowed to review, validate and complement the results obtained at the previous Needs and Challenges workshop, while the *Common Vision* method contributed to spatially identifying existing and future initiatives related to each one of the 3 pillar objectives of the pilot, to align them with local plans and strategies and to identify the needs for their implementation.

The second step consisted of two specific workshops, held in April 2024 and attended by 30 people in total, intended to connect the UP2030 project to diverse social and cultural groups (which for various reasons were not able to attend the plenary workshops) and to integrate and consider their opinion in the co-visioning process. The methodology used to compile this valuable contribution was the *Future Newspaper* given its possibilities to facilitate contributions in an easy and understandable way.

All the results from the application of the process in Granollers were uploaded to the digital platform [Participa](#), which is the channel that facilitates informing stakeholders from outside the group directly involved in the workshops and receiving their feedback.

Figure 29 Granollers Recommended Co-visionsing Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)

Figure 30 Vision workshop in Granollers.

5.2.3. Vision and Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

Granollers held their first visioning session on the 24th of January 2024 with a wide range of stakeholders. The internal stakeholders included politicians and technical staff from the departments of: Environment and Green areas, Urban Planning, Municipal Services, City Projects, Green Transition and Resilience,

Mobility, Civil Protection, Housing, GIS and Data, Public Health, New Citizenship, Creativity, Economic Promotion and Participation. The external stakeholders included municipal representatives of political groups, citizen associations of Granollers, Granollers Merchant Association Centre, Catalanoblear Society of Internal Medicine, Catalan Institute of Health, Chamber of Urban Property, Public transport operator Sagalés, Cetaqua, AGBAR, Fundación Ecologia Urbana y Territorial FEUT, AGBAR/ Director Dinapsis Granollers, and Blocs Vallès Architects, and other citizens.

Through the visioning workshop, Granollers had the intention to validate the results from their first engagement workshop which focused on needs and barriers, to present the ongoing urban planning projects and programmes within the city, and to co-create a shared vision and strategy for the future of the neighbourhood. They also planned to give a presentation to inspire and enlighten the stakeholders regarding transformative strategies for preventing and managing the risks of climate change.

Figure 31 Results of problem tree method, conducted in vision workshop.

The workshop accomplished these intentions by utilising two of the methods which were recommended in the Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement. First, they utilised the Problem Tree method, whereby they identified, expanded, and validated the underlying challenges related to carbon neutral planning in La Bòbila. Building off three starting points, central problems which had been identified along the lines of the three project pillars, they worked towards corrective actions for each pillar. For the carbon neutrality pillar, the starting point was the 'Lack of strategic coordination between local actors.' For the resilience pillar, the starting point was the 'Lack of quality public green spaces that actively contribute to the quality of life of citizens.' And for the Just Transition pillar, the starting point was 'Lack of adequate financing for affordable housing.' The results from the exercise can be seen in *Figure 31*.

Building upon the problem tree exercise, the workshop utilised the Common Vision method to build a

Figure 32 Preparation for the vision workshop.

holistic vision for the future of the neighbourhood. Through this process the stakeholders were put into groups each with a different objective and worked towards identifying specific pilot concepts for the pillar visions, and ultimately a unified pilot vision statement. These groups additionally unpacked the objectives into groups of actions, building towards the adaptive pathways' development. Whilst doing so, key pre-existing, ongoing and forthcoming plans, programmes, and policies were identified for strategic alignment. To spatialise the vision, the stakeholders did a mapping exercise to locate key green and grey infrastructural components vision. Afterwards, this map was digitised into a shapefile (.shp) and shared with the tool providers. The consolidated pillar visions, pilot vision statement, and validated objectives, can be found in *Figure 32*.

Granollers carried forward by building upon the visioning workshop to further develop the adaptive pathways. Engaging 5 technical managers of municipal services through in-depth interviews, objectives were unpacked further into actions, and associated risks were identified. The departments engaged were Environment and Green Space, Urban Planning, Energy Transition and Water Cycle, Mobility, and Strategic Planning and Citizenship. The interviews utilised prompts which TSPA and UIC had developed based upon the previous vision session and the benchmarking filter. (Prompts can be found in the section 8.3.3)

Figure 33 Digitised results from Common Vision mapping methods.

In turn, the documentation of the actions from both the vision workshop in January 2024, the interim meeting and the interviews from April 2024 were shared with technical partners to consolidate, synthesize, and sequence. Actions were consolidated into larger groups of thematically related clusters. Working with technical project partners, these clusters were assessed for gaps, and shared back with the city for validation and clarification. Finally, the actions, risks, and mitigation strategies were packaged into a database to be shared with the city to help navigate the next steps and action phase of the UP2030 project.

The results from the workshop consolidated into the initial version of adaptive pathways can be found in Annex 8.4.3.

Future Vision for La Bòbila Neighborhood

Resilient and sustainable neighborhood with opportunities for everyone

Granollers wants to move forward in a healthy and sustainable urban model that puts people at the center. The city is committed to integrating green spaces, mobility and digital infrastructures to foster communities that are connected and respectful of nature and planetary boundaries¹. Through initiatives such as a citizen laboratory, mobility as a service (MaaS), and sustainable energy and circular economy solutions, it is proposed to improve the quality of life in Granollers, while continuing to reduce emissions and adaptation to them in the face of the effects of the climate crisis on an urban scale: floods and the increase in temperature. This approach includes promoting mixed-use city developments, affordable housing and universal accessibility to ensure that all residents benefit from a culturally rich, equitable and adaptable urban environment. This vision integrates the objectives and actions necessary to create a prosperous² city with opportunities for all.

Just Neighborhood: social justice and economic viability

Neighborhood resilient to climate crisis: balance between infrastructure and creative innovation

Climate neutral neighborhood: systemic approach and coordination between plans and programs

The ecological transition that has into account the maintenance of jobs and the creation of activity in the new neighborhood to be developed, supporting population groups at risk, and that promotes diversification and specialization consistent with the social and economic context local.

The capacity of an ecosystem to resist and recover stability in the face of the effects of climate change. In the case of Granollers, the main climatic vulnerabilities are floods and the increase in temperature.

A situation in which there is a zero balance between greenhouse gas emissions and their absorption through carbon sinks. Carbon neutrality can be achieved at a local, regional, national, European or global scale, and also at the level of a company or organisation, or even in relation to a product or service.

Figure 34 Vision Page for Granollers Pilot.

5.2.3. Reflections

The co-visioning process, including visioning and adaptive pathways workshops and activities, enabled the Granollers pilot to initiate a holistic, integrative, and inclusive process for envisioning and co-designing the future La Bòbila neighbourhood. This process allowed the city pilot to validate the final objectives, envision the expected results, and establish a starting point to define a sequence of actions in the short, medium, and long term to materialize the defined objective and vision. This, therefore, represents the starting point for working on the prototype and scalability of the results.

The city and liaison felt that improvements in the application of the process could be made in terms of greater coordination to adapt the methodology and content further, to achieve all the expected outcomes for each phase. The stakeholders targeted by the Granollers pilot are diverse in areas of knowledge, interests, and cultural origins, requiring extra effort to localize the methodologies and materials to the specific city pilot context.

Regarding opportunities of the vision process, it was felt that it has the potential to be a very friendly and accessible way of fostering stakeholder participation, interaction, and creating synergies. This made it possible to share participants' visions on urban planning design, which is sometimes perceived as a distant question from our daily lives but with a high impact on our quality of life. It has also served as a meeting point for understanding the diversity of needs and challenges between stakeholders, policymakers, and decision-makers, to move forward with the prosperity of a new district to be developed in the city, with the common good as the denominator.

As a strength of the application of the vision, it can be highlighted that a large amount of information and content has been transferred to the participants in a short time. This fact has allowed the city to co-create and consolidate a common vision as the basis for the future city district. This basis (climate-neutral city, resilience, and social inclusion) is aligned with the action plan for the present political mandate in Granollers (2023-27): a city with more green and healthy public spaces, a city with opportunities for everyone, and a city committed to a diverse and local economic model.

5.2.4. Istanbul

Istanbul's aim within the UP2030 project is to inform decision making through a mix of data modelling and on-ground implementation of urban furniture and PV panels in the selected neighbourhood. The broader aim is to create a pilot for positive-energy districts. Istanbul's pilot area is Kadıköy, given its position as a high traffic transit point with multiple transportation modes available.

5.2.4. Proposed process and its application

The suggested methodology included spatial assessment to capitalise on synergies with other projects in the pilot area and to see how UP2030 can fit in. Integrated spatial analysis would support the strategizing on opportunities and objectives for mobility hubs, decarbonizing buildings, and further defining social benefits. Additionally, it would allow identification of areas most prone to climate hazards and most affected communities in Kadıköy. The next step was to include validation of objectives, to ensure the goals are up to date. These preparatory activities were suggested to ensure that the process builds on previously gathered content to build a holistic vision.

Figure 35 Istanbul’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023).

For defining pillar visions – contextualising resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition goals city have conducted one-on-one interviews to facilitate a structured exploration of the underlying causes and effects related to Kadıköy’s carbon neutrality goals. This approach utilized collaborative discussions, and one-on-one meetings, allowing stakeholders to thoroughly examine and dissect the central challenges of achieving carbon neutrality in Kadıköy.

Feedback from citizen surveys provided a comprehensive view of the community's perspective, enriching the problem analysis and ensuring a broad-based understanding of the issues at hand.

For the vision workshops, Istanbul chose to conduct online sessions. A key part of the meeting involved engaging stakeholders in an exercise to envision impactful climate-related headlines for 2030. To achieve these goals, the workshop utilized an interactive platform (Mentimeter) to collect and prioritize elements contributing to carbon neutrality, ensuring an efficient and engaging experience. A set of guiding questions with prompts was offered to the city team to guide the discussion. This helped evaluate various aspects of the project, from renewable energy to social welfare and urban planning. This participatory approach allowed stakeholders to rank priorities and barriers, ensuring that the outcomes reflected a collective viewpoint.

5.2.4. Vision and Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

The vision workshop was held on 22nd of February, aimed to establish actionable priorities for Kadıköy to advance towards carbon neutrality. The session focused on identifying strategies for a just transition to greener practices, encouraging social participation in carbon neutrality efforts, and assessing the opportunities and benefits of the UP2030 project. Additionally, it aimed to recognize and prioritize barriers and risks to successful project implementation and determine optimal areas for utilizing Kadıköy’s solar energy potential. Participants also discussed the possible contributions of the renewable energy potentials to the citizens and the city.

The sessions included various stakeholders, including representatives from the municipal administration, experts from the energy sector, public transportation and sustainable mobility, NGOs related to the

expertise in energy efficiency and green buildings, technology providers. Lastly, scholars and researchers supported the project with evidence-based planning and technical knowledge.

Figure 36 Moments from the vision workshop

The meeting resulted in the definition of a vision statement and future scenario, meanwhile, pillar visions were defined in November, during the one-on-one interviews. The outputs, along with key objectives, were gathered into the vision page (Figure 37).

The primary vision of the project is to unequivocally demonstrate to citizens, practitioners, and decision-makers that solar energy has the potential to significantly meet the substantial energy demands of buildings and everyday urban activities. By harnessing solar energy, Istanbul aims to showcase how this renewable energy source can be seamlessly integrated into urban landscapes, transforming our cities into hubs of sustainability. This initiative is not just about energy provision, it is about making a meaningful contribution towards Istanbul's ambitious goal of carbon neutrality for the city. The city believes that it can create an urban environment that not only meets the energy needs of its inhabitants but also serves as a beacon of environmental stewardship and innovation.

Regarding the adaptive pathways step, the city has decided to not conduct the suggested activities. It was stated that “in the previous needs & analysis workshop, vision workshop, and citizen survey, [they] have already discussed with the stakeholders about activities. [They] therefore decided that there was no need to organise a separate and special meeting for adaptive pathways.”

Forging a Greener Kadıköy and İstanbul

A Pioneering region with green energy, smart infrastructure, and community vitality

Prioritising regional renewable energy production to generate impact on achieving carbon neutrality in Kadıköy, İstanbul. There is a strong desire for energy autonomy and reducing reliance on external energy sources Robust Disaster Preparedness and Green Infrastructure: The adaptation to climate change with a strong focus on disaster preparedness and the enhancement of green infrastructure emerged as key themes. This indicates a proactive approach to not only addressing the current environmental challenges but also fortifying Kadıköy against future risks. Additionally, greater work towards updating Kadıköy’s buildings to be more energy-efficient and suitable for supporting new energy systems. sustainable and uninterrupted access to energy in urban planning resonated as an essential factor for a fair green transition. This reflects a commitment to ensure that Kadıköy’s shift to sustainable practices is equitable and inclusive.

Social Equity and Inclusivity

In Kadıköy, we envisage a future where every resident benefits from the district’s progress towards carbon neutrality. This means forging pathways to ensure that social equity is embedded in every strategy, from urban planning to environmental policy, guaranteeing inclusivity and equal access to the benefits of green initiatives for all demographics and communities within Kadıköy.

Integrated Sustainable Development

Our vision is for Kadıköy to be recognized as an exemplar of integrated sustainable development, characterized by the convergence of economic resilience, social equity, and environmental stewardship to create a dynamic urban fabric. It is aimed for the district to be transformed into an entity that thrives economically while upholding responsible practices, thus cultivating a just society that is well-prepared to meet future challenges.

Environmental Innovation and Resilience

Kadıköy’s vision encompasses a commitment to environmental innovation and resilience, creating adaptive pathways that embrace flexibility and the latest technologies. As we move towards a carbon-neutral future, our strategies will be shaped by a readiness to adopt new, sustainable technologies, agile policy-making, and a proactive stance on environmental and societal changes, ensuring Kadıköy not only endures but flourishes in the face of global environmental challenges.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405

Figure 37 Vision for İstanbul’s Pilot.

5.2.4. Reflections

Kadıköy is a popular neighbourhood, therefore it's helpful to access more stakeholders and engage wider groups. When determining the pilot region as Kadıköy, not only the fact that it is a crowded transit point but also the possibility of obtaining quality and sufficient data required for modelling studies was taken into consideration.

Particularly for the visibility of PV urban furniture, it will be important to choose a public space that is a crossroads for people from many different socio-cultural backgrounds (vulnerable groups: students, low-income workers, etc.).

- It was observed, as a weakness, that often it is hard to promote new and innovative ideas because citizens held scepticism to novelty or change.
- In the workshop, the participants were asked for their opinions on the pilot region and the prioritised studies deemed necessary in Istanbul. Mentimeter was used to compile quick responses and then those who wished to contribute with wider comments.
- Starting with a video introducing the project attracted the attention of the participants.

That the results of the project will form the basis for implementing the project is positively welcomed. Financial priorities raise a question mark in participants' minds about investing in new technologies. It needs to be supported by regulations and incentive mechanisms.

Figure 38 Moments from the workshop.

Istanbul has concluded that for the carbon-neutral transformation of cities, it is essential for users, citizens, and decision-makers to numerically quantify the energy consumed by buildings (heating, cooling, electricity, etc.), the thermal comfort of occupants, the amount of energy that can be produced from solar energy, and the impact of proposed retrofit scenarios on building energy performance and occupant comfort. This numerical representation can be achieved through the development of physics-based (energy

simulations) and data-driven machine learning models. However, to perform comprehensive and realistic urban-scale energy simulations and train data-driven ML models, there is a need for:

- geometric data, such as building footprints and floor heights, and
- semantic information related to zones, including thermal conductivity of envelope elements, window properties, and occupant-related information.

The municipal Directorates of Geographical Information Systems, Mapping and Urban Planning, and Smart Cities at IMM are actively engaged in providing both geometric and semantic data to support such energy models and data-driven ML models. This initiative is focused on supplying the necessary inputs required for the development and effective operation of these models within the context of urban energy management and planning.

Going forwards, it will be necessary for the citizen to decide for which purpose solar energy would be most practical (e.g. indoor lighting, transfer to micromobility or direct sale to the grid, etc.) the potential will be calculated by the model. As factors such as roof type and building structure are important in maximising solar energy potential, the model results will also provide a vision for the architectural structure of the city in the years to come.

There has been a common understanding identified that decision makers as local and central government should work effectively on regulation and financial incentive mechanisms to have an impact on the emergence of model outputs and the implementation and neutrality of the city after the project is completed.

By increasing the awareness of citizens and supporting them with incentives, it can be ensured that they prefer sustainable energy technologies as building and micro mobility users.

5.2.5. Lisbon

Under the UP2030 project, Lisbon's overall aim is to design a carbon-neutral neighbourhood that strengthens climate resilience and promotes an active, fair, and committed community to change. The approach will be tested and validated at the parish of Alvalade, with four intervention areas. The project aims to monitor the co-benefits of climate action through green initiatives and integrate intelligent decision support systems. Further developments include a portfolio of solutions and identification of critical locations to ensure the successful implementation of these objectives.

5.2.5. *Proposed process and it's applications*

Given the spatial aspects to Lisbon's pilot focus areas as well as their intended next steps for promoting synergies between projects and partners, the visioning process was shaped by spatial analysis and representation (Integrated Spatial Analysis, Community Mapping, and the Common Vision).

The city chose to organise a capacity building session with selected stakeholders. During the meeting project, progress was presented, diving deeper into four selected project areas – LNEC headquarters, Alvalade market, a municipal library and a rugby club. Stakeholders from each location had seven minutes to present seven challenges and propose solutions, showcasing replicable good practices for developing net-zero, just and climate resilient neighbourhoods.

Figure 39 Lisbon's Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023).

Figure 40 Lisbon's workshop on co-visioning methods (Source: CML, 2024).

After the presentations, the city fostered a debate including an 8-question mentimeter survey, which allowed to direct the discussion to the visioning process.

5.2.5. *Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes*

Figure 41 Vision workshop in Lisbon.

The vision workshop was held on the 28th of February 2024, focusing on the city's objectives of achieving carbon neutrality, resilience to climate change and inclusion. The event highlighted the importance of addressing current challenges through urban planning interventions aimed at applying the objectives to Alvalade and eventually replicating them in Lisbon.

The aim of the city is to continue the work carried out in Alvalade, engaging various local actors and partners to promote and implement local solutions to meet climate adaptation goals by 2030. The vision for Alvalade was distilled together with the task leaders. The process resulted in creating vision statements and future scenarios that was then edited and validated by city and liaison partners. Furthermore, vision pillars, reflecting how carbon neutrality, resilience and just transition are addressed were defined. The outputs, along with key objectives, were gathered into the vision page (Figure 42)

In terms of adaptive pathways activities, the city has distilled the actions needed to continue further four project implementations internally. The results, shared with the technical partners were further developed into the initial version of adaptive pathways. The initial version can be found in the Annex section 8.4.4.

Rethink Alvalade 2030

Towards Carbon Neutrality through four pilot locations in Alvalade

Focusing on pilot interventions at four locations – a library, a rugby club, a market, and a campus – the neighbourhood aims to implement solutions such as intelligent monitoring and decision systems, retrofittings, and the development of a catalogue of nature-based solutions to drive down carbon emissions through an inclusive and community-driven approach. Initiatives include the co-design of a street art mural with collective painting; promoting the neighborhood experience of involvement, sharing, and social inclusion about the vision and objectives of a carbon neutral neighborhood in Lisbon; site visits in Alvalade; alignment with the CCC Lisbon 2030 (policy/strategy) and ongoing projects/programs; and developing and implementing Guidelines for Pilot Project.

Fair & Inclusive Transition

The aim is to ensure a fair transition in Alvalade by addressing social justice issues and alleviating energy poverty. Initiatives to promote social inclusion such as creating accessible public spaces, enhancing mobility options, and ensuring that all community members, including those from marginalized groups, can have a say and benefit from the improvements in the neighborhood.

Towards Carbon Neutrality

Lisbon aims to achieve an 80% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions through several key initiatives. These include retrofitting of buildings and refrigeration systems, installation of systems to generate renewable energy, and intelligent monitoring systems to inform, evaluate and minimize energy and water consumption and consequently reduce emissions

Climate Resilient & Adaptive

The vision for Alvalade includes several initiatives specifically aimed at enhancing resilience and adaptation. These include increasing the drainage capacity of roofs to manage extreme weather events, implementing additional measures for emergency situations to protect infrastructure, reduce water consumption, integration of nature-based solutions, and fostering a behavioural change in residents towards more sustainable choices.

Figure 42 Vision for Lisbon's Pilot.

5.2.5. Reflections

The engagement process was crucial to map all the different ongoing projects within the Lisbon Municipality, enabling the integration of UP2030 into institutional activities, thus addressing internal needs and generating a real positive impact on the city.

The workshop was enthusiastically accepted by the stakeholders, the participants were highly engaged and encouraged to think beyond their usual work practices indicating that UP2030 activities are seen as an opportunity to concretely improve public administration decision-making processes, streamline decisions across different departments, and provide innovative and concrete solutions to their specific needs.

Key topics discussed included carbon neutrality, just transition, and resilience, with an emphasis on an inclusive process involving and benefiting the inhabitants, to implement solutions such as intelligent monitoring and decision systems, retrofitting, and the development of a catalogue of nature-based solutions to drive down carbon emissions through an inclusive and community-driven approach giving ownership back to the neighbourhoods.

The pathways materialisation is on-going in the four selected project areas mentioned above and will be consolidated in the next workshop on this subject.

5.2.6. Milan

The key challenge for the Milan is how to create districts that are resilient, inclusive, and carbon neutral, to achieve a more effective climate transition able to respond to the various critical urban issues and needs, and to make more efficient use of resources. From this perspective, some urban regeneration projects, pilot areas of UP2030, represent a unique opportunity to try to adopt this new integrated approach in the urban planning and design, especially by focusing on green as a mean to achieve a multiplicity of environmental, social and economic objectives. These projects can increase the availability and quality of urban green spaces and the implementation of “green” interventions (Nature-based solutions, de-paving, forestation, etc.), to improve the city’s adaptive capacity against heat islands and urban flooding, as well as mitigate climate change and offer more affordable and liveable spaces to citizens. So, the Municipality of Milan and its internal stakeholders decided to try to envision a new approach for the planning and design of urban green spaces to maximize their environmental, economic and social benefits, serving as resilient buffers against the impacts of climate change, and to turn challenges into opportunities for a more liveable and fairer city for all. For this purpose, two different tools were selected for testing new approaches on different pilots: the Ecosystem Services Assessment tool by LINKS and the City Resilience Framework (CRF) by Resilient Cities Network.

Figure 43 Milan’s Recommended Co-visionsing Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023).

5.2.6. Proposed Process and its application

To tackle the challenges of identifying how UP2030 can support ongoing efforts regarding the design of green spaces within urban regeneration areas, it was proposed to employ the *Community Maps* tool to identify and spatially map ongoing projects, initiatives and programs. *Integrated Spatial Analysis* was suggested for mapping vulnerabilities and opportunities by relying on stakeholder engagement and insights. The activities could support further ideation of the process and set a clearer direction and intervention fields for the next steps.

A capacity training, to support liaisons in facilitating visioning activities with each city, was held in early December 2023 with Milan’s liaison, LINKS.

Putting it into practice, Milan engaged mainly internal stakeholders (from different departments) in the co-visionsing process to define its specific objectives, vision and scope within the UP2030 project and to identify different pilot locations to work on during the implementation phase. This process was facilitated through different workshops/focus groups designed to achieve several key aims: outlining the benefits provided by the UP2030 project, highlighting the requirements of municipal departments for the planning and maintenance of urban green spaces, clarifying the specific goals of UP2030 for the City of Milan, determining pilot locations for implementing project tools and exploring how UP2030 can support the Municipality’s ongoing initiatives.

For the adaptive pathways, Milan executed other two workshops to co-develop the adaptive pathways engaging the different internal stakeholders. These workshops had the aim of both breaking down the objectives into tangible actions and identifying risks associated with the objectives and actions. Additionally, they aimed to propose alternative mitigation strategies to respond to those risks.

5.2.6. Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

Figure 44 Vision workshop in Milan.

The vision workshops/focus groups, facilitated by the Urban Resilience Department in the role of coordinator of UP2030 for Milan and the liaison and technical partner LINKS brought together various stakeholders interested in green space design: the Green Sector, responsible for the design and management of green areas; the Urban Regeneration Department, which handles urban planning and regeneration processes; the Energy and Climate Area, responsible for the monitoring of the municipal “Air and Climate Plan”; AMAT, the municipality's in-house agency for environmental: PIM, a consultant for the urban masterplan.

Several methods were employed in these engagement activities, including a keynote presentation on the program's scope within UP2030 and an explanation of the Ecosystem Services framework and its possible application within the Municipality. Key questions were posed regarding the scale and location of the selected pilots, along with the category focus of their Ecosystem Services framework. The Thematic Brainstorming method was used to identify pillar visions, detailing Milan's vision for resilience, carbon neutrality and a just transition.

Results and the culmination of the Vision workshop activities and outputs are documented on the Vision Page below in Figures 45 and 46.

Greener Districts for Milan

Enhancing ecosystem services in urban regeneration areas for climate adaptation and mitigation

Districts where urban green spaces are design to maximize their environmental, economic and social benefits, serving as resilient buffers against the impacts of climate change, in order to turn challenge into opportunities for a more liveable and fair city for all.

Affordable, Liveable & Fair

Create affordable and accessible green spaces and truly liveable urban areas, while also equitably compensating for the unavoidable environmental, social and economic losses of ecosystem services resulting from urban (re) generation processes.

Carbon Neutral

Enhance the green areas capacity to mitigate climate change by improving their actual and potential carbon sequestration and storage, as well as leveraging their role in energy saving for building cooling, thereby promoting a more conscious design of urban spaces.

Cooler & Safer

Use green areas as allies in combating urban heat island and flooding and in improving water retention, to make the district safer and more liveable and to contribute to the reduction of the costs due to climate change's impacts.

Figure 45 Vision for Milan's Pilot

Results from the Thematic Brainstorming

Objectives and ongoing process within the Municipality	Ecosystem Services of interest	Pilot Area	Stakeholders to be involved	When	Resources/ Critical Issues
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluating the environmental, social and economic benefits of the climate adaptation measures (e.g. depaving, NBS, forestation, etc...) included in the Air Climate Plan – PAC approved by the Municipality in 2022, in order to assess their effectiveness. Quantifying how many green spaces are needed to keep the increase in urban temperatures below 2°C by 2050 compared to 2017 (PAC challenge). 	Mainly Urban Cooling, Carbon storage, Access to nature. To evaluate: Rainwater retention and mitigation of urban flooding.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Urban scale; Smaller areas involved in adaptation intervention. 	AMAT, MM, Polimi, ARPA, real estate operators	Results by October-November 24.	Available data collected by the Green Sector (e.g. furniture in public green space, accessibility...), useful as input data.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being able to compare different project scenarios of urban projects to find the best one in terms of environmental, social and economic benefits provided to the city. Providing guidance for drafting projects to real estate operators. Improving the actual methodology used to calculate the compensation to be asked to real estate operators responsible for urban transformation, also including related biophysical and economic value of green areas (thus considering the impact of their intervention on ES). 		Urban scale		During 2024.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing the planners with guidance on green areas for urban regeneration projects. Comparing the ES of the masterplan with those of the Final Project and quantify the compensation in terms of ES (to be compensated). 		«Scalo Farini» (and «San Cristoforo» as area for compensations)		From April – May 24	

Figure 46 Results from Thematic Brainstorming method.

The stakeholders engaged during the adaptive pathways phase were the Urban Resilience Department, the Environmental authorisations and territorial management Area, the Energy and Climate Area, AMAT – the Milan Agency for Mobility Environment and Territory and then the Urban Regeneration Department.

During the workshops/focus groups a short presentation was used to introduce the contents, and brainstorming activities were driven by prompts developed by TSPA and UIC and based on Milan's vision and objectives. (prompts can be found in the section 8.3.4) They were designed to guide and stimulate discussion about context-specific actions, risks, and barriers – in terms of policy, urban planning, energy transition, citizen science / stakeholder engagement, and financing. The results from the workshop were combined and shared with TSPA. They were subsequently synthesized, analysed for gaps, and sequenced, before being delivered as databases and adaptive pathways pages which can be found in Annex section 8.4.5.

5.2.6. Reflections

A lot of workshops and focus groups have been held, involving different municipal Departments/Areas (6) and people (45). They were hosted with the aim of building an internal inter-directional working group on the topic of green design and the evaluation of its benefits. Indeed, the main challenge in Milan is the engagement of different Departments on common topics/activities to develop an integrated approach for the urban planning and design.

This engagement process was very useful to map the different ongoing projects within the Municipality to be able to integrate UP2030 as much as possible into institutional activities and thus answer to the internal needs and generate a real positive impact on the city.

Meetings were very well attended by the invited stakeholders, demonstrating that UP2030 activities are perceived as an opportunity to concretely improve public administration decision-making processes, streamline decisions within the different Departments and provide an innovative and concrete answer to their specific needs. Placing the needs of the Departments involved at the forefront of the participatory process and positioning UP2030 project as a supporter (and not at the centre) was the winning strategy.

Then, alternate workshops with smaller focus groups were useful (and necessary) to delve into specific topics, giving to each stakeholder the chance to better explain his/her/their needs and to work together on how to achieve the objectives, in line with UP2030 goals.

Some external strategic stakeholders (e.g. the regional environmental agency for environment - ARPA, the municipal in-house agency for environment – AMAT, universities, etc.) were also engaged in the process, starting to create a functional technical group for the implementation of the ESA and CRF tools.

The next implementation phase of the project will be dedicated to strengthening the internal working group and to the active engagement of some strategic external stakeholders that will be involve in the Learning and Action Alliance and then in the Partnership Commitment sign, a necessary step not only for the implementation of UP2030 but also for the replicability of some of its activities after the end of the project.

5.2.7. Münster

Münster's goal under UP2030 is to develop a Roadmap for neighbourhood-level climate strategies, based on the pilot project in Frauenstraße and linked to other ongoing projects in the Climate Office. This Roadmap will guide Münster in rebuilding neighbourhoods to be climate-neutral and climate-adapted. The specific focus will be on balancing mitigation and adaptation measures in governance, implementing social and spatial justice, and understanding existing policies and resources.

Additionally, Münster plans to align the UP2030 project with the ongoing "KlimaTraining" initiative on Frauenstraße, where volunteer climate trainers assist small groups in implementing everyday climate protection tips.

5.2.7. Proposed process and its application

Figure 47 Münster's Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023).

During the vision phase, the City of Münster decided to conduct two sessions dedicated to co-designing the Vision and Adaptive Pathways. To prepare for these vision workshops, task leaders held several meetings with city officials and liaisons to contextualize the workshop methods. These meetings provided a better understanding of the city's challenges, internal capacities, and goals.

The city expressed concerns that many projects run in parallel, leading to a lack of consistency and connection between them, highlighting the need for better structuring and linking of these projects. It was suggested to use the Community Maps platform, developed specifically for the UP2030 co-visioning process. This platform allows users to mark projects on an interactive map and provide information, facilitating knowledge sharing and identifying ongoing or planned projects that could impact or contribute to project goals. However, due to internal capacity constraints and the fact that there are other similar

tools which are already in use (for example Wechange, buergerbeteiligung.nrw.de), the city team decided not to use the platform.

Co-visioning workshop was shaped as a brainstorming session. To facilitate discussion during the session a set of guiding questions was proposed to support session preparation and ensure all topics were covered. The workshop included a presentation of the "Climate Proofing" method from Buro Happold, the selected tool provider supporting Münster in prototype creation within UP2030 project.

Similarly to the Co-visioning Workshop preparation, several online meetings were held to prepare for Adaptive Pathways Workshop. The city received materials to support the preparation and implementation of the Adaptive Pathways Workshop. These included templates for unpacking objectives into operative actions, templates for noting down risks and alternative actions to mitigate those risks, along with methodological guidelines and questions for the session. Additionally, a set of prompts was developed and shared prior to the session to ensure guided and comprehensive identification of actions. Specifically tailored for Münster, the prompts included questions such as: "Describe a measure to ensure that public participation is inclusive and reflects the diversity of users of public space" and "How should the city deal with the potential conflict between the preservation of historical spaces and materials and ecological goals?" The full list of prompts can be found in the Annex section 8.3.5.

Due to internal constraints, the city decided to alter the session format. The Climate Proofing tool was presented, showcasing progress, followed by a group discussion and brainstorming on co-creation and implementation of guidelines for the framework. The consolidated session results were then analyzed by technical partners and shared for feedback with the Münster team. The outcomes are presented in the following section.

It's important to mention that from the beginning of the process, the city had a close involvement with the selected tool provider. These efforts helped to ensure an integrated process moving from co-visioning towards prototype implementation.

5.2.7. Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

The Vision Workshop took place on March 14th, with seven members of the Climate Unit of the City of Münster participating, along with the team from Buro Happold, who are supporting the city as a tool provider. During the workshop, participants were presented with a selection of images depicting various aspects of neighbourhoods. Each person chose one or more images and used them to answer the key question: "Which image appeals to you most in relation to your work in neighbourhoods and why?".

The main focus of the session was on developing a vision of cooperation for climate-friendly neighborhoods. The discussion was divided into two parts. In step one, the aim was to jointly define the tasks and roles of the climate unit within the administration and identify blind spots in their activities. A visualization of the Climate Proofing method was presented to help participants classify current projects, approaches, and tasks within the process modules named by the method.

The workshop results were consolidated into the Vision Page (Figure 48).

Roadmap for climate friendly Münster

Roadmap for climate friendly neighborhoods that guides through the different step for a climate neutral and adapted neighborhood

The climate-friendly neighborhood roadmap enhances municipal cooperation by providing clear steps for achieving climate-neutral and adapted neighborhoods. It guides municipal staff through planning instruments, measures, databases, funding opportunities, and participation approaches essential for sustainable development. This tool helps integrate climate-friendly methods into neighborhood-level work, supporting the city's climate goals by linking mitigation, adaptation, and participation measures across various stages. Designed to be accessible and adaptable, it ensures practitioners from diverse backgrounds can effectively implement and scale its strategies.

Community Involvement	Carbon Neutrality	Climate Friendly Neighborhood
<p>In order to involve the various stakeholders living in the neighborhood in the process at an early stage, reduce reservations and to actively engage them, the previously citywide Climate Training concept will be adapted to the neighborhood level and become part of the roadmap.</p>	<p>Münster is one of the 100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities with its goal to be climate neutral by 2030. There is a high potential for CO₂ savings in the area of existing residential buildings. A key lever is therefore a significant increase in the refurbishment rate of existing buildings, as these are responsible for a large proportion of climate-relevant emissions. For this reason, the City of Münster would like to extend its previous approach of looking at individual buildings and other main CO₂ emitter to the neighborhood level.</p>	<p>Consideration of climate protection, climate adaptation and participation simultaneously in existing districts. The Roadmap will address the linkage between various planning phases and measures and suggest appropriate content for european-wide calls for tender for city quarter redevelopment and integrated neighbourhood concepts.</p>

Figure 48 Vision for Münster's Pilot.

Figure 49 Brainstorming session during visioning workshop in Münster.

During the session, participants developed a vision for future cooperation, beginning with defining what a "climate-friendly city" means and its significance for their respective departments. This vision emphasized the importance of continuous development and maintaining a dynamic approach to planning and implementing climate-friendly initiatives. They acknowledged that each neighbourhood is unique, requiring different priorities. To streamline planning processes, it was proposed to establish planning teams, similar to those already in place, for climate-friendly neighbourhood planning.

The development of guidelines to serve as a "filter tool" to assist in planning and decision-making steps was also suggested as a component of the Roadmap that is being jointly developed with BH. Additionally, the participants emphasized the importance of creating a centralized catalogue for all urban projects and data records, enhancing accessibility and coordination. This catalogue would allow users to input specific properties of individual projects, enabling them to filter and display related projects and datasets.

Creating synergies between climate protection, climate adaptation, and participation was highlighted as a key objective. The participants stressed the need for regular examination of dependencies between various initiatives and projects. It was also recognized that the framework must not be a static document but should be continuously developed and maintained.

The second session, held on May 3rd, primarily focused on Adaptive Pathways and the necessary actions to realize the vision. The discussion revolved around: which functionalities the proposed filtering tool feature (of the Roadmap) should possess; the content the tool should portray; and the responsible

departments or individuals that are associated with the various catalogued / best practice projects. Participants also explored the next steps, identifying other potential users of the Roadmap and determining the filter tool feature's design to ensure its usability across the administration. It was emphasized that the introduction must clearly state the guide's aim and be understandable to individuals from departments without specialist expertise. Based on input from the city, an initial version of Adaptive Pathways was developed and can be found in the Annex section 8.4.6.

As part of the workshop results, the input provided by the participants was aligned to the input on the ongoing and existing projects within the city of Münster and distributed along the steps from Climate Proofing method. This was done for the three fields of climate mitigation, climate adaptation and the participation and cooperation within the city. The inputs originally sketched on post-its within the workshop were then worked into the graphic (Figure 51) by the Climate Office of Münster.

Generally, the results show that on one hand, many initiatives and work is already going on within the fields of climate mitigation and adaptation on different scales within the city, but that the coordination between the topics is oftentimes lacking (middle part of the graphic). Through the further development of the Roadmap for climate-friendly neighbourhoods, these links are aimed to be established in line with the ongoing progress of the UP2030 urban planning processes.

Figure 50 Digitised results from vision workshop on the co-creation of guidelines for a joint approach to climate friendly and energy efficient neighbourhood development.

5.2.7. Reflections

The workshops held in Münster provided valuable insights into the city's current efforts and future goals regarding climate resilience and carbon neutrality. The involvement of various stakeholders highlighted the importance of a collaborative approach. The Vision and Adaptive Pathways developed during these sessions emphasized the need for continuous development and dynamic planning, acknowledging the uniqueness of each neighbourhood.

Main identified challenges along the process were:

- **Coordination and Integration:** One significant challenge identified was the lack of consistency and connection between parallel projects. The need for better structuring and linking of these projects was emphasized to avoid redundancy and ensure cohesive progress.
- **Internal Constraints:** Limited internal capacity coupled with legal constraints affecting the allowable communication platforms for public engagement, affected the city's ability to utilize tools like the Community Maps platform, which could have facilitated better project management and knowledge sharing.
- **Diverse Needs and Priorities:** Addressing the varying needs and priorities of different neighbourhoods makes it challenging to implement a one-size-fits-all guideline / Roadmap strategy, requiring a more tailored approach that is both time and resource intensive.

Meanwhile, the process also brought the following opportunities:

- **Enhanced Collaboration:** The workshops revealed opportunities for enhanced collaboration between different departments and stakeholders. Establishing planning teams specifically for climate-friendly neighbourhood planning was proposed to streamline efforts.
- **Centralized Data Catalogue:** Creating a centralized catalogue for urban projects and data records could significantly improve accessibility, coordination and access to data and knowledge sharing, allowing for better transparency, goal monitoring and decision-making support.
- **Synergy Creation:** The emphasis on creating synergies between climate protection, climate adaptation, and participation presents an opportunity to develop integrated solutions that address multiple goals simultaneously.

The roadmap for Münster is designed to enhance the city's resilience by rebuilding neighbourhoods to be climate-adapted, incorporating both mitigation and adaptation measures. The use of methodologies like the Climate Proofing method assisted to identify and address vulnerabilities, ensuring neighbourhoods are better prepared to withstand climate impacts.

By developing a clear vision and adaptive pathways, Münster can implement targeted actions to reduce carbon emissions at the neighbourhood level. The city's alignment with initiatives such as "KlimaTraining" promotes everyday climate protection practices, contributing the city's overall carbon neutrality goals.

The roadmap also emphasizes a just transition by prioritizing social and spatial justice in governance. This involves refining participation methods to ensure that climate actions benefit all residents, especially the most vulnerable. The integration of inclusive public participation processes into the Roadmap is crucial. It aims to reflect the diversity of users of public spaces, ensuring that the benefits of climate action are equitably distributed among all community members.

In terms of process replicability, it is essential to develop a transparent framework that can accommodate local contexts while maintaining core principles of inclusivity, collaboration, and dynamic planning. The use of adaptable tools and methodologies, like the Climate Proofing method, can be scaled and customized for different urban settings.

In terms of upscaling the process the city has identified the following needs:

- **Enhanced Capacity Building:** Strengthening internal capacities to manage and utilize existing tools and platforms is crucial for scaling the vision, including the adequate introduction, onboarding and buy-in for the resultant Roadmap & associated filtering tool.
- **Improved Coordination Mechanisms:** Establishing robust coordination mechanisms to link parallel projects can help in maintaining consistency and maximizing impact.
- **Tailored Support and Resources:** Providing tailored support and resources, including templates and methodological guidelines, can aid other cities in effectively implementing similar strategies.
- **Continuous Feedback and Adaptation:** Creating mechanisms for continuous feedback and adaptation that ensures that the Roadmap remains relevant and effective in the face of evolving challenges, opportunities, changing urban climate conditions.

By addressing these areas, other cities can successfully adopt and scale Münster's approach, contributing to broader goals of urban resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition.

5.2.8. [Rotterdam](#)

Under UP2030, Rotterdam aims to create a Resilient District Learning Toolbox that integrates lessons from the Resilient BoTu 2028 programs, applied in the Bospolder-Tussendijken districts ("BoTu") districts. This toolbox will provide guidance on applying these findings using UP2030 thematic areas of carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition as implementation trajectories.

5.2.8. [Process and its application](#)

Over the first year of the project, the city's focus shifted from an ambition to build a framework to upscale interventions aimed at raising social resilience, energy efficiency, and housing stock renovations, to the goal of distilling these learnings and consolidating them into the learning toolbox to participate in the embedding of the lessons and practices within the organisation.

Due to these refinements, the proposed approach at the beginning of the vision phase had to be updated and modified. Several meetings were held to discuss the best approaches and desired outcomes while planning the workshop. During this period, multiple options were drafted, consulting BoTu leadership and The Field Academy, a local knowledge centre in the community. Each session was carefully assessed in terms of its deliverables and contribution to the UP2030 process.

After validating objectives in November, it was decided to organize a combined session to co-design visions and adaptive pathways. Given the focus on distilling learnings from the process, it was determined that

the spatial component was not particularly relevant, and the focus was concentrated on identifying what the toolbox should consist of, and who are the key stakeholders to be included in its development.

Figure 51 Rotterdam’s Recommended Co-visioning Engagement Methods (Source: TSPA, 2023)

To define the vision and contextualise thematic areas (resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition) proposed methods such as Thematic Brainstorming and the Future Newspaper method were employed. Meanwhile, to determine the actions needed to achieve the objectives and answer the question of 'how to achieve the designed goal,' the *Minimum-Maximum* exercise was chosen. Instead of the proposed “unpacking objectives” session typically conducted in a group setting, it was decided to capitalize on the opportunity of having a diverse set of stakeholders present. They contributed by noting down minimum and maximum actions to be undertaken. Collecting the minimum and maximum actions for a diverse set of actors allowed to further identify the needs of the future users of the toolbox and gather best practices.

5.2.8. Visioning & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

The vision workshop in Rotterdam was held on April 18th, aiming to define a vision for a learning framework based on BoTu’s pilot learnings, and by integrating UP2030 thematic pillars - resilience, carbon neutrality, and inclusivity and justice. Consequently, the session primarily included internal municipal staff and representatives from selected districts chosen for testing the framework and replicating BoTu’s results.

The session commenced with a brief recap of the previous steps taken in UP2030, including needs and barriers identification, as well as the purpose and goals of the visioning phase.

Following the introduction, participants engaged in a card clustering exercise prepared by The Field Academy, which has extensively monitored the *Resilient BoTu* programme over the past five years. The inspirational cards highlighted key learnings from BoTu, facilitating a critical examination of UP2030's pillars. A thematic brainstorming exercise helped deepen the understanding of each topic and brainstorm how each pillar is contextualized.

Upscaling Learnings from BoTu

A Resilient District Learning Framework that is robust and replicable

The learning framework is a tool that the municipality can integrate in its way of working and leverage the lessons learnt from the Resilient BoTu 2028 program to achieve broader city goals on climate neutrality, energy transition, resilience and just transition. To ensure that the lessons are taken up and upscaled, it is crucial that the framework is robust, accessible and allows for practitioners from diverse backgrounds to contextualize and replicate it in their own work.

Just Transition

The learnings from the framework advocate for leveraging existing assets, talents and resources in the local context (applying the Asset Based Community Development method). A key aspect is to co-create and engage residents, ensuring the knowledge and investment stay in the neighbourhood. Building up awareness about the current inequalities.

Carbon Neutral

The aim is to apply the framework to advancing energy transition at the neighbourhood level by contextualising the learnings from the natural gas free districts programme for which BoTu was one of the pilot neighbourhoods. In BoTu, the energy transition was leveraged to address broader societal development.

Resilience

Social resilience and inclusion is at the heart of the BoTu learnings. Harnessing the power of community to address challenges and build adaptive capacity for responding better to shocks and stresses. These principles are embedded in the framework.

Figure 52 Vision for Rotterdam's Pilot.

After a short break, the group conducted the Future Newspaper method. Building on the previous exercises (Pillar Brainstorming and BoTu Lessons), participants created newspaper headlines to identify desirable future scenarios, including the short-term and long-term changes and actions required to

achieve the envisioned outcomes. Three different stories were developed in total. The vision statements were later consolidated by the city and liaison teams into a unified vision statement, representing a shared goal. The first part of the workshop results was compiled into the vision page (Figure 52).

The second part of the workshop focused on identifying next steps, known as adaptive pathways. During the minimum-maximum exercise, each participant considered actions within their own work, using maximum versus minimum scenarios, and noted them down on prepared templates. This approach helped participants think strategically about implementing the vision and identifying practical steps towards achieving the defined goals.

The results of the first exercise were then analysed by the task leader and consolidated into the first vision page draft. This was ultimately revised and integrated upon by the city as the scope of their vision changed from a framework for upscaling across the city, towards a toolbox for updating internal processes.

Due to the internal changes in the city administration and restricted capacity, Rotterdam have not yet advanced with the development of the adaptive pathways. However, the efforts for revising the information and starting to consolidate it into the initial version of the pathways, helped to clarify the vision statement and desired prototype development even further.

5.2.8. Reflections

The city stated that the guide which was created by TSPA for the visioning phase was in-depth, well-established and detailed. However, it was felt as a long process to go through all the information. Rotterdam first had to understand the goals of the process, establish which of the proposed methods allowed them to achieve their own goals within the process, and then to further translate this to their pilot reality. The city felt that collaboration with TSPA and the support it provided was good throughout the process.

When designing the workshop, the city noticed difficulties with the translation to the local reality and with the cooperation with other stakeholders (The Field Academy) who co-designed the workshop. The difficulties mainly resided in receiving the necessary information timely.

Rotterdam designed the visioning and adaptive pathways exercises in a way that it would directly contribute to 1) a co-creation process; 2) translation of BoTu approach to other districts/structures; 3) result in tangible outputs that could be reproduced (e.g., workshop exercises and descriptions); 4) experiment with a potentially replicable workshop/module based on the BoTu lessons.

During the visioning workshop, the participants were highly engaged and encouraged to think beyond their usual work practices. Many found connections and relevance to their work, with multiple participants mentioning that they were inspired by what they heard and learned during the workshop. However, due to the strong engagement and numerous exercises, not all activities could be fully executed, and some templates were not completed according to the exercises. To enhance future workshops, the city recommends either extending the duration of the day or removing an exercise to ensure all activities can be thoroughly completed.

Key topics discussed included carbon neutrality, just transition, and resilience, with an emphasis on an inclusive process involving and benefiting the inhabitants, giving ownership back to the neighbourhoods. The need for a flexible learning organization was highlighted, along with establishing a strong network

within the municipality to support this new way of working and to participate in implementing it in city projects.

Some invited participants were unable to attend due to various reasons but remain engaged in the process. For future steps, we will diversify the types of stakeholders and expand engagement, using insights from the minimum-maximum exercise to identify key stakeholders. The workshop demonstrated the importance of a collaborative and inclusive approach, highlighting the necessity of continued engagement and adaptation to improve future sessions.

5.2.9. Thessaloniki

Within UP2030, Thessaloniki’s goal is to establish the Diokitirion district as a sustainable, thriving, and climate-resilient neighborhood encompassing a diverse mix of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces. The citizens and the local UP2030 team – the municipality of Thessaloniki and MDAT – have expressed their need to focus on a district climate action plan. The district climate action plan will include small-scale applicable actions that will serve as a complimentary plan to the CCC of Thessaloniki. Additionally, the action plan and the UP2030 methodology will be shared with other city districts encouraging and urging them to design similar local climate, resilient, and just actions.

5.2.9. Proposed process and its application

Given this context, Thessaloniki’s co-visioning process can benefit a lot for the strong spatial assessment to identify possible areas of interventions, but also to identify ongoing projects and initiatives within the Diokitirion district. The purpose of this step is to capitalise on synergies with other ongoing projects in the pilot area and to see how UP2030 can fit in. Moreover, mapping climate adaptation/mitigation issues and opportunities, vulnerable communities within pilot area.

Figure 53 Co-visioning Roadmap with Suggested Engagement Methods for Thessaloniki (Source: TSPA, 2023)

During the vision phase, several online meetings were held to discuss the contextualization of the methodology and to prepare for the workshop. It was decided to organize a series of smaller engagement sessions, all leading towards the final workshop to co-design the vision for the pilot.

Vacant spaces in the street level of Kassandrou Street

Figure 54 Results from the spatial analysis milestone.

Early in the project, a spatial assessment was conducted, creating a solid foundation for future co-visioning steps. The spatial analysis included on-site visits by the liaison office using a camera and a map. More than 250 photos were collected reflecting the current state of the buildings, both occupied and empty, the status of the public and green spaces, the occupation of pedestrian zones by table seats and cars, the evolution of tourist accommodation services, the rise of Airbnb services, as well as the decline of the economic activity and vacant spaces (former shops or small crafts).

The city also performed an Integrated Spatial Analysis method, organizing several workshops with city employees, NGOs, citizens and users of the area as well as elderly residents who have lived in the area for many years and are aware of the current situation. Participants visualized the needs, barriers, challenges and opportunities of the area on a map.

Figure 55 Highlights from the Spatial Assessment Workshops & Interviews.

This participatory mapping was followed by a series of interviews with residents selected from the local stakeholders list. These individuals were considered to have a solid knowledge and high degree of experience in sustainable development, carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition topics. During the one-on-one interviews participants were also asked to highlight on the map the neighborhood characteristics: the human geography of the area, the economic characteristics, the needs for a just transition as well as specific actions to achieve carbon neutrality.

As a next step, the city worked from the current local status quo towards objectives aligning them with the UP2030 pillars, thus creating a base for identifying pillar visions, connecting to needs, barriers, opportunities, and setting KPIs. The objectives were categorized into the following groups.

- Energy Efficient Buildings
- Renewable Energy
- Sustainable Transportation
- Urban Green Spaces
- Waste Management
- Preparedness & Response
- Balanced Economy
- Housing
- Social Inclusiveness

The vision pillars were developed with the help of thematic brainstorming tool, in December 2023, during the internal session between the city and liaison teams. The purpose of the session was a) to match the objectives of the pilot with the three pillars of the UP2030 project and get a better understanding of the connections and b) to categorize the needs, barriers, and opportunities based on the pillars and key objectives. Following the vision workshop, preparations for the adaptive pathways workshop began. Like the visioning preparation, online meetings were held to discuss the steps and desired outcomes. It was decided to focus on three main objectives: promoting sustainable mobility, improving recycling efficiency and introducing a circular economy model, and providing more green and open spaces with natural elements. A set of prompts was created for each objective to guide the discussions and unpacking of actions. (Prompts can be found in the section 8.3.7)

5.2.9. Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

The vision workshop was held in March 2024. Its purpose was to discuss the vision for the pilot area of Dioikitirio with participants and to explore the changes they wanted to see in the area, including the transition to carbon neutrality, resilience, and just transition. The *Future Newspaper* method was used to identify statements during the group exercise. Participants were asked to imagine waking up in 2030, describe their daily routine, and write down the news they would read in the newspaper on provided templates.

Vision for Dioikitirio Neighbourhood

Creating a sustainable, thriving & climate-resilient neighbourhood

that encompasses a diverse mix of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces. A healthy, green, friendly, safe, affordable & accessible neighborhood that breaths, walks, plays, works, and offers to its residents and visitors.

- Boundary of the Area
- Neighborhoods with Special Characteristics
- Green Space
- Open Spaces
- Buildings with Potential for Development
- School Complexes
- High Property Prices
- Irregular Parking
- Lack of Transportation
- Short-term Rentals in Progress
- Transition Area
- Citizens' Society Organizations
- Metro Stations

Friendly & Safe

Create a safer & more resilient neighborhood by eliminating the risks of natural hazards. Organise proper community response to warnings. Increase green spaces that offer relief during heat waves, counter the urban heat island effect and absorb rainwater - essential aspects of a resilient area.

Affordable & Accessible

We imagine a neighborhood for living, working, and leisure. Providing decent, affordable housing for all, enabling real progress towards creating an inclusive urban space for all citizens.

Healthy & Green

Reduce greenhouse gases and air pollution and become a carbon neutral neighborhood, caring for the health and well-being of the people. Increase the amount of green space on roofs, balconies and facades, along streets and on squares and parks.

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

Figure 56 Vision for Thessaloniki's Pilot.

This session included elected officials, vice-mayors, municipal employees, and heads of planning offices. The results of the vision workshop, along with the vision pillars, objectives, and map, are presented on the vision page (Figure 56).

“Creating a sustainable, thriving & climate-resilient neighbourhood that encompasses a diverse mix of residential, commercial, and recreational spaces. A healthy, green, friendly, safe, affordable & accessible neighbourhood that breaths, walks, plays, works, and offers to its residents and visitors.”

The adaptive pathways workshop took place in April 2024. This workshop's aim was to identify the actions and risks associated with the pilot area's vision. Specifically, the scope was to pave the way for practical, adaptive strategies aligned with the local pilot objectives and vision. The session involved residents, civil society organizations, academics, municipality employees, and shop owners.

The consolidated results were analysed with the involvement of other technical partners within the project. This process culminated in the initial version of the adaptive pathways, which is presented both in a short form below and in a more comprehensive and dynamic version as a database. Initial version of Adaptive Pathways can be found in Annex section 8.4.7.

Figure 57 Highlights from the Adaptive Pathways workshop in Thessaloniki.

UP2030
STRATEGIC ADAPTIVE PATHWAY
 CITY NAME: THESSALONIKI
 PLOT TITLE: Creating a sustainable, thriving & climate-resilient neighborhood in Dioxidorion area

ΔΕΜΑΡΧΙΟ ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΗΣ: Δ.Ι.Β.Χ.Ε.Τ.Π.Σ.Π. Β. Π.Α.Ρ.Α.Π.Η.Λ.Α.Σ.Π.Ν.

ΤΙΤΛΟΣ ΑΡΧΗΣ: ΑΝΑΚΥΚΛΩΣΗ ΚΑΙ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΑΠΟΡΡΙΜΜΑΤΩΝ ΣΤΟ ΚΑΤΑΣΤΗΜΑΤΑ / ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΙΑ

ΤΙΤΛΟΣ ΥΠΟ-ΑΡΧΗΣ	ΠΕΡΙΓΡΑΦΗ ΥΠΟ-ΑΡΧΗΣ	ΕΜΠΛΕΚΟΜΕΝΟ	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΗ	ΠΡΑΚΤΙΚΟ ΚΙΝΗΜΑΤΩΝ Η ΕΥΡΕΣΕΙΣ	ΣΤΡΑΤΗΓΙΚΕΣ ΥΠΕΡΑΡΧΗΣ
2	ΧΑΡΤΑΙ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΑΝΑΡΤΗΣΗ	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΚΑΙ ΑΝΑΡΤΗΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΑΝΑΡΤΗΣΗ	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)
3	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)
4	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)
5	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)
6	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)
7	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)	ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ) ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ (ΕΠΙΧΕΙΡΗΣΕΙΣ)

Co-funded by the European Union
 Funded by the European Union. This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement n° 101096405

Figure 58 Template filled during the Adaptive Pathway Workshop: Waste Management / Recycling and waste management actions by local shops/restaurants/hotels.

5.2.9. Reflections

The city found that all participatory processes carried out within the framework of UP2030 were very interesting, both in terms of the results and the strong desire of the residents and other type of stakeholders to actively participate.

The residents expressed a need to connect with each other and collaborate within more organised efforts and under the coordination of a team. During the adaptive pathways workshop, the idea of forming a neighbourhood group was initiated that would undertake the next steps of co-designing and co-implementing with the neighbourhoods through the next years.

Most of the proposed actions are to be implemented by the community with the support of the municipality. The local UP2030 team will continue to coordinate the implementation of these actions and will support the official launch of the neighbourhoods’ teams.

It was felt that this will be a great opportunity to ensure the sustainability of the UP2030 local actions even when the project comes to its end. The neighbourhoods’ teams will continue to take responsibility for the local action plan and the collaboration with the local community.

The meaning of carbon neutrality, resilience and just transition were not always clear to stakeholders, that’s why the city didn’t focus the discussions on explaining the terms. The discussions were centred on how they can improve the health of the citizens and of the environment taking care on the same time the most vulnerable groups living in the area. In the end the results collected from the workshops were linked with the three pillars of the project.

The primary goal, which was the promotion of social housing, proved to be beyond the project's capabilities and its place took the key topics of waste management, green and open spaces, and sustainable mobility. In relation to these three key topics, the need for a series of trainings has emerged. Capacity building and raising awareness is among the next steps to be organized supporting further the community to implement the adaptive pathways.

5.2.10. Zagreb

Zagreb’s overarching aim under UP2030 project is to develop a circular system of modular urban farms that capitalizes on a strong local agricultural history and community involvement. In connection to the main goal, some of the key objectives include raising public awareness about local climate issues and development of educational programs. This project not only seeks to reduce the carbon footprint but also aims to create a fairer distribution of food by increasing food resilience and introducing modular urban farms. For its pilot area within UP2030 project, Zagreb has chosen two areas: the elementary school in the district of Sesevete and a zoo in the city district of Maksimir.

5.2.10. Proposed process and it's applications

Co-visioning process in Zagreb focuses on ideating the process for development of circular food system, including the strategies for dissemination and awareness raising among citizens on food circularity and carbon neutrality topics. The emphasis of the project is largely on the community involvement into the co-creation process as well as ideation on how UP2030 can support ongoing efforts. Therefore, suggested co-visioning process also included engagement methods with youth. Due to the scale of the pilot area (school and zoo) spatial analysis was only an optional method, and instead it was suggested to dedicate more time for co-developing pilot vision in a participatory approach. Moreover, defining pillar visions that reflect contextualized goals for a carbon-neutral, resilient, and just transition is crucial to supporting further steps and framing adaptive pathways.

To align the co-visioning methodology with Zagreb's goals and in consultation with the UP2030 team, the vision scope was defined into two primary goals:

- Ensuring the replicability of the modular solution
- Raising awareness and spreading knowledge

Figure 59 Co-visioning Roadmap with Suggested Engagement Methods for Zagreb (Source: TSPA, 2023).

5.2.10. Vision & Adaptive Pathways Outcomes

A vision workshop was held on April 4, 2024, followed by a public event held on May 23. during the initial session, key stakeholders from the private and public sectors, along with NGOs, collaborated to identify strategic ambitions related to resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition topics. This was achieved through structured discussions and brainstorming. The session involved defining common terminology, outlining desirable outcomes, and connecting needs with potential solutions.

Urban farms for better climate resilience

Moving towards reducing the carbon footprint and fairer distribution of food by introducing modular urban farms

Focusing on pilot interventions at two locations – Elementary School Luka Sesvete and Zoo Zagreb, aim is to demonstrate a concept of indoor vertical growing of edible plants, with all its benefits towards carbon neutrality, resilience and just transition. At the school, various green farming technologies will be implemented for indoor growing, while the zoo will feature a modular pavilion farm. These implementations will illustrate the possibility of growing 1,000 plants per square meter in indoor space, and growing 3,000 plants in less than 30 days. Additionally, these projects will highlight the added benefits of creating a greener ambiance, cleaner air, healthier food choices, and an improved thermal image of the site.

Just Transition in Healthy Choices

The aim is to avoid conflicts where any fast transition – no matter how widely positive it may be – is not always “user friendly” either is socially sensitive. Food – as one of the essential needs, and not only to human kind – should be more available to everyone, especially in context of climate changes. This process would like to make “green transition” more available to everyone by raising awareness of respecting the value of nature as well as decreasing need to commercially penalize CO2 credits.

Towards Carbon Neutrality

The goal is to try to reduce food production processes and food chain systems that are not always friendly towards carbon neutrality. Presuming that the restriction approach is not here mostly preferred, we will be rather demonstrating positive and liveable examples instead. The activities that will be carried out will try to show in a very vivid way that process of “self-growing” plants – especially edible ones- at the exact location of consumption can shorten the “delivery route”, reduce the pollution that occurs in the transfer, make the living space healthier and, not least - significantly affect the temperature reduction on micro location environment!

Food Resilience

Facing the era of climate changes and significant global changes in area of political, social and economic transition – the aim is to demonstrate that by changing food choices and expectations towards processed food, we can grow some of the food by ourselves, particularly in “in-door” conditions away from weather challenges, and within this process to decrease bad influence of climate change as well as increase personal independence from commercial food chains. This small step can be a significant showcase of a bigger picture: increment of food resilience!

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101095405

Figure 60 Vision for Zagreb’s pilot.

During the discussion, definitions of each thematic pillar was clarified to align all engaged participants. Carbon neutrality was identified as efforts for establishing a balance between CO₂ emissions caused by human activity and the amount of carbon dioxide removed by human activity. It was further clarified that green city infrastructure, cycling and walking, urban greening, local vegetable growing, personal food cultivation, and reducing meat consumption are the key strategies and needed urban planning interventions for aligning with carbon neutrality pillar. Resilience pillar was understood as the institutional and individual ability to function during crises, emphasizing social solidarity and promoting greening in all forms. It also means being prepared for situations and external influences that, while unavoidable, can be anticipated. Meanwhile Just Transition pillar was defined as a systematic change towards behaviour that mitigates negative impacts, ensuring that the same rules apply to everyone in the requested behaviour change. Just transition also means equal access to information and green education, equal opportunities to use carbon credits, a fair reward system for green actions, and shared responsibility towards nature protection.

The discussion then was followed by a survey which helped to gather participants' opinions on the relevance and understanding of the three project pillars, informing the vision and highlighting knowledge gaps to address in future sessions.

The vision statement for Zagreb's pilot was crafted by noting down participants' opinions on sticky notes and consolidating them into one shared goal, reflecting a holistic vision for the project. Finalised Zagreb's vision can be found in Figure 60.

Second session that took place on 23rd of May focused on identifying *how* can the identified vision be achieved. Workshop was shaped as social event and took place at the school where the first prototype is being implemented. Each participant received a printed educational brochure on the interdependence of food and climate change. The first step to identifying the actions were discussions with LAA. The main pillar for the identification of the actions were workshops held previously under the UP2030 scope. During the event participants identified actions for achieving the vision, by following the inputs and guidelines provided by Zagreb city team. Additionally, a survey was conducted to further identify and clarify action. Most of the participants stated that education, replicability, good communication practices and better management of food surplus were the main topics regarding raising awareness and spreading knowledge. During the co-visioning process, Zagreb's pilot team (involved city administration supported by liaisons) had several iterations with the primary school administration. These workshops took place

21st of December and 23rd of May along several other more informal exchanges. These meetings helped to validate and conclude unpacking objectives into actions to achieve the vision. Initial version of adaptive pathways can be found in Annex section 8.4.8.

5.2.10. Reflections

As one of the reflections of the process, it was noted that working with a dedicated and diverse team in the city and UP2030 project has been a remarkable experience. The pilot project has benefitted immensely from the varied knowledge and expertise of partners who, despite having different specific objectives, share overarching goals focused on creating a sustainable, resilient, and equitable urban environment. Despite some difficulties in the beginning of the project to involve the external stakeholders, the city has seen an increasing interest among diverse groups of stakeholders to contribute to co-designing pilot vision and its successful implementation.

As one of the key challenges the city has faced during the project has been implementing solutions across Zagreb's diverse neighbourhoods. Each community has unique demographic profiles, necessitating tailored approaches to effectively meet specific local needs. This customization was and is essential for the success of the project and ensures that all community members can benefit from and support the implemented solutions.

Figure 61 Vision workshop in Zagreb.

In conclusion, the city is convinced that its Zagreb's efforts reflect strong commitment to the goals of the UP2030 project and alignment with the EU Green Deal initiatives. By addressing the geopolitical challenges, adapting to shifting community sentiments, and emphasizing the need for customized educational initiatives, Zagreb is well positioned to achieve its ambitious sustainability goals. The collaboration with diverse stakeholders and alignment with EU Green Deal initiatives further strengthens the city's capacity to implement innovative solutions for the benefit of future generations.

Further, there is a recognized need for comprehensive educational programs that cater to all levels of the population. These programs are crucial in fostering an informed and engaged community that understands and supports sustainable practices. Education must be inclusive, reaching various age groups, educational backgrounds, and demographics to ensure wide-reaching impact.

6. Conclusions and Next Steps

This section includes observations and learnings to support the future application of methodology. In addition, the overview of the next steps will be presented here as well, showing the links to the work done within Implementation Task Force and further Engagement activities.

6.1. Key observations

This section reflects the key observations and takeaways from the application process of the developed methodology for co-designing visions.

- **Establishing common understanding of core concepts:** One of the key observations was that due to the complex topics this project addresses, there was often a need for additional iteration for building a common understanding for topics such as carbon neutrality, resilience or just transition. This need was addressed internally in the project through organization of masterclasses. However, several pilot cities have mentioned that more time was needed to discuss, present, and educate participants on the differences between concepts such as carbon neutrality and net zero prior to the workshop sessions. While this was often the case with diverse stakeholder groups that included citizens, it was also the case in certain contexts within internal stakeholder groups.
- **Liaisons' role:** Throughout this process, the role of liaisons, with their understanding of the overarching project goals, was crucial to the success of the methodology implementation. More successful results stemmed from cases where the dedication of the liaisons and city teams was higher, resulting in several online sessions with the methodology authors (TSPA) to discuss opportunities and fully contextualize the proposed methodology.
- **Ownership and responsibility:** Some cases faced challenges due to a lack of ownership in the process, making it difficult to reach and support cities in implementation. Yet this highlighted the importance of defining responsibilities among technical partners, liaisons and cities more clearly. When ownership was well-established, it greatly supported the cities in implementing their visions and adaptive pathways effectively. However, in other cases, the onus fell on the task leader, who ultimately did not have the position to enforce the completion of these processes.
- **Communicating the value of adaptive pathways:** While some cities initially viewed adaptive pathways as challenging, many recognized their value and chose to integrate them into their processes, whether through internal meetings or workshops. This adaptation led to a more dynamic and engaging approach to developing visions and goals. Eventually, some pilot cities chose not to organize workshop sessions explicitly for adaptive pathways due to the stage of their projects.
- **Process contributions towards prototypes:** The iterative nature of developing visions and adaptive pathways significantly contributed to refining goals for prototypes. This process fostered a flexible, creative, and comprehensive approach, enhancing the potential for impactful outcomes.
- **Translation and language barriers:** The international scope of the project introduced language challenges, particularly in translating technical jargon. The crucial role of liaisons in ensuring accurate translations emphasized the importance of clear communication in a co-creative process, preventing misunderstandings and ensuring all participants' ideas were faithfully represented.

- **Engagement of residents:** Engagement strategies varied across pilots, with some cities being more open to engage external stakeholders, while others face greater challenges due to cultural or thematic reasons. Meanwhile, the positive feedback was received regarding the increasing stakeholder interest during this process.
- **Involvement of vulnerable or typically excluded groups:** Incorporating vulnerable or less-engaged groups from the beginning was key to a fair and just transition, one of UP2030's fundamental goals. Several pilot cities involved elderly and youth into the co-design process. This broadened participation enriched the process and opened up new perspectives. This inclusivity enhanced the quality and depth of discussions, leading to more innovative ideas.
- **Engagement Fatigue:** While some cities expressed concerns about potential engagement fatigue, the emphasis was on aligning engagement activities with actionable steps, ensuring the alignment with the ongoing processes. This point further connects to the customisation aspect of the proposed methodology, pointing out a need to customise to select methods that foster internal and external buy-in.
- **Time commitment to capacity training:** The co-visioning methodology was developed and delivered to the pilots by this task leader. However, a challenge for the application of this methodology lies in the fact, that the authors were not facilitating the workshops or engagement activities. During the first months of the project, the discussion whether or not the delivery of methodology and support of cities should happen in person took place. Due to the language barrier as well as extent of the project, it was decided to optimise the process and leverage the role of liaisons, who become a pivotal part in supporting cities with implementation. Therefore, to introduce the methodology and further support pilot cities in the preparation of co-design workshops, periodic online sessions were held (for more details, refer to the section 3.3 and 3.4). In general, these sessions proved to be effective.

6.2. [Next Steps](#)

As project cities transition from the design phase to action, their focus shifts towards implementing prototypes based on the co-designed visions and adaptive pathways established in earlier stages. It's important to note that the adaptive pathways developed thus far should be considered as initial versions. These will serve as dynamic planning tools that are continually refined and updated throughout the process to stay aligned with evolving needs and insights.

Similar to earlier project phases, the action phase incorporates engagement process. This ongoing engagement is crucial for maintaining momentum and ensuring that the adaptive pathways remain relevant and effective in addressing the challenges and opportunities identified during the visioning process.

In parallel, cities are each currently developing a partnership commitment document that will encapsulates the co-designed visions. Initially created as a template by technical partners, this document is now being contextualized by each pilot city. This customization process considers the unique approaches and stakeholder dynamics of each city, ensuring that the document reflects the specific needs and aspirations of the local context. The document allows to solidify the commitment of all partners involved, setting a firm foundation for the successful implementation of the pilot vision and prototypes.

7. References

- Ammouriova, M., Tsertsvadze, V. (2023). D4.4 – Report on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots.
- Barnett, J., & O'Neill, S. (2010). Maladaptation. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(2), 211-213.
- Barnett, J., Evans, L. S., Gross, C., Kiem, A. S., Kingsford, R. T., Palutikof, J. P., Pickering, C. M., & Smithers, S. G. (2015). From barriers to limits to climate change adaptation: path dependency and the speed of change. *Ecology and Society*, 20(3). <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26270227>
- Basnou, C., Pino, J., Davies, C., Winkel, G., & De Vreese, R. (2020). Co-design Processes to Address Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem Services Demands: The Long and Winding Road Towards Inclusive Urban Planning. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 2, 572556.
- Billger, M., Kain, J., Niwagaba, C.B., & McConville, J.R. (2020). Lessons from co-designing a resource-recovery game for collaborative urban sanitation planning. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 588.
- Covernton, E., Francis, L., Stockwell H., Johnson, K. (2023). Interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality. Available at: https://up2030-he.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/UP2030_WP2_D2.4_2023-08-31.pdf [Accessed on 07.12.2023]
- Fernandez, T., Diaz, C., Vera C. (2023). 5UP Approach and its contextualisation in the project cities. Available at https://up2030-he.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/UP2030_WP2_D2.1_2023-06-30.pdf [Accessed on 07.12.2023]
- Glover, J., Elliott, J., McIntyre Muddle, K., & South West Frail Senior Strategy Regional Patient and Family Caregiver Advisory Group (2023). Co-Designing Together through Crisis: Development of a Virtual Care Guidance Document to Support Providers, Older Adults, and Caregivers. *Canadian journal on aging = La revue canadienne du vieillissement*, 42(2), 359–369. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0714980822000307>
- Haasnoot, M., Kwakkel, J. H., Walker, W. E., & ter Maat, J. (2013). Dynamic adaptive policy pathways: A method for crafting robust decisions for a deeply uncertain world. *Global Environmental Change*, 23 (2), 485-498.
- Jittrapirom, P., Bekius, F., & Führer, K. (2023). Visioning future transport systems with an integrated robust and generative framework. *Scientific reports*, 13(1), 4316. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-30818-2>
- Lawrence, J., & Haasnoot, M. (2017). What it took to catalyse uptake of dynamic adaptive pathways planning to address climate change uncertainty. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 68, 47-57.
- Lawrence, J., Bell, R.G., & Stroombergen, A.S. (2019). A hybrid process to address uncertainty and changing climate risk in coastal areas using Dynamic adaptive pathways planning, multi-criteria decision analysis & Real options analysis: A New Zealand application. *Sustainability*.
- Manzini, E. (2015). *Design, When Everybody Designs: An Introduction to Design for Social Innovation*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Mark Pelling, Thaisa Comelli, Marco Cordova, Sibel Kalaycioğlu, Jonathan Menoscal, Rachana Upadhyaya & Matthias Garschagen (2023) Normative future visioning for city resilience and development, *Climate and Development*, DOI: 10.1080/17565529.2023.2223564

- Minowitz, P. (2012). Vision and visioning in planning: What do these terms really mean?. Arizona State University
- RCities (2023). Belfast City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Budapest City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Granollers City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Istanbul City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Lisbon City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Milan City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Münster City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Rotterdam City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Thessaloniki City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- RCities (2023). Zagreb City Storyline [Living document]. Confidential. Note: Document created and updated by multiple collaborators.
- Robertson, T., & Simonsen, J. (2013). Participatory design: an introduction. In J. Simonsen & T. Robertson (Eds.), *Routledge International Handbook of Participatory Design* (pp. 1-17). New York: Routledge.
- Sanders, E. B.-N., & Stappers, P. J. (2008). Co-creation and the new landscapes of design. *CoDesign*, 4(1), 5-18.
- Shiple, R. (2000). The Origin and Development of Vision and Visioning in Planning. *International Planning Studies*, 5(2)
- Steen, M., Manschot, M., & De Koning, N. (2011). Benefits of co-design in service design projects. *International Journal of Design*, 5(2), 53-60.
- Sundblad, Y. (2011). UTOPIA: Participatory Design from Scandinavia to the World. In: Impagliazzo, J., Lundin, P., Wangler, B. (eds) *History of Nordic Computing 3*. HiNC 2010. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, vol 350. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Tewdwr-Jones, M., & Wilson, A. (2022). Co-Designing Urban Planning Engagement and Innovation: Using LEGO® to Facilitate Collaboration, Participation and Ideas. *Urban Planning*.
- The Rockefeller Foundation and ARUP. (2014). *City resilience framework.*, 928.

Turner, J. F. C. (1976). *Housing by people: Towards autonomy in building environments*. Marion Boyars.

United Nations Environment Programme (2022). *2022 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction: Towards a Zero emission, Efficient and Resilient Buildings and Construction Sector*. Nairobi.

UP2030. (2022). Grant Agreement Project: 101096405 — UP2030 — HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-02. Confidential

Walker, W., Haasnoot, M., & Kwakkel, J. (2013). Adapt or Perish: A Review of Planning Approaches for Adaptation under Deep Uncertainty. *Sustainability*, 5(3), 955–979. MDPI AG. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su5030955>

Werners, S. E., Wise, R. M., Butler, J. R. A., et al. (2021). Adaptation pathways: A review of approaches and a learning framework. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 266-275.

Wise, R. M., Fazey, I., Stafford Smith, M., Park, S. E., Eakin, H. C., Archer Van Garderen, E. R., & Campbell, B. (2014). Reconceptualising adaptation to climate change as part of pathways of change and response. *_Global Environmental Change_, _28_, 325-336.*

References for Websites

Healthy Streets, (2023). What is Healthy Streets?. [online] Available at: <https://www.healthystreets.com/what-is-healthy-streets>. [Accessed 13.12.2023].

Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality, (2023). Toolkit for Stakeholder Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality. [online] Available at: <https://up2030.notion.site/Toolkit-for-Stakeholder-Engagement-towards-Carbon-Neutrality-1b79a41fcb954cb5b5f457f3364c58e0> [Accessed 11.12.2023].

UP2030. (2023). Pilot Cities. [online] Available at: <https://up2030-he.eu/pilot-cities/>. [Accessed 18.12.2023].

8. Annex

This section will include the additional materials that have been collected throughout the process, such as templates for preparatory activities or final outcomes.

8.1. Guide for Visioning

This section includes a guide, prepared for co-visioning and adaptive pathways process. The document also includes a compilation of recommendations drafted for each pilot city.

Glossary for Vision & Adaptive Pathways

To facilitate the visioning and adaptive pathways co-design process, a comprehensive glossary has been developed, featuring outlined key terms.

This glossary serves as a valuable resource to ensure that all stakeholders involved in the process have a clear and unified understanding of the relevant terms and their precise definitions.

Overview of Key Terms:

- Action
- Adaptive Pathways
- Adaptive Pathways Page
- Barriers
- Engagement Method
- Engagement Toolkit
- Pilot Objective
- Pilot Vision
- Vision Page
- Vision Pillar

Glossary for Vision & Adaptive Pathways

Action: a specific activity, task or intervention designed to implement a particular strategy and vision. Multiple sequenced actions form adaptive pathways, which outline paths towards transformation in the pilot.

Adaptive Pathways: a sequence of actions required to achieve a defined objective and vision. Barriers, timing points, and adaptability are considered in the sequencing of actions, which leads to alternative routes that can be taken in the future. This is a flexible and dynamic approach to implementing strategies, as it allows for adjustments and responses while addressing challenges and needs.

Adaptive Pathways Page: a concise document outlining the pilot's adaptive pathways process. It encapsulates actions, barriers and preferred strategy for achieving transformation, serving as a reference for the envisioned future state. [Link to come soon](#)

Barriers: refers to the obstacles and challenges that hinder the effective implementation of policies, programs or initiatives and which were identified during the needs and barriers assessment steps.

Engagement Method: structured approach designed to involve various stakeholders in the planning process and capture diverse insights presented in the process and to ensure that all concerns and responses are reflected.

Engagement Toolkit: a comprehensive collection of methodologies, technical partners that will be used within the project. The toolkit was designed based on the methodology used for the UP2030 project, aiming to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging participatory urban planning and design. [Link](#)

Glossary for Vision & Adaptive Pathways

Pilot Objectives: statements about desired outcomes for climate neutrality that the city is trying to achieve through UP2030 in the pilot area.

Pilot Vision: a clear, aspirational statement that outlines desired future scenarios which serves to guide short-term actions and long-term strategies towards sustainable, inclusive, and resilient urban development. The comprehensive future-oriented framework engaged various stakeholders, leverages innovative and technological solutions, and provides a holistic approach to urban development. A vision provides a crucial guiding framework for its realisation.

Vision Page: represents a concise document outlining the desired outcome of a pilot visioning process. It captures the vision statement, pilot visions and objectives, for the future that the visioning process seeks to achieve. [Link](#)

Vision Pillar: it represents a thematic element within the overarching Pilot Vision, focusing on a specific realm crucial to achieving inclusive, climate neutral and resilient urban development. Each Vision Pillar addresses distinct, yet interconnected, aspects of urban development and provides detailed, aspirational, objectives which will guide actions and decision making within its particular sphere.

- **Pillar for Carbon Neutrality** aims to establish a strategic framework for achieving net-zero carbon footprint within pilot area
- **Pillar for Resilience** aims to develop a foundation to enhance the capacity to anticipate, withstand, prepare and adapt to various challenges (environmental, social, economic)
- **Pillar for Just Transition** aims to ensure inclusive and equitable progress within the pilot area as it navigates towards a resilient and carbon neutral vision.

Process & Steps

Key Engagement Aspects

Before moving to the Visioning, it is highly recommended that cities consider the following:

Internal Stakeholders

What's the internal (city hall) stakeholders drive and collaboration level? Without the buy-in of key city hall decision-makers, projects have limited chances to succeed.

External Stakeholders

Is the level of external stakeholders' engagement satisfactory to ensure that visioning is successful? Visioners that do not recognise this are likely to suffer from community push-back, which also has major impacts on the project itself but also on reputation.

Expectations

If stakeholder engagement and participation has been high, do you have a plan to manage expectations? Not all needs will be addressed or met through this process, so it is good to be realistic and communicate transparently with your audience.

Priorities

To what extent are stakeholders clear on the priorities you want to tackle through this process? Lack of clarity makes stakeholder engagement processes less focused, and as a result, less efficient or null.

UP2030 Visioning Process Overview

A general overview of the UP2030 visioning process, outlining key milestones for planning up to 2030.

Customizable

It's essential to recognize that each city can tailor this process to its unique requirements and circumstances. The suggestions tailored to each pilot are at the end of this guide.

Workshop Options

Activities can be consolidated into a comprehensive on-site workshop or distributed over an extended period, treating each milestone as an individual phase.

Milestones & Activities

Every milestone comes with recommended activities and identifies stakeholders suggested to be involved. However, the execution and its timeline is flexible.

Engagement Methods

All methods utilized here are sourced from the UP2030 Engagement Toolkit. [View the Toolkit here](#)

Process

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

13

Overview of Suggested Methods

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

14

Validating Existing Objectives

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

15

Pillar Visions

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

16

Spatial Assessment

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

17

Pilot Vision

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement/ID 101019719

18

Actions and Barriers

Filtering Actions

Comprehensive Assessment

Validating Adaptive Pathways

Contextualising the Process

Contextualising the Visioning Process

A general overview of the UP2030 visioning process, outlining key milestones for planning up to 2030.

Istanbul Recommendations

- The aim is to build on existing information collected in UP2030 and not duplicate efforts and to precisely define the scope for mapping.
- To use the community mapping method to replicate on a strategic scale, integrated spatial analysis will support the ongoing on opportunities and obstacles for mobility from, throughout, between, and within urban local authority areas. Additionally, to identify areas most prone to climate impacts and most affected communities.
- Continuing dialogues with three more localised thematic experts under each UP2030 offer Cluster leadership, benchmarking, and Joint Transitions will help to frame the vision in the pilot's specific context.
- The goal is to build one holistic vision for the pilot area by guiding the decision-making process of the urban development of the pilot area. The consensus-making method can be used to create a conceptual spatial strategy connecting the opportunities identified in the integrated spatial analysis.
- The goal is to identify actions for achieving the vision. By using the matrix and scoring approach a process of UP2030 can be used to help to provide a set of alternative actions to avoid risks in the future and to provide an adaptive decision-making framework.
- Test the actions against criteria developed in the benchmarking task, to make sure actions do not lead to maladaptation.
- The technical assessment of adaptive pathways is conducted by the bottom partners and shared with the UP2030 pilot area as a step 6. In that way, more comprehensive urban development can be secured without limitation of time within workshop.
- The validation of the adaptive pathways for cities, as part of the co-design principle, is to ensure there is an iterative process after the comprehensive assessment.

Lisbon Recommendations

- The aim is to build on existing information collected in UP2030 and not duplicate efforts and to precisely define the scope for mapping.
- The community mapping method needs to be replicated on a strategic scale, with other pilots for the pilot area goal to use the UP2030 can be used to help to provide a set of alternative actions to avoid risks in the future and to provide an adaptive decision-making framework.
- Continuing dialogues with three more localised thematic experts under each UP2030 offer Cluster leadership, benchmarking, and Joint Transitions will help to frame the vision in the pilot's specific context.
- The goal is to build one holistic vision for a carbon-neutral, inclusive, and resilient region by guiding the decision-making process of the urban development of the pilot area. The consensus-making method can be used to create a conceptual spatial strategy including areas for interventions.
- The goal is to identify actions for achieving the vision. By using the matrix and scoring approach a process of UP2030 can be used to help to provide a set of alternative actions to avoid risks in the future and to provide an adaptive decision-making framework.
- Test the actions against criteria developed in the benchmarking task, to make sure actions do not lead to maladaptation.
- The technical assessment of adaptive pathways is conducted by the bottom partners and shared with the UP2030 pilot area as a step 6. In that way, more comprehensive urban development can be secured without limitation of time within workshop.
- The validation of the adaptive pathways for cities, as part of the co-design principle, is to ensure there is an iterative process after the comprehensive assessment.

Milan Recommendations

- The aim is to build on existing information collected in UP2030 and not duplicate efforts and to precisely define the scope for mapping.
- The consensus-making method can be used to determine priorities for climate-resilient development. Stakeholders are engaged in a co-design and feedback process, increasing spatial resilience and building resilience.
- Continuing dialogues with three more localised thematic experts under each UP2030 offer Cluster leadership, benchmarking, and Joint Transitions will help to frame the vision in the pilot's specific context.
- The goal is to build one holistic vision for the pilot area by guiding the decision-making process of the urban development of the pilot area. The consensus-making method can be used to create a conceptual spatial strategy connecting the opportunities identified in the integrated spatial analysis.
- The goal is to identify actions for achieving the vision. By using the matrix and scoring approach a process of UP2030 can be used to help to provide a set of alternative actions to avoid risks in the future and to provide an adaptive decision-making framework.
- Test the actions against criteria developed in the benchmarking task, to make sure actions do not lead to maladaptation.
- The technical assessment of adaptive pathways is conducted by the bottom partners and shared with the UP2030 pilot area as a step 6. In that way, more comprehensive urban development can be secured without limitation of time within workshop.
- The validation of the adaptive pathways for cities, as part of the co-design principle, is to ensure there is an iterative process after the comprehensive assessment.

Münster Recommendations

- The aim is to build on existing information collected in UP2030 and not duplicate efforts and to precisely define the scope for mapping.
- To use the community mapping method to replicate on a strategic scale, integrated spatial analysis will support the ongoing on opportunities and obstacles for mobility from, throughout, between, and within urban local authority areas. Additionally, to identify areas most prone to climate impacts and most affected communities.
- Continuing dialogues with three more localised thematic experts under each UP2030 offer Cluster leadership, benchmarking, and Joint Transitions will help to frame the vision in the pilot's specific context.
- The goal is to build one holistic vision for a shape of neighbourhood-level climate strategy. The consensus-making method can be used to create a conceptual spatial strategy connecting the opportunities identified in the integrated spatial analysis.
- The goal is to identify actions for achieving the vision. By using the matrix and scoring approach a process of UP2030 can be used to help to provide a set of alternative actions to avoid risks in the future and to provide an adaptive decision-making framework.
- Test the actions against criteria developed in the benchmarking task, to make sure actions do not lead to maladaptation.
- The technical assessment of adaptive pathways is conducted by the bottom partners and shared with the UP2030 pilot area as a step 6. In that way, more comprehensive urban development can be secured without limitation of time within workshop.
- The validation of the adaptive pathways for cities, as part of the co-design principle, is to ensure there is an iterative process after the comprehensive assessment.

Capacity Training: Cluster Specific

Cluster Rationale
Reasoning behind the clustering of cities for the purpose of the visioning capacity training

Going Through Entire Process
What is the step-by-step process of the co-visioning and adaptive pathways, and what are the associated engagement methods that can be used for each step.

Interactive Session
Running one engagement method in depth to gain a better understanding to support facilitation during the city sessions.

Final Templates
To have an idea of what the final outcome of the co-visioning process will look like to know what we are working towards.

Questions
To have time to be set aside for questions about the facilitation of the visioning process.

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement 101019746.

End Outcome

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement 101019746.

Vision Page

The Vision Page encompasses final outcomes from the engagement activities. The information collected by city team and liaisons, will be put together by the technical partners for the final output: Vision Page. Later, it will be presented to the city's project team for evaluation and validation.

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement 101019746.

Adaptive Pathways Page

The Adaptive Pathways Page encompasses final outcomes from the engagement activities during the second part of the visioning process. The information collected by city team and liaisons, will be put together by the technical partners for the final output: Adaptive Pathways Page. Later, it will be presented to the city's project team for evaluation and validation.

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement 101019746.

Questions & Support

Stakeholder Engagement and Visioning Task Force
Resilient Cities Network (RCN) - task force leader
rcn@resilientcitiesnetwork.org
Mapping for Change (Louise and Hannah)
lfranco@mappingforchange.org.uk
hstockwell@mappingforchange.org.uk
ICforall (Tommaso)
tommaso@icforall.eu

Visioning and Adaptive Pathways task group
TSPA (Annelis, Franke, and Dole) - task leader
ann@tspa.eu
Bart Heppelink (Jill, Felicitas, and Peter)
jill.theobald@bartheppelink.com
Felicitas.Lentz@bartheppelink.com

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Action under the grant agreement 101019746.

UP2030 Guide for the Visioning and Adaptive Pathways Process

8.2. Guiding Questions for Workshop Implementation

8.2.1. Co-Visioning

General

Set intentions and expectations for the workshop

- Define carbon neutrality, resilience and just transition - in each city's own terms.
 - Follow up with a question: Is there anyone who needs further clarification on this terminology or what is meant?
- What are the participants' desired outcomes from this workshop?
- For groups to stimulate introductions:
 - What is your name, professional background and relationship to the project?
 - If you could identify one key outcome of the project, what would it be?

Spatial Analysis

We suggest starting by explaining any vocabulary that may be unclear to participants, e.g. driver, climate neutrality, resilience.

Barriers/issues/challenges

- What are the barriers/issues/challenges related to climate change in the pilot area?
- What are the spatial issues/challenges related to carbon neutrality targets?
- What are the spatial challenges related to social inequalities?
- Which systems are most affected by climate change? (e.g. infrastructure, public spaces, neighbourhoods, landscape)
- Who/what target groups are most affected? (e.g. residents, business owners, vulnerable communities)
- Can you locate these on the map of the pilot area? (mark the most affected areas on the map and assign a letter to each)
- Which barriers do you see standing in the way of the validated objectives?
- Can you locate these on the map? (e.g. In the case of an objective regarding walkability or sustainable mobility, a barrier could be a major highway which runs through the pilot)

Opportunities/Strengths/Drivers

- What are the spatial opportunities to transform the area into a climate neutral, just, and resilient project area? (eg. unused riverfront, ongoing projects...)

- What synergies can be established / created between the above mentioned and UP2030 goals? How can these contribute to the project's core themes (carbon neutrality, resilience, just transition)?
- Who is the promoter/responsible agency (e.g. municipal department, community-based) for this identified opportunity?
- Can you locate these opportunities/strengths on the map of the pilot area? (mark the areas on the map and assign a number to each)
- What are the key spatial opportunities for the validated objectives? (e.g. disused parking lots for addition of green space)
- Can you locate these spaces on the map?

Pillar Vision

Provide a brief overview of the goals (Objectives validation document) and needs (list based on City Storyline document) collected so far.

Resilience

- What are the key elements of a resilient future for (insert name of pilot area)? (e.g. promoting biodiversity, water permeability, flood resilience, food security)
- Can you summarise these elements in one phrase that describes what a resilient future would look like in (insert pilot area name)?

Just Transition

- What are the key elements of a just future for (insert pilot area name)? (e.g. affordability, distribution of green spaces, diversity, intergenerational community)
- Can you summarise these elements in one phrase that describes what a resilient future would look like in (insert pilot area name)?

Carbon Neutrality

- What are the key elements of a carbon neutral future for (insert name of pilot area)? (e.g. local energy production, sustainable mobility, carbon sequestration)
- Can you summarise these elements in one sentence of what a carbon neutral future would look like in (insert pilot area name)?

Consolidate outcomes from each group.

Pilot Vision

Vision Statement

- If you were to read a newspaper article about the success of (insert pilot name), regarding its positive impacts on carbon neutrality, resilience, and the just transition, what would that headline say?
- Think about what the article would include: What achievements were made? What changes have they brought with them?

Give prompts to kick off the discussion (depending on what question is asked):

- (Insert pilot name) is a place where....

Spatial understanding of the objectives & vision (optional)

- **Question to be answered overall by the exercise:** What are the high-level spatial strategies, needed to achieve the defined objectives and vision?
- What are the ongoing projects that could contribute to achieving the resilient, carbon neutral, just future of (insert pilot name)? Can you locate which spatial areas they relate to?
- Where are the key (spatial) areas that you identify as opportunities, to achieve transformation towards the envisioned future/identified objectives? (e.g. water fronts, green areas, street network, industrial areas, housing stock, public spaces, etc.)
- Taking the key opportunity areas from the previous question, can you identify the components of the vision which could be implemented in these spaces? Mark these down on the map.

8.2.2. Adaptive Pathways

Checklist

- *We suggest providing the suggestions for each table, to ensure guided and comprehensive discussion. It is a role of the moderator to guide the participants through the process according to the suggestions listed below.*

Prior the Workshop

- We suggest to include the pilot objectives into the workshop invitation. Set the clear goals and expectations of the session. If possible, ask participants to come prepared – ideate actions related to achieve the set objectives
- Revise the prompts suggested for each objective and if needed, refine the prompts together with UP2030 partners
- Once the list is settled, translate the: checklist, prompts and objectives.
- Technical partners will provide templates

Introduction – Guiding points to start the discussion on actions identification

It is recommended to provide overview of already collected needs and barriers to the participants, to avoid asking the same questions as before. Also, provide a brief re-cap of identified vision, objectives and UP2030 goals for the pilot

- Keep in mind that not all objectives need to be long-term; many can also be achieved through the short-term activities
- Build upon existing programs, plans, and agendas, leveraging what is already working in the status quo.
- Identify actions needed to shift from 'business as usual' to a more innovative approach in order to achieve the vision - transformation.

Start - Setting actions/activities/measures per each objective

- **Moderator of the table should encourage the participants to explore the feasibility, success conditions as well as risk associated to each action that will be derived.**
- Determine immediate actions required to fulfil or respond to urgent issues.
- Explore how initial findings from short-term actions can be organised to bridge the gap towards long-term strategies. What are the medium-term strategies?
- Identify which long-term actions can bring more structural changes to achieve the objective and therefore, the vision.
- Highlight interdependencies between identified actions

Validation - Adaptive pathway identification

- Revisit the template to discuss and refine the defined actions. The goal is to identify risks or barriers that might hinder the implementation.
- Identify the risks that might pose challenges or obstacles to the successful implementation of the listed pathways. (*Pathway is set of actions per objective*)
- Determine actions/strategies that can be put in place to mitigate the identified risks.

8.3. [Action Prompts](#)

8.3.1. [Belfast](#)

Greening group

Objective: Improve access to greenspace for residents

- Describe ways to ensure that greenspaces are socially and economically accessible to all residents. Consider the location, entry fees, and the types of activities and amenities offered
- Identify what strategies, policies and design interventions are necessary to ensure greenspaces are physically accessible to individuals with disabilities, including those requiring wheelchair access, and to the elderly
- Identify the financial strategies/ actions to ensure the long-term maintenance of green spaces

Objective: Increase green infrastructure in the pilot areas

- Identify how underutilised areas or vacant spaces within the neighbourhood that can be transformed into green spaces or pocket parks (if possible, mark them on the map)
- Identify potential funding sources and financial mechanisms for green infrastructure projects. Consider public funds, grants, private investments, and public-private partnerships
- Define strategies and mechanisms to integrate innovative design approaches for green infrastructure addressing specific local challenges, such as flooding, heat, and biodiversity loss

Objective: Buy-in achieved from residents

- Identify and list strategies/actions (i.e. policy, process, incentives oriented) to encourage community involvement in the development and upkeep of green spaces
- Identify and list strategies for establishing a practice for participatory design processes that involve residents in the planning and design of green spaces. How can these processes be structured to be inclusive and empowering?

Objective: Increased community cohesion through shared spaces

- Define an action to include the communities in the co-design of shared spaces
- Define strategies to increase the attractiveness of current shared spaces (consider current barriers to attractivity and how to overcome them)
- Identify what would be the governance arrangements needed (in terms of financial sustainability and organisational responsibility) to develop an agenda of activities in these shared spaces. You can identify on the map which spaces are more relevant to host different kinds of activities.

Objective: Reduced risk of flooding and heat islands

- Identify potential trade-offs that can arise from implementing measures against flooding and heat islands (i.e., increase of grey infrastructure against flooding)
- Define strategies for how to integrate green infrastructure elements like rain gardens, bioswales, permeable pavements, and green roofs to be integrated into urban planning process or existing places to mitigate climate risk
- Define strategies to engage communities in the planning and implementation of flood and heat reduction strategies (i.e. consider community-led green space initiatives)
- Define how the connectivity between green spaces, water bodies, and other natural elements can be improved to enhance ecological corridors that mitigate flooding and heat

Objective: Increased carbon offset

- Identify spatial strategies, intervention for optimising urban form to reduce carbon emissions within the pilot area
- Identify strategies to update policies/guidelines for low-carbon urban planning/design, for example: promoting mix use developments, green infrastructure, sustainable transportation
- Identify strategies for establishing monitoring process of carbon emissions to assess the impact of different offset strategies.

- Describe an action to upskill Belfast's practitioners on the topic of carbon offsetting

Active travel group

Objective: Improve active travel infrastructure that is fit for purpose

- Describe an action to ensure that the improvement of active travel infrastructure considers the needs of every population group.
- Describe an action to involve citizens and local communities in the co-design of the new infrastructures
- Reflect on an action to improve multi-scale coordination through the development of new infrastructures
- Define strategies/interventions/actions for retrofitting existing urban spaces to accommodate active travel infrastructure. If possible, mark them on the map

Objective: Improve reliability and affordability of public transport

- Describe an action to enhance the coordination between the different institutions which oversee providing public transport services
- Reflect about new potential financial streams / change in the business model to allow for more affordability of public transport

Objective: Induce behavioural change among residents regarding the choice of mobility mode

- Describe the characteristics needed for the active travel infrastructures to be easily accessible for every population group (i.e., children, elderly). List strategies/actions to achieve them.
- Describe actions to ensure that all categories of the population are being reached by communication campaigns and incentives.
- Define what improvements are needed in terms of infrastructure (e.g., dedicated bike lanes, pedestrian-friendly streets, efficient public transit) to support a shift in mobility behaviour

Objective: Extend the framework to other neighbourhoods in Belfast

- Describe an action to improve multi-scale coordination to facilitate the upscaling of these methods in other areas of Belfast.
- Describe a strategy aiming to mitigate risks of gentrification that could be associated with the larger-scale transformation of the mobility system

Objective: Transform the city into a more child-friendly environment and enhance safety

- Describe an action to engage children and include their perception in the co-design of the transport system
- Describe strategies to ensure children are able to use infrastructures for active mobility (i.e., consider financial barriers, cycling skills, collaboration with schools and community centres).

Retrofitting

Objective: Achieve harmonization among existing policies that currently conflict or contrast

- Define what is needed to conduct a detailed review and mapping of all existing policies related to building retrofitting. What are the specific areas of conflict or contrast between these policies?
- Describe how dedicated task force could facilitate the consolidation and implementation of harmonized policies and monitor their impact.
- Describe what is needed to implement pilot projects to test the practical application of harmonized policies. How can these projects provide insights into the effectiveness of policy integration?

Objective: Develop and implement a more efficient, simplified planning process

- Identify how integration of digital tools and technologies can be incorporated to simplify the application and approval process.
- Describe steps to streamline approval processes, such as combining or eliminating certain approvals or using a tiered system based on project complexity
- Describe training and capacity building actions for planning department staff to improve handling retrofitting applications more efficiently
- Define strategies to enhance coordination between different municipal departments (e.g., building, environmental, zoning) involved in the retrofitting approval process

Objective: Improve the energy efficiency of buildings and reduce carbon footprint from buildings

- Describe actions to update building codes and standards to reflect the latest energy-efficient technologies and practices. What specific changes are needed to encourage or mandate higher efficiency standards?
- Describe what is needed to develop targeted retrofit programs to improve insulation, heating and cooling systems, lighting, and other key aspects of energy use in buildings.
- Identify what financial or regulatory incentives can be offered to building owners to undertake these retrofits. How various financial models such as on-bill financing, green bonds, or performance contracting can be implemented to fund energy efficiency projects?

Objective: Reduce the risks of energy poverty (derived from reduce energy bills)

- Outline steps to explore new funding models, such as sliding scale payments, and ways to enhance the visibility and accessibility of these subsidies.
- Identify the actions needed to implement educational and outreach programs that effectively teach energy-saving techniques and inform vulnerable communities about available energy assistance.

Objective: Extend the framework to other neighborhoods in Belfast

- Describe the necessary steps to ensure economic viability, including addressing upfront costs of renovation projects and creating sustainable financial models
- Describe an action for encouraging the creation of new business opportunities for local stakeholders during the upscaling process

8.3.2. Budapest**Objective 1: Urban development professionals (architects, designers, urban planners, engineers) learn and apply extensively Budapest's Healthy Street approach in practice in public space development projects.**

- Describe an action to enhance coordination between departments and practitioners while learning and applying the approach
- Describe a strategy to extend the Healthy Street approach beyond the municipality to involve external stakeholders (i.e., consultancy and engineering firms, architects, etc.)
- Describe how principles of HS approach can be integrated into the curricula of educational institutions to train future architects/planners/engineers
- How can the application of the methodology be disseminated across districts?
- How can municipalities outside the capital be encouraged to apply the methodology to public space planning and development?
- Describe an action aiming to mitigate risks of gentrification linked to the scaling-up of the Healthy Streets approach
- Describe an action allowing cross-sectoral and stakeholders coordination during the wide-spread implementation of the approach
- Describe the financial actions needed for the widespread implementation of the approach (think about the initial costs and the longer-term maintenance costs).

Objective 2: Creation of 'LAA' for Budapest Healthy Streets to disseminate and adapt the methodology, creation of discourse, and the establishment of Healthy Streets knowledge centre.

- Define what action and strategies are needed to establish the knowledge centre and maintain it over the long term
- Define what financial mechanisms are needed to establish a centre. Identify associated risk that could hinder the implementation and maintenance of the centre
- Describe actions to train and capacitate LAA members for establishing and running the knowledge centre
- Describe a strategy to effectively communicate about the framework to Budapest's residents and local stakeholders
- Define the governance arrangements needed to facilitate widespread learning and application of the method within the municipality of Budapest.

Objective 3: Enhance Budapest citizens' public discourse on public health of their streets and public spaces, awareness raising and building public expectations.

- Describe an action to ensure that the discourse and awareness-raising efforts reach every population group, including those in low-socioeconomic neighbourhood
- Describe an action to promote collective agency among citizens, to be more involved in the projects concerning their surrounding streets and public spaces

Objective 4: Testing community mapping instruments in line with the Healthy Street approach to gather public opinion, define potential projects and development targets, and raise awareness.

- Describe an action to ensure that the use of community mapping instruments is inclusive and involve different communities and social groups

Objective 5: Create guides and standards for our own companies, districts and the planners involved.

- What is needed for Municipality of Budapest to prepare and enforce standards for its own companies or for third parties (districts, private property developers etc.)
- Describe sub-actions/steps to ensure that the standards incorporate the UP2030 dimensions of carbon-neutrality and resilience and social justice.
- Define action how guides and standards can include community involvement approaches in the planning and development process.
- Explore what strategies can be used embedded these guides and standards into planning and development processes within private and public sector. What mechanisms can be put in place to adapt the guides in response to changes in regulations and policies?

Objective 6: Involvement of market players who are (financially) interested and can be the drivers of change

- Think about an action to ensure the transparency of decision taken by financial stakeholders
- Describe an action to keep market players interested in the long-term
- Identify what actions are needed to ensure that private sector investments align with broader urban development goals and regulations (sustainability, inclusivity)

Objective 7: Supporting the involvement of local citizens through the districts in the planning and implementation.

- Describe an action to support behavioural change through the involvement of citizens (educational outcomes)
- Describe an action to ensure the involvement of citizens is inclusive, and every group and community participate in the discussion
- Describe an action for ensuring that the involvement of local citizens influence local policies and is coordinated with the policies of the local government
- Describe an action to promote collective learning and the development of new knowledge through citizen involvement

Objective 8: Implement Healthy Streets projects across Budapest (winning proposals).

- Discuss what are the strategies to monitor the success and impact of the HS projects on topics such as liveability, health, environmental sustainability, carbon neutrality, etc.

Objective 9: Achievement of a standard noise level

- Describe an action promoting the coordination of different departments of the municipality to tackle this issue
- Describe an action to train Budapest's practitioners on the topic of noise pollution and its consequences for the environment and human health.
- Describe a strategy to ensure that the population most vulnerable to noise pollution, living in high density areas or near the main axis of communication, are being targeted/ prioritized in the implementation of noise reduction policies.

8.3.3. Granollers**Objective 1 – Designing La Bòbila to be a net-zero emissions neighbourhood (guidelines and KPIs)**

Q: How would you define the criteria and technical requirements necessary for La Bòbila to achieve carbon neutrality? (Think about aspects such as embedded carbon in buildings, mobility, and food?) What do see as the greatest risks or barriers for Granollers to arrive at a carbon-neutral design?

Q: How do you intend to engage and involve the community in the definition of guidelines and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for achieving carbon neutrality in La Bòbila? What are the challenges you could foresee in this process?

Objective 2 - Defining Policy recommendations to achieve climate neutrality, resilience, and liveability in La Bòbila

Q: What do you think are the potential trade-offs between carbon-neutrality, resilience, and justice in the development of the vision for La Bòbila? I.e., Which priorities are at risk of competing against each other?

Q: How do you propose integrating resilience and justice considerations alongside carbon-neutrality to prevent negative externalities?

Q: How will you facilitate the collaboration among different municipal departments to develop holistic policy recommendations for La Bòbila's transformation? (Think about the transportation, housing, and waste management departments, among others)

Objective 3 - Development of other climate-neutral areas in the city by 2030 (urban renovation areas)

Q: What steps are necessary to ensure economic viability and sustainable financial models for the development of climate-neutral areas? More particularly, how will you address the upfront costs needed?

Q: Based on the methods and innovations used for La Bòbila, which do you believe are the most feasible and appealing for replication in other neighbourhoods of Granollers? What are the challenges achieving similar outcomes in other contexts?

Q: How will the community be involved in the development of these new climate-neutral areas? Will the methods used in UP to involve the communities and stakeholders be replicated?

Objective 4 - Identifying the balance between grey and blue/green infrastructure through the use of the RESCUE tool

Q: Will the municipality's practitioners have to upskill in order to use and implement the tools from UP? If yes, how do you propose to do that?

Q: What criteria should the RESCUE tool consider to promote green infrastructures within La Bòbila?

Objective 5 - Link urban green grid and related projects with the East Mountain, agricultural, and river spaces through La Bòbila's green infrastructure, as part of the Green City strategy development

Q: Can you identify spatial interventions and projects to support the creation of a green grid in La Bòbila? What intervention will be needed to link the grid with neighboring areas such as the East Mountain, agricultural lands, and river spaces?

Q: What characteristics do you believe are essential for the green infrastructure of La Bòbila to be inclusive for all groups? (Elderly, children, etc.) Will the green spaces of La Bòbila be inclusive through active transportation modes?

Q: Are other scales of governance involved in the development of the Green City Strategy? (i.e., regional or national stakeholders). If yes, how are you coordinating with them? How could this collaboration be enhanced?

Objective 6 - Implementing cross-cutting climate mitigation and spatial justice tools to assess future urban planning (RESCUE and Parametric tool)

Objective 7 - Creation of a citizen laboratory focused on the urban transformation of the city

Q: How do you imagine the collaboration between the Citizen Laboratory, the local government and the municipal departments? What will be needed in order to foster a collaboration?

Q: Can you outline the governance arrangements required for the Citizen Laboratory to function effectively? More specifically, how will you ensure its financial sustainability? Who will ensure the different tasks and responsibilities?

Objective 8: Preventing Gentrification

Q: What are the greatest risks for gentrification in the development of La Bòbila? If unmitigated, how could La Bòbila be a source of gentrification?

Q: According to you, what could be potential actions to mitigate the risks of gentrification in Granollers? (Think about La Bòbila but also future carbon-neutral areas).

Q: The topic of gentrification and affordable housing can concern different departments. Is your own department knowledgeable about this issue? How do you intend to collaborate with other departments? If a collaboration is already in place, what could be done to strengthen it?

Objective 9: Maintaining Inclusion and Equity

Q: According to you, what are the criteria the municipality should follow to ensure inclusion and equity within La Bòbila? What are the strategies could be implemented to ensure that the needs of different groups are being addressed in the spatial development of La Bòbila?

Q: How could you envision a system that assesses whether Granollers' principles of equity and inclusion are – over time – being maintained? How could this be monitored throughout the future development La Bòbila and beyond to the occupation of the site?

Objective 10: Integration of the policy recommendations in tender processes/calls for urban transformation/renovation projects

Q: Can you think of an action to ensure that policy guidelines (for resilience, justice, and carbon neutrality) are integrated into future tender processes? How can this be formalised in order to avoid the risk of inconsistent implementation across new projects?

Q: Given the challenge of collaboration across municipal departments such as transportation, housing, waste management, etc., how can the risk of developing these policy recommendations in silos be avoided? Can you think of a strategy to facilitate collaboration among different departments?

8.3.4. Milan

Objective 1: Evaluate the environmental, social and economic benefits of the climate adaptation measures (e.g. depaving, NBS, forestation) included in the Air Climate Plan, in order to assess their effectiveness.

- *Identify what is needed to create a detailed framework for evaluating social and economic benefits. What should be the criteria to assess the benefits of the climate adaptation measures?*
- *What do you think are the potential risks that can arise between environmental, social and economic outcomes of the adaptation measure? Which priorities are at risk to compete against each other? How are you planning on assessing those trade-offs?*
- *What is needed to be done to gather needed data for such evolution?*
- *What are the strategies to assess cost benefits of quick wins versus long term goals of such measures?*

Objective 2: Quantifying how many green spaces are needed to keep the increase in urban temperatures below 2°C by 2050 compared to 2017 (PAC challenge).

- *What needs to be implemented to achieve a quantitative understanding of the need for green spaces? (Which departments and actors should be responsible for leading this? Which tools are required?)*

- *Should the quantification consider only the total cumulative green space or focus on distribution? What are the relative trade-offs between larger centralised green spaces and smaller distributed green spaces and networks?*
- *How do you envision the community being involved in assessing green space deficits?*

Objective 3: Being able to compare different project scenarios of urban projects to find the best one in terms of environmental, social and economic benefits provided to the city.

- *What actions need to be taken to develop the knowledge, skills, and tools required in order to have the capacity for such comparisons?*
- *What do you see as risks in trying to weight the importance of each of these aspects against each other? (For example, how do you see weighing the economic benefits and costs against environmental benefits?)*
- *How do you think such comparison systems should be standardised and communicated with external stakeholders?*

Objective 4: Providing guidance for drafting projects to real estate operators.

- *What needs to be done to ensure fair communication and guidance to real estate operators and developers?*
- *How should these development stakeholders be involved in the process of shaping the new set of standards and compensation systems?*
- *What risks do you see in the communication between the municipality and real estate operators in this process? (What sort of opposition do you expect to arise?)*

Objective 5: Improving the actual methodology used to calculate the compensation to be asked to real estate operators responsible for urban transformation, also including related biophysical and economic value of green areas (thus considering the impact of their intervention on ES).

- *How should the calculation for compensation be decided upon? Who is responsible for assessing the relative value of different Ecosystem Services?*
- *In your opinion, what would be the best way to develop this methodology and to roll it out in practice? (Especially regarding consistency across projects and with different real estate operators)*
- *What potential risks do you see regarding the ecosystem service compensation framework? How could the system fail to contribute effectively to Milan's climate, resilience, and justice targets?*

Objective 6: Providing the planners with guidance on green areas for urban regeneration projects.

- *How do you think planners should be informed / educated on this new methodology of ES compensation for green areas? Which systems would they need training on?*
- *Who - whether internal or external - should be responsible for shaping and delivering the training programme?*

Objective 7: Comparing the ES of the masterplan with those of the Final Project and quantify the compensation in terms of ES (to be compensated).

- *What needs to be done in order to have a functioning compensation mechanism?*
- *How should the form and location of compensation be decided upon? How should the community be involved in the decision making process?*

8.3.5. Münster

Objective 1: Coordination between mitigation and adaptation measures

- *List what could be the potential trade-offs between mitigation and adaptation while developing certain resilient concepts for the inner city of Münster. (For example, the sponge city concept and its relationship to carbon footprint). For each example, you can describe overcoming strategies.*
- *Describe a strategy to coordinate between the different departments in charge of various adaptation and mitigation policies.*
- *Teil des 1. Workshops und Darstellung im Leitfaden (Rollen und Zuständigkeiten)*
- *Consider a strategy to create synergies between parallel projects in Münster.*
- *Integration in den Leitfaden durch "Exkurs" Boxen von umgesetzten Beispielen und Verweisen auf Synergien*

Objective 2: Social and spatial justice through participatory approaches

- *Describe an action to ensure the involvement of citizens is inclusive and reflects the diversity of public space users. How should the city address the potential clash between preservation of historical spaces and materials and environmental objectives.*
- *Describe actions required to ensure diverse and particularly underrepresented demographics are made more visible in urban space?*
- *Describe a strategy to financially support the development of participatory workshops within the city.*
- *Describe an action that would ensure that the transformation strategies reflect social and spatial justice of both the residents of the inner (old) city, and residents who visit and work in there (i.e. accessibility, heat-stress, etc.)*
- *Integration in den Leitfaden durch Verweis auf "Komonitor" Tool der Stadt*

Objective 3: To become a blueprint for other districts

- *Reflect on what are the methods used in Frauenstraße that could be the most feasible to replicate in other neighbourhoods.*
- *Sanierungsmaßnahmen und zug. (KfW) Förderung: Integration in den Leitfaden*
- *Describe what would be the focal points of a communication strategy aimed at promoting the energy transformation in the neighbourhood of Frauenstraße. How could this be kickstarted?*
- *How could the approaches used and tested for contested topics in Frauenstraße be documented and shared for their replicability and upscaling?*

Objective 4: Leveraging & Adapting the Klima Training Programme for greater equity

- *How could a superblock or car-free concept for the Frauenstraße neighbourhood begin to be implemented? What would the first (or next) steps be?*
- *Verweis auf Reallabor Innenstadt (Autofreie Straßen, VeloRouten etc. Als Best Practice): Was waren die Prozesse für eine positive Umsetzung? Integration in Beispielboxen des Leitfadens*
- *Describe an action that could ensure that equity is included in the Klima training programme - both in terms of who receives the training, and within the training curriculum itself. How can social and spatial justice be taught as a parallel pillar alongside CO2 mitigation, resilience, and climate adaptation?*
- *Partizipative Strang in der Weiterentwicklung Climate Proofing (Bezug auch zu Prompt 02)*
- *Describe the actions required to facilitate the Klima training programme for short and long term efficacy.*
- *How could a networking app for climate training in the neighbourhood be implemented?*

Objective 5: Co-creation of a neighbourhood level roadmap for climate strategies

- *What are the next actions required to develop the neighbourhood level roadmap for climate strategies?*
- *How can the Climate Proofing tool be leveraged to deliver a plan for short and long term transformation?*
- *What actions are required to upscale the roadmap to other parts of the city?*
- *What information, data, or expertise are required to*

Objective 6: Harmonise use of technical tools and planning instruments between departments *Describe an action that would facilitate alignment of departments in their usage of technical tools and planning instruments.*

- *Erste Schritte des Climate Proofing zum Verstehen/ Analysieren der Grundlagen und Einsatz von vorhandenen Tools (in Münster)*
- *What new tools need to be developed or adopted? Describe the actions required to integrate these into municipal processes?*
- *Fokus auf Tools, die aktuell in der Entwicklung sind: wie können diese langfristig in Entwicklungs- und Entscheidungsprozesse integriert werden?*

Objective 7: Explore possibility of implementing temporary and mobile interventions

- *What are the actions required to change and update policies to facilitate new testing of temporary and mobile solutions?*
- *What would be the required actions to determine which parts of the neighbourhood temporary solutions should be implemented in.*
- *Describe a strategy to involve citizens into the co-design of these temporary interventions. How can equity and spatial justice be incorporated into the process?*
- *KlimaTraining*
- *Which temporary or mobile solutions are most critical and/or impactful to test? Describe the steps required to test and potentially upscale new temporary solutions.*

Objective 8: Explore what specific data is missing and for what purpose and to identify what data collection is still needed (to enable climate proofing or support the realisation of the pilot, for example) Describe the governance arrangements required to develop this strategy of data collection (i.e., consider financial needs, upskilling requirements, organisational responsibilities, upskilling needs, etc.)

- *Which are the most pressing data needs in order to estimate the conditions/impacts of green in urban space? Describe the actions required to ameliorate the challenges.*
- *Describe the actions required to build an effective digital twin model that would facilitate the alignment of new blue/green infrastructures with existing built and underground infrastructure.*

Objective 9: Internal department cooperation and buy-in

- *Describe a strategy to improve the coordination between the different internal departments of the municipality.*
- *Which sort of thematic or dedicated planning teams might need to be established to achieve Münster's climate goals? If any, what are the steps necessary to implement them?*
- *Describe a strategy to upskill municipality's practitioners on digital twin*

8.3.6. Thessaloniki

Objective 1: [Sustainable Mobility] Promote eco-friendly transport modes

- Describe an action leading to collective learning and promoting a change of behaviour among Thessaloniki's residents.
- Identify which specific streets or corridors in the neighbourhood could be redesigned and how to prioritise pedestrians and cyclists, potentially introducing car-free zones or shared streets
- Define how neighbourhood's layout and land use can be optimized to support local shops, services, and amenities within walking or cycling distance for most residents

Objective 2: [Green Spaces] Provide more green and open spaces and infrastructures adding more natural elements

- Describe a strategy to allow for a greater use of current open spaces.
- Identify how underutilized land, such as vacant lots, rooftops, and abandoned spaces, be transformed into green areas like community gardens, pocket parks, or green roofs. If possible, mark that on the map.
- Describe actions to ensure that the new green open space is accessible and attractive for all categories of people (i.e., elderly, children)
- Define how can zoning laws and building codes be adapted to promote the creation, accessibility and maintenance of green and open spaces
- Define strategies how local communities can be engaged in the design and maintenance (stewardship) of green and open spaces

- Identify how underutilized land, such as vacant lots, rooftops, and abandoned spaces, be transformed into green areas like community gardens, pocket parks, or green roofs. If possible, mark that on the map.

Objective 3: [Waste Management] Improve recycling efficiency and introduce circular economy model

- Describe a strategy to develop better recycling and composting systems, starting by tackling the lack of bins (think about spatial, organisational and financial arrangements).
- Define strategies (policies, programs, regulations) to advocate for supporting circular economy initiatives, mandatory recycling or bans
- Describe an action to raise awareness about the aim and functioning of circular economy among the residents

The following prompts were not used, as the city decided for a different approach

Objective 4: [Buildings] Increase the energy efficiency of the buildings (private & public)

- Describe the necessary actions to ensure a sustainable business model and financial streams necessary for the wide-scale improvement of the building stock.
- If retrofitting public buildings is within the jurisdiction of the municipality, this is not the case for private buildings. Reflect about the actions needed to induce change within the private building stock.

Objective 5: [Response] Improve climate preparedness and emergency response strategies

- Describe a strategy to upskill municipality's practitioners on the topic of climate change, climate risks, and resilience
- Define upgrades and strategies/ nature based solutions to be made to the neighbourhood's infrastructure (e.g., drainage systems, electrical grid, permeable surfaces, natural cooling systems) to make it more resilient to climate change impacts

Objective 6: [Housing] Establish affordable, green and social housing policies

- Describe an action to reduce administrative/ bureaucratic barriers that could impede the access to social housing
- Describe the administrative and financial steps necessary to make the building in Dioikitirion available for social housing
- Define policy strategies to maintain or increase the affordability of existing housing units while improving their quality and sustainability

Objective 7: [Economy] Create a dynamic and balanced local economy

- Describe an action to enhance cross-departmental coordination on this topic, in order to develop synergies between different sectors (food, hospitality, services, etc.)
- Describe a strategy and actions to encourage the creation of new business opportunities for local stakeholders through the development of a circular economy model.

8.4. [Pilot Adaptive Pathways Pages](#)

The following section presents the initial adaptive pathways developed to UP2030 pilots. The Adaptive Pathways Page represents the shorted version of pathways, showcasing strategies/projects per objectives. The pathways page is seen rather as a communication tool, therefore, cities which have developed adaptive pathways also received an a more comprehensive, editable version, also known as pathways database.

8.4.1. Adaptive Pathways Page for Belfast

Adapted from: [Urban Access Hub](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union under the grant agreement n° 101019760

Risk Legend

Active Mobility

- R1. Multi-annual Funding
- R2. Cost and accessibility
- R3. Travelling in changing weather is off-putting
- R4. Funding needs to be longer term investment. Not year to year - month to month
- R5. Working with multiple stakeholders
- R6. Not cohesive
- R7. Multiple silos
- R8. Disjointed process for thinking about Active Travel
- R9. BCC has no powers
- R10. Public perceptions. Need to focus on the benefits not the cost
- R11. Need to factor in a genuine co-design phase for at least 3 months for active travel at a neighbourhood level and should be an essential part of the programme, not a box-ticking yes/no exercise.
- R12. Pedestrian friendly streets
- R13. Need to have a resilience aspect
- R14. Health benefits etc
- R15. Engaging but also maybe just giving stakeholders information but go ahead
- R16. Address barriers to public transport costs e.g. proposed change to increase age to 65
- R17. Timescales to implement legislative changes for bus lanes - need to speed up
- R18. Messaging about why city is greening and keeping foot fall up and people not worrying about lack of parking
- R19. Think beyond financial benefits - benefits for people and community
- R20. Planning applications. Currently there's 2 extremes – very high or very low density
- R21. Funding. Changing mindsets
- R22. Campaigns on Billboards - People represented, need to relate to themselves
- R23. Leadership and governance
- R24. School run need to be tackled
- R25. Challenge for communities to access jobs in places like gasworks due to attainment challenges
- R26. Congestion from parents travelling into area
- R27. The culture is risk-averse
- R28. A shift needs to happen in behaviour change - accepting its wrong problem and the desire to change
- R29. Educational/Awareness
- R30. The experience for children needs to change
- R31. Greener. Improving air quality. A much better experience as well as safer

Belfast

Greening

As part of the framework, consider a menu of proposals that support green infrastructure development and net zero ambitions including tree planting, SUDS, rooftop gardens, and improving the quality of existing open spaces.

Adapted from: [Reflex Gaming](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Research under the grant agreement n° 101019718

Risk Legend

Greening

- R1. The gasworks – the green area in the Markets accessed by an Asian family playing cricket – but they were stopped
- R2. Territorial issues to accessing
- R3. Verity lane Cat 3 (S.0) It needs to be balanced approach - mix of housing, (students and residents) services and prioritise green space
- R4. Planning law and polices legislation - how can that lead to developers positively contributing creating green space
- R5. Using tech to inform decision making
- R6. Value of green space - none in city
- R7. Competition over funding and resources
- R8. Deposit/return scheme
- R9. Revenue funding is difficult to get
- R10. Finding a way to build trust with people- needs a realistic timeframe
- R11. Resource engagement. It is more expensive but currently not valued. Shouldn't be tokenistic
- R12. Community taking ownership looking at case study like Peace park
- R13. Air conditioning will be required to cool future budlings and that heat is pushed out
- R14. Not being done because its not mandatory e.g. SUDS
- R15. Working in silos
- R16. Disjointed planning for flood alleviation
- R17. New flood barriers or greenspaces may cause feelings of insecurity for vulnerable groups e.g. women
- R18. Wider context DFI & NIW, Hospitals, Schools City wide problem needs to be a shift in thinking. NIW capacity for drainage so how we address this
- R19. Green building audits – how can this be incentivised
- R20. How SMEs can begin to look at carbon footprint – don't know where to start – what support is there?
- R21. Play and risk with water
- R22. Perception: uncertainty of coming into a space not for them
- R23. Playgrounds are impermeable and amplify or reflect heat

Belfast

Retrofitting

Retrofitting is the act of adapting a building to increase energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption through a range of interventions such as modifications to the building fabric (insulation, airtightness improvement, ventilation, new and improved windows and doors), new or improved low carbon heating systems and renewable energy generation.

UP2030 This project has received funding from the European Union under the grant agreement n° 101016064

8.4.2. Adaptive Pathways Page for Budapest

This project has received funding from the Horizon Research Action under the grant agreement of 101019400

Adapted from: [Baker](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union under the grant agreement n° 101016045

Risk Legend

- R1.** Risk in the application of methodology
- R2.** Old habits, difficult to change professionally
- R3.** No dedicated funding in Budapest municipality's budget for active mobility and road safety improvements
- R4.** Designers are not familiar with all parts of the permitting process
- R5.** Not familiar with Healthy Streets methodology, reluctant to apply it
- R6.** Establishment, maintenance and operation of a knowledge centre is questionable in the absence of resources
- R7.** Continuous improvement of knowledge transfer so that it does not become irrelevant
- R8.** One-sided composition, missing actors (private sector, educational institutions, public sector?)
- R9.** Without a "project" (money), the actors are not motivated
- R10.** But what about the parking spaces?
- R11.** Passivity
- R12.** Bottom-up initiatives stalled, validation in Healthy Streets project
- R13.** Continuous improvement of knowledge transfer so that it does not become irrelevant
- R14.** One-sided composition, missing actors (private sector, educational institutions, public sector?)
- R15.** Applications should be available in Hungarian (language barriers)
- R16.** Digital culture, lack of "literacy" (elderly)
- R17.** Availability of online map tool "barrier-free" version for people without internet, smartphone
- R18.** Passivity, lack of motivation among the public
- R19.** Failure to reach out to potentially engaged partners, use their resources
- R20.** Resources of the civil sector are final
- R21.** Companies, districts and institutions will not use the guides. They will not follow them because they are only recommendations and not binding.
- R22.** If the guidelines are not clear, they will not be effective
- R23.** If it is produced but not "disseminated" , it will not be effective
- R24.** Actors are not open to involvement and do not see it as in their interest to invest time and money
- R25.** Striving for a mandatory minimum, maximum profit
- R26.** Municipality's "follow" behaviour, "deal" situations
- R27.** Market actors (SMEs) lack resources
- R28.** Not interested in changing the status quo
- R29.** Lack of engagement is the biggest risk, and all actors (e.g. districts) need to understand this money
- R30.** Decision makers do not undertake plans to backstop car traffic, they prefer to introduce them at the last minute
- R31.** Ineffective involvement, lack of interest
- R32.** No interest from the district in creating a dialogue with residents
- R33.** Cost overruns, reduction of technical content
- R34.** Abandonment of the project after implementation
- R35.** Costs exceed the resources available or received, causing a possible deterioration in quality
- R36.** Different priorities due to new district management
- R37.** If there is no direct financial incentive, urban public spaces will not be renovated according to the Healthy Streets methodology
- R38.** Politics does not dare to control and punish drivers (speeding, noise)
- R39.** Difficulty of rational control, controllability
- R40.** Not a "sexy" topic in public opinion

8.4.3. Adaptive Pathways Page for Granollers

Adapted from: [Source]

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Access under the grant agreement n° 101016045

Risk Legend

- R1. Speed, coordination, lack of resources (incl. time)
- R2. Public perception is that it is naïve; people do not believe in it.
- R3. Future station/inter-modal space will generate emissions, as it will be an attractor pole for travel.
- R4. Cruising for parking may be generated in the new neighborhood due to the inter-modal station
- R5. Technicians / technical experts can redirect, limit, and narrow the focus of debates.
- R6. That the participants are [not] sufficiently representative of the population; diversity not respected.
- R7. Lack of imagination on the part of the participants
- R8. Not having the technical support before the writing to know what needs to be taken into account when establishing the criteria.
- R9. Being too slow
- R10. Fragmented between departments and services in silos
- R11. Economic Feasibility
- R12. Segregation, gentrification, 'snobbery'
- R13. Generate high expectations that cannot be carried out due to a matter of space and topography
- R14. becoming an exclusively residential neighborhood:
- R15. Any modification of transportation routes must be agreed upon between 4 TRANSGRAN municipalities
- R16. Interlocutors are not accurately representative voices
- R17. Difficult to promote new and innovative model
- R18. Lack of political will or prioritization
- R19. Danger of technical design and regulatory solutions causing significant construction cost increases
- R20. Competition between climate neutral & resilient urban design, and social housing programs in terms of economic feasibility
- R21. That the results of the pilot do not become a standard/ reference for other neighborhoods.
- R22. Risk that responsibility for shared solutions is unclear or ineffective
- R23. Return expectations for the developer's initial investment
- R24. Cost-overruns in refurbishments & retrofitting

8.4.4. Adaptive Pathways Page for Lisbon

Adaptation Pathway

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Research and Innovation Actions under the grant agreement No 101019718

Risk Legend

- R1.** Funding Shortages - reduced funding for energy conversion projects
- R2.** Bureaucracy - overly bureaucratic financing process
- R3.** Level of decision - many decisions go beyond the neighborhood intervention/decision scale process
- R4.** Uncertainty on benefits of actions - lack of clear perception of how certain actions/projects/solutions contribute to a better quality of life and environmental sustainability
- R5.** Funding Shortages - Reduced funding for projects/equipment and little speed in processes.
- R6.** Lack of transparency of management and decision-making processes
- R7.** Communication that is too technical and hermetic, not understood by everyone
- R8.** High costs of recycled or reused materials
- R9.** Low technical capability for reduced real time monitoring
- R10.** Low replicability of solutions
- R11.** Bureaucracy - overly bureaucratic financing process
- R12.** Difficulty in articulation between all entities with responsibilities in the territory
- R13.** Existing conflicts between different urban and economic interests in the same territory

8.4.5. Adaptive Pathways Page for Milan

Risk Legend

- R1.** Lack of data useful for carrying out evaluations (e.g. climate data, population data, etc.).
- R2.** There are different methodologies for assessing ecosystem services, but none "official" justifying their use within a public administration.
- R3.** Lack of expertise in municipal staff to apply evaluation methodologies and manage the processes.
- R4.** Evaluation methods fail to really influence the decision-making process and thus the design of interventions
- R5.** Real estate operators may not be in favour of using an unofficial-unmandatory methodology for the evaluation of their projects.
- R6.** Some real estate operators use other methodologies/standards to assess the benefits of the interventions they carry out and may not have the expertise to use a specific methodology in the design of projects.
- R7.** Evaluation methods fail to really influence the decision-making process and thus the design of interventions.
- R8.** It sometimes happens that there are major changes between masterplans and final projects, with a reduction in the ecosystem value of green spaces.
- R9.** Real estate operators consider green spaces as a cost, both for their implementation and management and asking for more ecosystem services can also mean an increase of costs for their interventions. This problem also affects the municipality, which, a few years after the work has been carried out, regains possession of the green areas and has to manage them with its own resources.
- R10.** Real estate operators may be hesitant to adopt an unofficial-unmandatory methodology for the evaluation of their projects.
- R11.** The municipality may not be able to make new compensation calculation systems official due to a lack of regulatory recognition on a regional/national scale.
- R12.** Difficulty for the municipality to define the transversal orientations on which to concentrate with internal and external stakeholders.
- R13.** Low buy-in and long-term commitment of the stakeholders in Milan's governance framework.
- R14.** Lack of a unified understanding and common vision on the addressed thematic.

8.4.6. Adaptive Pathways Page for Münster

8.4.7. Adaptive Pathways Page for Thessaloniki

Adapted from: Thessaloniki

This project has received funding from the European Union under the grant agreement 101016466

Risk Legend

- R1. Car owners
- R2. Shopkeepers
- R3. Gentrification
- R4. Maturation
- R5. Cost
- R6. People with disabilities
- R7. Shop owners
- R8. Suppliers
- R9. Car owners
- R10. Political support
- R11. Conflict of interest
- R12. Removal of parking lots
- R13. Resources
- R14. Rejection of consultation results
- R15. Lack of physical design
- R16. Reactions
- R17. Vandalism
- R18. Reactions
- R19. Violations
- R20. Digital literacy
- R21. Lack of confidence
- R22. Refusal to cooperate by businesses
- R23. Lack of confidence

8.4.8. Adaptive Pathways Page for Zagreb

UP2030 This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101016426. Adaptive Information | 2 | Page 166